

Adoption of Cloud Computing for e-Learning in Higher Education

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DECLARATION

I, Isaiah Ewuzie, hereby declare that this research, including the primary work was carried out by me, for the award of a PhD degree in the School of Engineering and Computing, University of the West of Scotland.

Signature.....

Date.....

DEDICATION

I dedicate this research to the memory of my late brother, Mr Jeff Ewuzie.

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To God be the Glory for giving me the strength, energy, determination, knowledge and wisdom to accomplish this research.

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GLOSSARY

ARPANETA	Advanced Research Projects Agency Network
B.Sc	Bachelor of Science
CBL	Computer Based Learning
CBT	Computer Based Training
CSA	Cloud Security Alliance
CSE	Computer Self Efficacy
CSPs	Cloud Service Providers
DaaS	Data as a Service
DMS	Document Management System
DOI	Diffusion of Innovation
DoS	Denial of Service
DR	Disaster Recovery
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
ENISA	European Network and Information Security Agency
GUI	Graphic User Interface
HE	Higher Education
HEIs	Higher Educational Institutions
HESA	Higher Education Statistics Agency
HNC	Higher National Certificate
HND	Higher National Diploma
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IP	Internet Protocols
IS	Information Systems
IT	Information Technology

ITaaS	IT as a Service
ITDS	Information Technology and Digital Services
JIT	Just in Time
KS	Knowledge Source
LMS	Learning Management Systems
MBA	Masters of Business Administration
M.Eng	Master of Engineering
M.Sc	Master of Science
MOODLE	Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment
NHS	National Health Service
NIST	National Institutes of Standards and Technology
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PEOU	Perceived Ease of Use
PgD	Postgraduate Diploma
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PR	Perceived Resources
PU	Perceived Usefulness
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Relative Advantage
RGU	Robert Gordon University
ROI	Return on Investment
SaaS	Software as a Service
SMEs	Small Business Enterprises
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
SVQ	Scottish Vocational Qualification
TAM	Technology Adoption Model

TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TOE	Technology Organisation Environment
TR	Technology Readiness
TRA	Theory of Reasoned Action
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WebCT	Web Course Tool

ABSTRACT

Information Systems (IS) play a key role in modern business process and its adoption is critical for achieving competitive advantage. Technology and IS adoptions have been extensively researched and cloud computing has emerged as one of the major areas of research in recent years. That notwithstanding, research findings indicate that the rate of adoption and subsequent deployment within higher educational institutions (HEIs) is low when compared to other sectors. This low rate of adoption constitutes the key issue addressed by this research.

The increasing cost of higher education even with less public funding has necessitated the HEIs to look for ways of being competitive in the global market while improving their modes and methods of delivery. Cloud computing is seen as a potential solution for the HEIs to improve their e-learning systems because it has the capability for end users to seamlessly access data and applications from multiple devices and platforms.

The research therefore aimed to identify factors that could cause the problem and investigate how they could be used so as to achieve a high adoption for this important technology. To achieve this aim, a systematic secondary research was done and this revealed four key theoretical frameworks – Technology Adoption Model (TAM), Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE), Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI) and Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE). These frameworks along with a pilot study produced constructs that were related using hypotheses to form a conceptual model for this research. In the process, two new variables – cost and security - that were not part of the theoretical frameworks were added to the conceptual model.

Taking mainly a quantitative approach, except at the exploratory pilot study, the model was operationalised into a 42-item survey questionnaire that used a 5-point-Likert scale. After being pilot tested, the questionnaire was administered to 625 respondents via emails. 99 responded which resulted in the response rate of 15.8%. After correcting for item non-response and incomplete responses, the completed questionnaires were subjected to reliability tests before the actual data analysis.

Data analysis indicates that while technology, DOI and CES have positive relationships with adoption, organisation and environment do not show relationships with adoption due to a number of factors. Findings indicate that technological factors of adoption are significant in adoption of cloud computing.

The uniqueness of this research is that it studied adoption both from individual and organisational perspectives by combining variables from TAM, TOE, DOI and CSE. The study contributed by extending the TOE framework to include security (as one of the technology variables) and cost considerations. Findings indicate that both perspectives are important in relation to this study. The research combined the strength of TAM and TOE models to produce a hybrid model of adoption. If the research recommendations are well implemented, it will help institutions in their long term e-learning and IT strategy.

Future studies on adoption of e-learning technologies should consider it from users' perspective since this study was based on IT, teaching and management staff's perspectives.

CHAPTER 1- INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In recent years e-learning appear to be growing and are becoming widely accepted as a learning method. This growth and acceptability may not be unconnected to, among others, its flexibility to access, just in time delivery (JIT) and perceived cost effectiveness (Wang, 2011), and the potential and challenges it poses for education and learning (Cobcroft et al 2006), as well as the opportunity for creation, implementation and delivering of user specific applications anytime and anywhere. The growth and acceptability of e-learning and advances in information technology (IT) have resulted in a shift from the traditional learning methods to a more advanced form of learning through the use of the internet, thereby resulting in changes in the learning content, delivery and modes (McGuire and Gubbins, 2010).

There also seems to be rapid and drastic changes in the way and manner learning institutions and organisations conduct their businesses, brought about by advances in information technology (IT). These advances have given rise to developments and research in cloud computing. As the demand for education and the need to develop and improve e-learning solution increases, cloud computing is seen as a new direction for e-learning systems in order to keep pace with developments in technology (Pocatilu et al, 2010).

IT has been recognised as an integral part of business process. Cloud on the other hand tends to deliver new functionalities by using existing IT services that were previously considered impracticable (Marston et al, 2011). In academia, its potential for storage and collaboration is essential for research, dissemination, peer-review, critique and publication of materials considering the huge amount of data that are dynamically generated and stored during research (Thomas, 2011).

Several meanings of adoption have been proposed and cloud computing has also been viewed as an IT innovation. Therefore, within the context of IT, Damanpour (1991) describes adoption to involve the process of creation, development and execution of new ideas. Rogers (1983) describes adoption based on choice as to whether to fully make use of the innovation or not. IT innovation adoption can be triggered by change in business conditions (making it a requirement for the organisation to operate) and management decision i.e. such that innovation can bring improved efficiency and performance (Subramanian and Nilakanta 1996; cited by Hamed et al, 2012).

However, successful innovations in organisations depend on how well the innovation has been accepted by users, integrated within an organisation and used by individuals over time (Gopalakrishnan and Damanpour, 1997; Hammed et al, 2012). Considering the growth and acceptability of e-learning tools, the direction in which cloud computing is heading and the ubiquitous nature of Internet technologies and applications, there appears to be a slow rate of adoption compared to other businesses and organisations (Low et al 2011). The proposed study therefore aims to investigate the factors affecting the slow rate of adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in higher education with a view to developing a conceptual model. It is expected that the findings of this research will aid institutions of higher learning to make informed strategic decisions about adopting cloud computing considering its enormous potentials.

1.2 Gap in Knowledge

IT has continued to play a hugely important role in various walks of life and the impact on e-learning is visibly evident in the ability of learners and users to access, evaluate and use information to build knowledge and solve problems through the use of digital library (Neuman, 1997). The role of higher education as innovators and adopters of innovative IT cannot be overemphasised. This is because HE has been in the forefront of innovations. The development of first computers, four nodes of the ARPANET, and various breakthroughs in networking had their origins from different universities (Katz et al, 2010). Advances in IT bring new opportunities thus, enhancing teaching and learning while also helping learners to personalise their environment by using a range of tools to meet their requirements. It also has the potential to foster collaboration in the academia among researchers hence improving practice and learning outcomes (Thomas, 2011).

Businesswise, IT and Internet technologies have become integral parts of business process as firms are leveraging their potentials to transact business with their partners (Ercan, 2010) as well as improving their competitive advantage. The urgency to meet the dynamic needs and improve service delivery has subsequently led to growing acceptance of cloud by business communities, thus, cutting down costs but with greater flexibility, reliability and compliance.

In academia, cloud computing is also integral to the institutional processes thus, helping to improve e-learning contents, modes and method of delivery (see sections 2.9, 2.10 and 2.11 and for further detail).

However, the use of cloud computing for e-learning, research, teaching and learning; and collaborations etc. in academics only constitutes about 4%. The remaining 96% are comprised of industrial sectors and services (Mokhtar et al 2013). This low percentage of cloud adoption in the academics when compared to other sectors constitutes the key issue being addressed in this research.

Different factors have been identified which represents significant challenges in an effort to adopt emerging technology like cloud computing for e-learning in HE. Thomas (2011), is of the view that adoption of new and emerging technologies and pedagogies are difficult because HE is highly unstable and continuously evolving. Furthermore, instructors lack adequate skills for certain technological-supported technique. Therefore, learners are not adequately supported to develop essential skills. He therefore concluded that there is a slim chance of adoption of new technologies that may subsequently foster innovation in pedagogy. Lee (2008) posits that technology users are strongly motivated when they perceive the availability of vital resources (support training and equipment accessibility) thus, leading to better online learning adoption. Therefore instructors' lack of essential skills (Tomas, 2011) and inadequate support for learners (Lee, 2008) are important factors in the adoption of emerging technologies like cloud computing for HE.

Though cloud adoption and usage in HE is growing the level is low compared to other fields. Therefore, a sound theoretical framework and research model is needed to identify factors and their relationships affecting the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

1.3 Research Questions

In order to fill the identified gap, the following research questions have been formulated

- What factors are likely to influence the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE?
- How can these factors be combined to develop a theoretical model that can address the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE?

The figure below shows step by step approach to be adopted in order to solve the research problem.

Figure 1: Step by step approach to solving the research problem.

1.4 Aims and Objectives

This research is based on a number of previous research concepts. It therefore aims to investigate the low rate of cloud computing adoption for e-learning in HE with a view to developing a conceptual model. The following objectives have been formulated in order to achieve the aims:

- Conducting a critical review of the relationships between cloud computing adoption and e-learning.
- Identifying factors that are likely to influence adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE
- Evaluating the changes that are needed to aid the development of cloud model for e-learning organisations.
- Establishing the relationships between the identified factors.
- Developing a theoretical model that may be used in adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.
- Performing primary study to validate the research model.
- Performing of data analysis and discussion of findings.
- Presenting implications (recommendations) and framework that may act as platform for practice and future research.

1.5 Scope

This research is drawn from the e-learning and computing discipline (cloud) with adoption as part of the major element of the research. Considering the interdisciplinary nature and the vastness of the fields, an in-depth analysis and discussions of these disciplines are outside the scope of this research. However, an area of common interest which is about adoption within

the HE and various factors that may influence it forms the focal point of this research. These factors and many more issues about adoption will thoroughly be discussed in subsequent chapters.

1.6 Outline of the Theses

Brief descriptions of the chapters are given below.

Chapter 2: This chapter focuses on critically reviewing the existing literatures detailing different e-learning and cloud computing concepts and models. The chapter is concluded by detailing the relationship between e-learning, IT and cloud computing.

Chapter 3: In this chapter, different methodologies will be discussed and justification for the chosen method.

Chapter 4: This chapter discusses how the conceptual model and hypotheses were derived.

Chapter 5: This chapter focuses on the specific procedures that the research will employ in collecting data.

Chapter 6: This chapter will analyse the demographic characteristics and detailed analysis of data.

Chapter 7: This chapter focuses on the discussion and the presentation of the research findings.

Chapter 8: This chapter discusses the contributions to knowledge, implications, limitations and areas for further research.

Figure 2: Pictorial representation of the theses by chapters

CHAPTER 2- LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter begins with critical review of literatures and a presentation of major e-learning systems and tools and their categorisation. After that it presents detailed description of cloud computing concepts, service and deployment models. It then discusses the benefits of using cloud for e-learning, the role that IT plays and the relationship between e-learning, IT and cloud.

2.1 Defining E-learning

The term e-learning is not a new concept but the advent of the Internet has given it an entire new meaning and dimension; such that it has become a widely accepted way of learning. Such innovations as the Internet, broadband, digital videos and personal computers have made e-learning a commonplace and even more acceptable (Catherall 2005). The Internet and the World Wide Web are seen as the focal points of e-learning technologies since they are delivered via the web browser, such as the Internet Explorer. E-learning as the word suggests, simply means electronic learning which includes traditional electronic media such as video and more recent media as the Internet. It is an innovative approach for delivering well-designed, learner-centred, interactive and facilitated learning environments to anyone, anyplace and anytime (Dong et al, 2009). Therefore the use of any technology (computer based) that allows for delivery (online) of learning resources or communication between tutor and students is defined as e-learning (Catherall, 2005). E-learning is not a new concept; it is believed that the use of computers for teaching and learning dates back to the 1940s after the first modern stored program (Cook et al, 2007). The earliest application technologies for learning were focused on content delivery in the 1950s and 1960s mainly applying behaviourist models using early mainframes (Cook et al, 2007). Today it is widely used on different educational levels: continuous education, organisational training, academic courses, etc (Pocatilu et al, 2010).

Sun et al (2008) described e-learning as the paradigm of modern education considering the progress of information and communication technology development. It appears that many institutions of higher learning are already making the transition to online teaching and learning by contracting technology and courseware vendors to design the infrastructure needed to customize their own online programs (Ngai et al, 2007).

E-learning systems were initially provided as a means of helping teachers (not necessarily IT literate) to manage their content on the web by providing integrated tools for managing and

communicating with groups and recently enterprise systems such as student e-mails (Cook et al, 2007). Early generations of learning technology adopted tended to fulfil multi-facet roles; often combining e-learning research with support for practitioners in terms of the use of the technologies, and input at institutional levels in terms of strategy and policy (Conole et al, 2007). Nonetheless, e-learning systems have continued to evolve over the years with the introduction of computers, from computer based learning (CBL) to computer based training (CBT) and web based learning tools. In recent years e-learning appears to be conventional as many higher institutions now support one form of environment with web presence or another.

Various definitions of e-learning have been proposed over the years. Some researchers and authors describe it as a virtual classroom. To some others it is described in terms of storage of course materials. Hence, understanding technology that is included under e-learning will give a clearer meaning of term e-learning and its technology (Bostrom, 2003).

IEEE Learning Technology Standard Committee described a Web-based learning system as: “A learning technology system that uses Web-browsers as the primary means of interaction with learners, and the Internet or an intranet as the primary means of communication among its subsystems and with other systems” (Ngai et al, 2007). Some defined e-learning based on technology tools used to access it (Sun et al, 2008, Georgouli, 2011, Rodrigues et al, 2011).

It was Tavangarian et al. (2004) who argued that technology is inadequate as a descriptor. They stated that e-learning is not only procedural but also shows some transformation of an individual's experience into the individual's knowledge through the knowledge construction process. Ellis (2004) and Triacca et al. (2004) are of the opinion that some level of interactivity needs to be included to make the definition truly applicable in describing the learning experience. Bostrom (2003) defined e-learning based on time-place matrix; that is, technology that supports learning synchronously or asynchronously anywhere and anytime.

Table 1: The time-place matrix of e-learning environments (Bostrom, 2003).

Table 2: E-learning environment and key technologies (Bostrom, 2003).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Bostrom, R., (2003). E-learning: Facilitating learning through technology. *AMCIS 2003 Proceedings*, p. 419.

Georgouli (2011) shares the same view with Bostro (2003) in the categorisation of e-learning. However, Georgouli's definition is based on the active participation of learners and instructors for the synchronous process while asynchronous does not require the active participation of both learners and instructors. Considering communication methods and flexibility of time and place that the learning technologies offer, some argue that these systems would be better suited to the geographically dispersed learners (distance learning) with conflicting schedules (Pituch and Lee, 2006; Sanchez et al, 2013).

Though technologies may seem indispensable in providing e-learning solutions, it is important to focus on providing learning opportunities, participation and appropriate integration of technologies in the learning process rather than the characteristics of technology used (Turker and Gentry, 2009; Moore et al, 2010; Sanchez et al, 2013). Bostrom (2003) however argued that for e-learning to take place the following technologies are needed irrespective of the environment.

Table 3: Types and description of technologies in e-learning systems (Bostrom, 2003)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Bostrom, R., (2003). E-learning: Facilitating learning through technology. *AMCIS 2003 Proceedings*, p. 419.

2.2 E-learning Systems and Tools

Tools used to support e-learning cover a wide range of different applications. They include discussion forums, chat, file sharing, video conferences, shared whiteboards, e-portfolios, weblogs and wikis. Such tools can be used to support different activities involved in the learning process. In fact all learning activities and materials in a course are organized and managed by and within the system (Dalsgaard, 2006). They provide e-learning platforms that use the Internet as a delivery mechanism to allow students from all over the world to access various learning tools, thus leading to many businesses and institutions adopting such Web-based learning systems for their e-learning courses (Ngai et al, 2007). Furthermore there are possibilities of meeting preferred learners' style through integrating various learning contents according to the needs of the learner (Karaari et al, 2011).

The large availability of computers both in schools and at home and the ease of access to Internet has influenced in large the educational technology in recent years and has led to the development of the so-called "Web-Based Education" (Georgouli, 2011), thus making e-learning an important medium of instruction in higher institutions. Technology has capabilities that can aid and augment university education rather than replace the face to face method of teaching (Sanchez et al, 2013). Thus, the use of technologies and their integration in educational systems, evaluation of the existing programs and managing subsequent changes have been on the agenda of the European higher education environment.

Information technology (IT) however has been regarded as an essential tool in enhancing the competitiveness of the country's economy, driving businesses and organisations forward by improving performance and productivity (Tucker and Gentry 2009; Oliveira and Martins, 2011). The role of (IT) and Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) in teaching and learning therefore cannot be overemphasised. IT in teaching and learning has transformed how students learn by using more modern, efficient and effective alternatives such as e-learning thus resulting in changes in education process (Selim, 2007). IT is seen as a major tool that drives e-learning. Integrating e-learning into university courses has been aided due to the development in IT.

ICT plays a key role in innovation process and adapting to new teaching and learning approaches that it provides will help institutions keep in touch with the new social reality (Rodrigues et al, 2011). Advancement in ICT and increase in the use of the Internet have also brought lots of opportunities to instructional technologies. Learning institutions are providing a wide range of learning alternatives for students thus, leading to acquisition of knowledge by learners (Aydin and Tirkes 2010; Georgouli 2011; Sanchez et al 2013). To maximise the potential and to effectively support the implementation of new technology within the learning systems, there is however need to adequately train skilled manpower to handle the challenges ahead (Tucker and Gentry 2009; Sanchez et al 2013).

Sanchez et al (2013) points out the long standing debate that learning in the digital age is now focused on the student and not the teachers as a result of the impact of ICT. They argue that ICT and the Internet are not there to educate or replace teachers but to augment their role; thus, helping to improve the learning content, allowing students the flexibility of study plans and providing assessment tools. Furthermore, they highlighted the impact of Web 2.0 on both learners and learning content with the tendency to receive education via a variety of digital platforms. However, they advocated the need for teacher's guidance.

2.3 Learning Management Systems

Learning Management Systems (LMS) are dedicated application-software intended to manage the learning environment and synchronize production and dissemination of tasks (Georgouli, 2011 and Rodrigues et al, 2011). LMS are Virtual Learning Environments (VLE) that manage the log-in of registered users; course catalogues record data from learners as well as providing reports to management and is being used by institutions to advance learning (Aydin and Tirkes, 2010). According to Georgouli (2011) VLEs are based on the integration of external modules, plug-ins or web services. LMS have continued to evolve from course

management tools to high a level of interaction between instructors and learners (Albarrak, 2010). According to Sanchez et al (2013), many of these VLEs vary in complexity but with a common methodology. Some of the major and most widely used learning management tools are discussed below.

2.3.1 Massive Open Online Courses

Massive open online courses (MOOCs) as the name suggests, is an open access platform where large number of learners access educational contents online on an enormous scale. MOOCs are not necessarily associated with a university but rather a platform where scholars provide content of various forms to participants irrespective of time and place (Batuary, 2015; Kenedy, 2014).

MOOCs are relatively new but gained popularity in 2011 after video materials were released on the platform by Stanford University professors and since then, other platforms have emerged from different parts of the world (Batuary, 2015; Brahim and Sarirete, 2015). As with new technologies or innovations, MOOCs are expected to continue to evolve in approaches, processes, priorities, offerings etc with more research (Perna et al, 2014). In fact, deWaard et al (2011) described it as self-organising because it is continuously evolving and interacting with external environment. The table below summarises the major advantages of MOOCs.

Table 4: Advantages of MOOCs (Source: own, adapted from Batuary, 2015)

Advantages	Characteristics
Massive	It accommodates a very large number of users taking full length courses at the same time.
Open	There is no restriction thus; it is open (technology, software, resources, knowledge etc) to anyone with internet connectivity to participate and to take courses.
Participatory	It involves voluntary creation and sharing of materials; and interactions with contributors thus, enhancing participation.
Distributed	It involves sharing of information, files, materials and contents across a network of participants or learners in social learning environments that encourages discussions.

Despite empowering learners on a massive scale, there are also problems and criticisms associated with MOOCs just like any new technology or innovation. For instance, assessing

large number of learners has been considered problematic considering that multiple choice questions are being used. This may have led to further criticism that learners are not being equipped for creativity and novelty (Batuary, 2015). There are scepticisms on the quality of education being offered on MOOCs when compared to face-to-face teaching and learning; as survey conducted by Gallup suggests (Jaschik and Lederman, 2013; cited by Brahim and Sarirete, 2015).

Researchers also argue that measuring academic progress is currently an issue. This is because the milestones for measuring such progress are still undetermined as providers are yet to reach a consensus considering that MOOCs are still steadily evolving (Perna et al, 2014). Similarly, user outcome differ due to different characteristics of MOOCs. However, it remains unknown how these characteristics affects outcomes.

Furthermore, research indicates that completion rate is low with only about 10% on the average of the participants completing their courses (Brahimi and Sarirete, 2015; Perna et al, 2014). In addition, it remains uncertain if the cost implications associated with higher education has adequately been addressed by MOOCs (Perna et al, 2014).

MOOCs are noted to leverage the participatory power of contributors and learners. However, research by Kop et al (2011) shows that available support system for learners are inadequate. For example, 1,641 participants in PLENK2010 have only 4 facilitators while only 2 facilitators cater for over 700 participants.

2.3.2 Web Course Tools

Web course tools (WebCT) is known as one of the best course management systems available and it provides a number of learning tools (Ngai et al, 2007). It was originally developed at Canada's University of British Columbia by computer engineer Murray Goldberg. In 1995, Murray began searching for Web-based systems that could be applied to education. His research showed that the level of student satisfaction and academic performance could be improved by deploying educational resources based on Internet websites. He set about constructing a system to enable the creation of educational settings based on Web pages, and came up with the first version of WebCT. This virtual teaching platform enabled the creation of flexible learning environments on the Web with versatile, easy to learn and connected solutions (Sanchez et al, 2013) while promoting learning collaboratively, critical thinking and increased participation (Hazari, 2014).

WebCT was developed with the aim of helping faculties to improve instructional materials, thus, providing additional information and services through course website; where students can access materials. The main features of WebCT include:

- i. *Communication*: it allows for interaction and communication between students and the contents, students and instructors and student to student.
- ii. *Assessment and grading*: students are able to retrieve assignments and coursework irrespective of time and place. It also has features that allow for testing of students using a variety of methods including multiple choice, true or false, and short answer questions.
- iii. *Performance feedback mechanism*: this feature enables students-instructors engagement and interaction; and students are capable to view and obtain feedback on their assignments and grading.
- iv. *Collaboration*: the availability of bulletins, chat rooms, emails calendars etc make it easier for students to collaborate in work groups and discussion groups for assignments, coursework, group projects etc. This is particularly important because students are not limited by time and place (Wernet et al 2000).
- v. *Administration*: this allows for creating, importing, archiving of accounts and emails and discussion on graded assessment.

Hazari (2014) is of the opinion that web based instructions can foster a learning environment where students are engaged actively in applied knowledge at controlled pace thus, helping them to evolve during learning.

2.3.3 Blackboard

Blackboard Inc. is a software company based in Washington D.C. (USA) that was founded in 1997 as a consultancy with a contract with the non-profit IMS Global Learning Consortium. In 2006, Blackboard merged with the rival WebCT Company, and the product previously called WebCT became known as the Blackboard Learning System. (Sanchez et al, 2013).

Blackboard was designed to overcome complex application of other formal models thus, the flexibility in the architectures (Corkill, 1991) and it has become one of the leading LMS platforms and is mainly used for content delivery (Martin, 2008).

The three components of blackboard system are

1. *Knowledge sources*: knowledge sources (KSs) are independent units having the knowledge needed to solve problems.
2. *The blackboard*: the blackboard is the database containing input, solutions and data at various problem-solving stages.
3. *Control component*: is the unit that is independent of the individual KSs; directing problem-solving by allowing KSs to act in response to changes in the blackboard database (Corkill, 1991)

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Figure 3: Basic components of the blackboard model (Corkill, 1991)

Characteristics of Blackboard

Following this paragraph are some of the characteristics and potentials of blackboard system Corkill (1991).

- i. *Independence of expertise*: Blackboard has experts that are independent of other experts in a modular form i.e. knowledge source (KS). KS can be improved or removed due to performance related issues.
- ii. *Multiple approaches to problem solving problem*: the internal approach to problem solving used by KS is only visible from the back-end while the external approach is visible from the outside. However, different approaches (forward-chaining, linear-programming, neural network approach, procedural simulation etc) are important to the overall structure.

- iii. *Flexibility of information representation:* information that could be obtained from Blackboard is not restricted. Different applications allow for different types of information to be explored for solution and maintained on the platform.
- iv. *Regular language for interaction:* in addition to the flexibility of information, there is a common understanding of the language in order for the KS and experts to communicate, interact and interpret information. KS may consist of experts from different nationalities with different language thus; the use of jargons may limit communication.
- v. *Information positioning:* Blackboard is divided in such a way that related information is grouped into regions for easy retrieval. This method is commonly used where multiple blackboards or different levels are used to group related objects. In addition, blackboard sorts information using different matrices within each region e.g. numeric, alphabetical or by relevance. Sometimes contributions by KS may not be relevant at a time but are saved within the system. However, efficiency in retrieving information by KS when needed is dependent on the executing KS to quickly check for relevant information other information being used by a KS.
- vi. *Event-triggered activity:* contributions by KS and experts are triggered by events on blackboard thus, giving them opportunity to respond to such events. These events could be change, addition or removal of existing information and external events e.g. phone calls etc. Sometimes KS could specify the events of interest and would be notified whenever the event is triggered.
- vii. *Control:* to avoid chaos, some form of control and administration is needed. Control is responsible for overseeing and directing the course of problem solving. Similarly, control could affect the system effectiveness and efficiency as well as determine actions to take and in what order (Hayes-Roth, 1989). Control is done by taking into account the general benefits of the contributions that would be made by triggered KSs. Therefore, the most appropriate pending KS is selected for execution as soon as the currently executing KS is complete.
- viii. *Incremental solution:* solutions are added by the KSs as they become available after refinements. Having a solution go through series of refinements and improvements helps the KSs to offer a more robust solution and are added incrementally and at various stages in the process.

Disadvantages of Blackboard

Despite the aforementioned characteristics and potentials that blackboard possess, it also has disadvantages thus limiting its use in applications.

- a. They do not scale down therefore mainly used in complex applications.
- b. It is useful in prototyping but once developed it is no longer needed for the application to be re-implemented.
- c. Software specifically developed for blackboard applications are in short supply.
- d. Lack and shortage of technical skills (developers with experience and skills for building blackboard applications are in short supply).

2.3.4 Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment

Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment (Moodle) originated from Perth, Western Australia, in 1999 but not until the last few years that it began to gain popularity due to increase in demand for learning methodologies and technologies for e-learning. Today it is used across the world in about 227 countries with over 65 million users (<https://moodle.org/stats>).

It is a VLE and is one of the most commonly used LMSs. It has the ability to track learner's progress which can also be monitored by instructors and learners. Course information for a specific subject are organised in blocks containing general, administrative and support information, the rest are organised in a different way (Martín-Blas and Serrano-Fernández 2009).

Moodle enables teachers and instructors to provide graded assignments, lessons and to share documents, quizzes, workshops, chats, offering a forum for learners in a manner that is both easy and of high quality learning. It is specifically designed to help educators who want to create high quality on-line courses (Al-Ajlan & Zedan, 2008). It is an open source i.e. provides developer information, roadmap, and guide to access its source code.

Moodle is not without criticisms. Kumar et al (2011) argues that it does not provide formal model for future development. While Al-Ajlan and Zedan (2008) are of the opinion that it is complex and requires an administrator to work with the teachers and technicians. However, Berggren et al. (2005), cited by Martín-Blas and Serrano-Fernández (2009), argued that maintaining a clear and open line of communication for continuous exchange of ideas between Moodle lecturers and developers will eventually lead to the development of new versions and can be improved by implementing web-based peer assessment.

2.3.5 Sakai

Sakai was developed by 5 US universities (Michigan, Stanford, MIT, UC Berkeley, and Indiana) and was released to the public in 2005 and is managed today by the Sakai Foundation, which oversees its development and project roadmap. The application is programmed in Java and designed to be a service-oriented application suite. The initial idea was for collaborative learning environment; however it covers a wide range of commercial solutions.

There are two components of sakai: the sakai framework and the sakai tools. The sakai framework is in the form of a basic system that provide general services. On the hand, the tools are designed for specific purposes such as chat rooms and discussion boards with plug-in capabilities. Sakai tools can also be used for such services as retrieval of current user information (Yang and Allan, 2007).

Sakai is made up of four architectural layers: service, tools, presentation and aggregator. The services layer deals with data in the database and retrieved by either services or tools. The tools layer bridges the gap between data (services) and user interfaces (presentation layer). While the aggregator works with the presentation layer to deliver interfaces in an accessible and customisable way to the end-users (Allan and Yang, 2007).

Figure 4: Sakai architecture (Allan and Yang, 2007)

Sakai's main features include: general collaboration tools (blog, chat rooms, email archives, wikis) learning and teaching portfolio (assignments, grade book and module editor) and administration and management (announcement, resources, calendars discussions, wikis etc) are used in project management and administration (Allan and Yang, 2007).

Advantages

One of the major advantages of sakai is its flexibility and capability to be extended with other tools and services (Yang and Rob, 2007; Rob and Yang, 2007). For instance:

1. It formed the basis for the virtual research environment VRE and document management system DMS.

2. Integrated and used with web 2.0 for collaboration.
3. As an e-research environment, it is used to support users in multi institution VRE.

Disadvantages

Some of the disadvantages of sakai include:

1. Inability to work off line.
2. Inability to integrate with other institutional environments e.g. exchange server.

2.4 Some Major E-Learning Studies and Their Findings

This section summarises some of the major studies more specifically on e-learning and their findings. Importantly, these studies were carried out by either combining different constructs or adopting and adapting from other studies.

A critical look at the table (5) below shows that 6 out of 13 studies listed underlined the importance of technology or technical related factors in adoption of any technology. The rest highlighted and established the importance of management support, organisational effects, behavioural intentions, perceptions, attitudes etc to technology adoption. Based on the findings of the research discussed, it is apparent that these studies only considered the perspectives of the users irrespective of the constructs used. Although this study will combine different theories and models, it will consider both institutional and the user's perspectives. This is because decision on the type of e-learning platform or technology to be adopted and used lies with the management of the institution. Further details on the limitations of the individual theoretical underpinning and how this study combined their strengths are found in section 8.1.

On the other hand, Vankatesh (2000) though not specific to e-learning however, identified user perception as a key determinant factor in technology use. Fishbien and Ajzen (1975) measures attitude and beliefs with regards to use of technology. Furthermore, Oliveira and Martin (2011) reviewed literature on information technology adoption at firm level. The studies reviewed applied DOI, TOE framework as well as combining TOE framework with other theories and models. Their findings indicate that TOE framework explains innovations adoption at firm levels better than other theories, thus, they considered TOE framework to be more robust.

Table 5: Summary of e-learning literatures

Study	Methodology	Sample	Construct	Contributions/Findings
Sanchez, Hueros and Ordaz (2013)	Theoretical and survey	226 students of university of Huelva	Six constructs were used; technical support (TS), computer self-efficacy (CSE), perceived ease of use (PEOU), perceived usefulness (PU), attitude (A) and system usage (SU) to determine adoption and acceptance of WebCT.	The importance of technical support to students using WebCT systems; they are more motivated, keener and more receptive to WebCT platform.
Chien (2012)	Survey	314 employees of financial services industry in Taiwan	A combination of various constructs and items from Pituch and Lee (2006), Selim (2007), Campeau and Higgins (1995) and Chuang and YaNg (2006) were used.	The result showed that both system and computer factors significantly and positively influence the e-learning effectiveness. It also shows a correlation between higher computer self-efficacy and higher training effectiveness thus, supporting previous studies.
Chen (2011)	Theoretical and survey	626 university students.	Seven constructs adopted from Moore and Benbasat (1991) and Venkatesh et al (2003) were used but four were identified as major performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social	The result showed that technological expectancy and educational compatibility were important determinants of e-learning acceptance. Thus, it provides a theoretical basis that is empirically supported to further understand e-learning acceptance.

			influence (SI) and facilitating conditions (FC).	
Karaali, Gumussoy and Calisir (2011)	Theoretical and survey	546 blue-collar workers in automotive industry in Turkey.	Extended TAM to include social influence, facilitating conditions and anxiety as factors to use web-based learning systems.	The result showed that social influence was the most important factor for behavioural intention to use web-based learning systems. However, social influence, anxiety and facilitating conditions together with perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU) and attitude towards use are important variables affecting the acceptance of web-based learning systems. Thus, an extension of TAM.
Lin (2011)	Survey	256 university students.	Six construct (Attitude, continuance intention CI, frequency of negative critical incidence NCI, PEOU, PU and quality attributes cumulative satisfaction QAS) together with various construct measures.	Results show that negative critical incidents and attitude are the main determinants of the users' intention to continue using the e-learning, irrespective of their level of e-learning experience.
Lee, Hsieh and Ma (2011)	Survey	357 employees from four industries in Taiwan	Nine constructs were adapted which also included many factors and measurement items to determine employee's e-	Organisational and management support significantly affects perceived usefulness and intention to use. Thus, it provides insight of individual, organisational and task characteristics in

			learning systems acceptance.	predicting e-learning acceptance behaviour in the organisational context.
Lee (2010)	Survey	363 students enrolled on at least one course offered by e-learning service in the continuing education program.	Four theories – expectation confirmation model (ECM), technology acceptance (TAM), theory of planned behaviour (TPB) and flow theory were synthesised hypothesised to explain user's behaviour to continue using e-learning systems.	The high proportion of variation of continued intention to use e-learning is correlated to the extended ECM model. Also flow theory though new variable is compatible with TAM, TPB and ECM.
Wang and Wang (2009)	Survey	268 instructors from three universities in Taiwan.	Nine constructs consisting of 49 items were used.	Service quality contributed more to PEOU but together with systems quality and self-efficacy increased PEOU, thus, it emphasises the importance of providing timely and efficient assistance to instructors using web-based learning systems.
Lee (2008)	Theoretical	1,107 (810 undergraduate, 245 postgraduate and 51 college students)	Extended TAM for online learning systems that included perceived resources (PR). Two major aspects are intra-organisational and extra-organisational factors. Each factor also has three dimensions.	The result underlined the significance of the role of PR in adopting online learning; internal support and training and extra-university organisation significantly affects online learning adoption.
Selim	Theoretical	538	Four major	The study showed eight

(2007)	and survey	undergraduate students (enrolled in five 100-level mandatory lap top based courses)	categories of e-learning critical success factor were used (instructor characteristics, student characteristics, technology, and university support).	e-learning critical success factor (CSF) categories that can assist universities and instructors to efficiently and effectively adopt e-learning technologies.
Ngai, Poon and Chan (2007)	Theoretical and survey	836 students (undergraduate and postgraduate) of seven universities in Hong Kong	Extended TAM by adding technical support as an external factor that affects the acceptance of WebCT for higher education.	The result underlined the importance of user support (technical support) and training and the fundamental relationship between perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) with perceptions of users and the use of learning systems.
Pituch and Lee (2006)	Theoretical	259 college students in Taiwan with basic computer literacy and currently enrolled on computer course.	Three major characteristics critical to development of e-learning systems were used (system functionality, system interactivity and system response)	System characteristics impacts on the student use of e-learning systems were found to be consistent with the findings of previous studies. Also user's familiarity of a system may be an important determinant in adoption of that system.
Ong, Lai and Wang (2004)	Survey	140 engineers from six international organisations	CSE (four items were adapted from Compeau et al 1999), PU PEOU, perceived credibility, behavioural intentions to use (adopted from	The result strongly supports the extended TAM in predicting engineers' intention to use e-learning

			TAM)	
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2.5 Defining Cloud Computing

This research refers to cloud as cloud computing, cloud technologies and cloud services. The field of cloud computing is so vast that an in-depth analysis and discussion is outside the scope of this research. However, a brief definition and introduction to the concept of cloud computing will be a good starting point. An in depth discussion of cloud computing is from next section onwards.

Cloud computing is seen by some authors as not a new concept but an evolution of different computing resources and technologies at various times. These computing resources are combined to deliver new possibilities aided by high speed internetworks (Hugos & Hulitzky, 2011, Lin et al, 2009, Pocatilu et al, 2010, Sultan, 2009, Vouk, 2008, Weiss, 2007).

Some researchers are of the opinion that cloud is a new paradigm with new technologies, such as virtualisation (Buyya et al, 2009, Low et al, 2011, Goscinski and Brock, 2010, Ercan, 2010).

Also there seems to be a lack of consensus among authors and researchers on how cloud computing should be defined. Some have defined it based on its scalability and elasticity, others on its capabilities to be delivered and accessed in real time, while other definitions are based on cost considerations and on demand capabilities (Hugos & Hulitzky, 2011, Sultan, 2010).

Lin et al (2009) defined it based on three different perspectives of users:

- a) *For application and IT users:* it is IT as a service (ITaaS)—that is, delivery of computing, storage, and applications over the Internet from centralised data centres.
- b) *For Internet application developers:* it is an Internet-scale software development platform and runtime environment.
- c) *For infrastructure providers and administrators:* it is the massive distributed data centre infrastructure connected by IP networks.

Staten (2008) defined cloud computing as a pool of abstracted, highly scalable, and managed computing infrastructure capable of hosting end-customer applications and billed by consumption. Vaquero et al (2009) defined it from the technical perspective; viewed it as a

new concept associated with provision of computing infrastructures. These concepts shift the location of the infrastructure to the network to reduce the cost associated with management of hardware and software. Meanwhile, Buyya et al (2009) defined cloud computing as a type of parallel and distributed system consisting of a collection of inter-connected and virtualized computers that are dynamically provisioned and presented as one or more unified computing resource(s) based on service-level agreements established through negotiations between the service provider and consumers.

Though a lot more attempts have been made by authors, researchers and practitioners alike to define cloud computing, the definition in 2011 by The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) appears to be widely accepted in the cloud computing industry as it includes the key elements and characteristics of cloud computing. The NIST defined cloud computing as:

“A model for enabling convenient, on-demand network access to shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g. networks, servers, storage, applications and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction”.

The five key attributes of cloud computing as contained in the NIST definition 2011 are:

- *On-demand self-service:* Ability of consumers to access computing resources (e.g. server time and network storage) instantaneously and unilaterally without need for human interaction.
- *Broad network access:* Availability of computing resources and capabilities over the network (e.g. Internet) and accessed using various heterogeneous platforms (e.g. mobile phones, tablets, laptops and workstations).
- *Resource pooling:* The ability to pool providers’ computing resources to serve multiple consumers using a multi-tenant virtualisation model while dynamically meeting the needs of the consumer. With a pool based model the consumer has no control or knowledge of the exact location as the computing resources (storage, processing, etc) are virtualised.
- *Rapid elasticity:* Ability to provision instantaneously and dynamically based on particular needs and demands at any time.

Measured service: Being able to measure usage of computing resources with the use of metering mechanism such that resources are better controlled and monitored.

Figure 5: Common characteristics of cloud computing (NIST, 2011)

2.6 Cloud Computing Characteristics

Various definitions of cloud computing have been proposed (section 2.5). The reasons attributed to the lack of common definition of cloud computing includes but not limited to:

- i. Diverse background of cloud computing researchers thus, different viewpoints
- ii. The evolving nature of cloud computing technologies such as Web 2.0 and service oriented architecture
- iii. Lack of large scale deployment and usage (Wang et al, 2008).

Notwithstanding the lack of a common definition and description of cloud, common characteristics as noted from various researchers and authors are detailed in table 6 below.

Table 6: Summary of key characteristics of cloud as contained in definitions by different authors. (Source: own)

Authors	Software	Hardware	Service	Data	Scalability	Virtualisation	Network	Pay-Per-Use	SLA	No Upfront Cost
Buyya et al (2009)		√			√	√			√	
Low et al (2011)	√	√	√			√	√			
Ercan (2010)					√	√	√			
Lin et al (2009)	√	√	√				√			
NIST (2011)	√	√	√		√	√	√	√		
Pocatilu et al (2010)	√	√	√				√			
Staten (2008)	√	√			√	√		√		√
Vaquero et al (2009)		√	√		√	√		√	√	
Wang et al (2008)	√	√	√	√						
Weiss (2007)	√	√	√		√		√			
Total	7	9	7	1	6	6	6	3	2	1

2.7 Cloud Computing Models

In addition to the five distinguishing attributes discussed in the foregoing paragraph, cloud computing models are classified based on service provided and method of deployment. Cloud service models are: Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) and the recently emerging Data as a Service (DaaS) that delivers virtualised specific data on demand. Cloud deployment models are: private cloud, community cloud, public cloud and hybrid cloud. Sections (2.7.2 and 2.7.3) provide detailed discussion on service and deployment models of cloud.

2.7.1 Cloud Business Models

Cloud computing models are classified based on the services provided and the method of deployment. However, before detailed discussions on the actual classification and methods of deployment of cloud models, it is imperative to have a broader view of cloud business model. Rappa (2004) defined a business model as a method of doing business, specifying what a company does to create value, how it is situated among upstream and downstream partners in the value chain, and the type of arrangement it has with its customers to generate revenue.

According to Rappa, utility services are shaped by a combination of characteristics: necessity, reliability, usability, utilisation, scalability and exclusivity.

Weinhardt et al (2009) identified pay-per-use and subscription as the most frequently used by consumers. He points out consumers overall understanding of the pricing model as the reason for their preference. Dynamic pricing however are calculated as a result of varying supply and demands.

Table 7: Cloud business models (Weinhardt et al, 2009), * free up to limited contingent e.g. 5GB or 7GB.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Weinhardt, C., Anandasivam, A., Blau, B., Borissov, N., Meinel, T., Michalk, W and Stober, J, (2009). Cloud Computing - A Classification, Business Models and Research Directions. *Business and Information Systems and Engineering*, 1 (5), pp. 391-399.

Bakhtiar and Razavi (2011) are of the view that IaaS is the best solution for metered model as this model is applied to standardised and possibly regulated products that make up the IaaS layer e.g. processing power and use of storage devices. Further, they argued that it will be

difficult applying the same model to PaaS. Rather they suggested that it should be merged with the cost of infrastructure since consumers never see, therefore never consider this layer. Since SaaS layer has numerous products especially QoS, Bakhtiar and Razavi suggests subscription and the pay-as-you-go pricing model.

Table 8: Business model of utility services (Rappa, 2004).

Types of Service	Business Models
Water	Metered service
Electricity	Metered service
Transport (common carrier)	Pay-as-you-go for one way/round trip. Subscription for commuter service
<i>Telephone:</i>	
Post	Subscription for local service; metered usage for long distance service
Cellular	Subscription with usage limits; metered usage in excess of the subscription limit equipment purchased or bundled with subscription
<i>Radio and TV</i>	
Terrestrial	Advertiser - sponsored, community sponsored
Satellite	Subscription (basic and premium services). Lease or purchase equipment
Cable	Subscription (basic and premium services). Pay-per-view for special programmes.
<i>Internet Access</i>	
DSL	Subscription (unlimited service). Leased equipment is unbundled with service
Cable	Subscription (unlimited service). Leased equipment is unbundled with service
Dial Up	Subscription (unlimited service) or metered service. equipment is purchased

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2.7.2 Cloud Service Models

As mentioned briefly in section 2.7, the major cloud service models that have been proposed and are widely used in the cloud industry include:

Software as a Service (SaaS). SaaS is distribution model that can be accessed over a cloud infrastructure by consumers using various client devices, employing either a multi-tenancy system architecture or single thin client interface. The vendor or service providers are solely responsible for control and management of the cloud infrastructure (network, servers, operating systems, storage, etc). User's control may be limited over specific application settings. SaaS essentially delivers software services on demand across the Internet, cushioning the cost effect of purchase price and licensing which have been integral parts of IT expenses for organisations. The reduced cost has thus led to increase in demand for SaaS services (Bakhtair and Razavi, 2011).

Platform as a Service

Platform as a Service (PaaS) provides development capabilities presented to the consumers to develop services and applications onto cloud infrastructure using tools supported by the vendor, e.g. Google AppEngine, Microsoft Azure, IBM sMash, Tibco Silver etc. PaaS is the focal point of cloud computing and the engine room of software infrastructure and operating systems, proving environment for cloud developers with benefits such as: automatic scaling and load balancing, authentication and communication services and graphic user interface (GUI) components (Bakhtair and Razavi, 2011). While SaaS is a distribution model for making available completed and hosted cloud applications, PaaS provides the development platform. Therefore successful cloud enterprise is dependent on the PaaS operating systems/middleware providing seamless integration of various systems (Bakhtair and Razavi, 2011). The control and management of infrastructure are however, the responsibility of the vendor with consumers having little control like application settings.

Infrastructure as a Service

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) is a provision model in which cloud consumers use IT infrastructures and resources (processing, storage, networks etc) in the cloud to deploy and run software which may include operating systems and applications. IaaS is modelled after utility services that are formed by a combination of characteristics which according to Rappa (2004) include: necessity, reliability, usability, utilisation rates, scalability and service distinction. Bakhtiar and Razavi (2011) proposed commoditization as a characteristic and according to them, all utility companies offer virtually products that are standardised or commoditised. Furthermore, Bakhtiar and Razavi proposed factors to be considered by IaaS vendors both for investment and pricing models; they include:

- i. Infrastructure necessary for efficient operations of customer's business; therefore interruptions may have both financial and legal implications.
- ii. Service availability irrespective of time and place of user.
- iii. Minimal interference irrespective of the complexities of the technology
- iv. Scalability to meet the dynamic demands of the users.
- v. Determination by IaaS providers of a realistic threshold beyond which the quality of service may drop.
- vi. Legal issues that arise from customers using physical infrastructures outside the customer's national boundaries.

Data as a Service

Data as a Service (DaaS) is emerging as a cloud service model that supports web service and service oriented architecture (SOA). DaaS is the delivery of virtualised specific data on demand, employing pay-as-you-go model, where consumers pay for the actual usage with the flexibility of scaling up or down depending on their dynamic needs.

Figure 6: Cloud computing layers (Source: own)

2.7.3 Cloud Deployment Models

There are three cloud deployment models which in effect are the cloud types. They are: private, public and hybrid models.

- *Private cloud.* The cloud infrastructure is provisioned for one organisation but may comprise of multiple users. It may be managed by the organisation and or third party. Since many more organisations are increasingly concerned about security and privacy, private clouds are designed to give organisations a lot more control behind a firewall.
- *Public cloud.* Provisioned for the general public to access computing resources over the Internet via a web service interface, usually on a pay-as-you-go pricing model. It is the commonest type of cloud deployment model with the focus on giving the public full ownership of management and control. Businesses, academic and government organisations use this type of cloud infrastructure and it is situated on the premises of the provider. They offer a large pool of scalable resources on a temporary basis without the need for capital investment infrastructure (Kizza, 2013).
- *Hybrid cloud.* Cloud infrastructure comprising two or more clouds (private, community or public). In hybrid cloud the uniqueness of each of the entities are maintained but with a standardisation in technology to enable data application portability.

Figure 7: Classification of service and deployment models of cloud computing (Source: own)

2.8 Cloud Computing Adoption Studies

Literature indicates that different cloud computing adoption studies have been undertaken by researchers cutting across a variety of industries and are summarised in table 9 below. Most of these studies used survey or interview methodology for data collection. Similarly, theoretical underpinning and frameworks that were used for these studies were either combined or adopted and adapted from existing constructs. Thus, this research will combine and adapt from existing studies and constructs also.

Specifically, only three of the ten studies in the table are related to academic institutions. Though the findings and conclusions vary, the studies however, highlighted the importance of technological factors in cloud computing adoption.

Table 9: Summary of cloud computing adoption studies

Study	Methodology	Sample	Construct	Findings
Behrend,	Theoreti	Students from	TAM 3 was	Ease of use, access to

Wiebe, London and Johnson, (2011).	cal and Survey	two community colleges. 142 from rural college and 618 from urban college	adapted and factors that may influence ease of use and usefulness were grouped according to students attitudes situational factors and students experience	alternative tools were factors in adoption and usage of cloud computing.
Safar, Safari and Hasanzadeh, (2014).	Survey	22 university experts, 30 IT professionals in 15 IT enterprises	TOE, DOI (adapted) to include security and privacy, IT resource, sharing and collaboration culture and social influence	Technology construct, (relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, observability and security and privacy), Organization (IT resource, sharing and collaboration culture) and environment (competitive pressure, social influence) are influential in the adoption of SaaS.
Sabi, Uzoka, Langmia and Njeh, (2016).	Survey	35 academics attending ICT conference in Yaounde, Cameroun.	DOI and TAM constructs were extended to include result demonstrable, economic factors (cost), technological factors (risk, data security), contextual factors (infrastructure,	The preliminary results from the pilot study indicate that the reliability of the constructs was established. The validated study will then be used for the larger scale study.

			socio-cultural, awareness)	
Low, Chen and Wu, (2011).	Survey	128 high tech firms in Taiwan	TOE framework	Complexity, compatibility and relative advantage could be barriers to adoption. Trading partner pressure is an influential factor affecting adoption.
Alshamaila, Papagiannidis and Li, (2012).	Theoretical and Semi structured interview	15 SMEs and service providers in the north east of England	Extended TOE framework to include uncertainty, innovativeness, prior IT experience, industry, market scope; and supplier efforts and external computing support.	relative advantage, uncertainty, geo-restriction, compatibility, trialability, size, top management support, prior experience, innovativeness, industry, market scope, supplier efforts and external computing support.
Senyo, Effah and Aday, (2016).	Survey	305 organisations from different industries in Ghana	TAM construct were extended to include security concerns and regulatory support	Relative advantage, security concern, top management support, technology readiness, competitive pressure and trading partners' pressure were the TOE factors found to be significant in cloud computing adoption in a developing country context.
Lian, Yen	Survey	CIOs from 106	TOE framework	Technology, human and

and Wang, (2014).		large medical centres and metropolitan hospitals were surveyed	and HOF-fit model were combined into a four dimensional model (human, technology, organisation and environment).	environment are found to be critical in adoption of cloud while data security has opposite effect on adoption.
Gutierrez, Boukrami and Lumsden, (2015).	Survey	257 mid-to-senior level decision making business and IT professionals	TOE framework	Competitive pressure, complexity, technology readiness, and trading partner pressure were significant in adoption of cloud computing.
Lin and Chen, (2012).	Theoretical/ interview	19 middle to senior IT managers in Taiwan	DOI	Compatibility is a significant factor in adoption, no relative advantage of cloud computing is identified and lack of standards affect adoption.
Tarhini, Masadeh, Al-Badi, Almajali and Alrabayah, (2017)	Survey	205 staff working in Aqaba city hotels in Jordan.	Theoretical framework	Competitive pressure and top management support affect adoption of cloud computing. Ease of use, usefulness and CSE does not affect adoption.

2.9 Cloud Computing Benefits for E-learning

The rapid advancement in the Internet technologies, personal computers, tablets and mobile devices have made computing ubiquitous (Bakhtiar and Razavi, 2011), thus becoming part of our everyday life. Such has led to businesses and institutions taking full advantage of the ubiquitous nature of today's computing to compete in global markets and move their businesses forward. In fact, cloud technology has the power to fundamentally shift competitive landscape by providing a new platform for creating and delivering business value (Berman et al, 2012).

Cloud computing has enormous advantages and benefits, which if properly harnessed will take e-learning and higher education forward. Latest software and hardware attracts students, keep pace with rapid advancement in digital technologies and cloud is seen as a means of achieving these ambitions at an affordable cost too (Sultan, 2010), thereby making institutions much more competitive.

Research so far shows that cost savings appear to be one the major indicators for cloud adoption by organisation. The cloud flexible pricing model (pay-as-you-go) has the potential to reduce fixed IT costs from capital expenses to operational expenses (no need for hardware and software installation; upgrade and license cost is moved to data centre level) thereby; allowing organisations to pay for what is actually needed and when it is needed (Pocatilu et al, 2010; Berman et al, 2012). Pocalitu et al (2010) posits that e-learning can specifically benefit from cloud:

- i. *Infrastructure*: by using e-learning solution on provider's infrastructure
- ii. *Platform*: by developing an e-learning solution based on the provider's development interface
- iii. *Service*: by using the e-learning solution given by the provider

Dillion et al (2010), however, argues that the cost of migration to and from the community cloud and the cost per unit of VMs of computing resources as well as integration cost are likely to be higher, due to different cloud vendors using proprietary protocols and interfaces.

Security is seen both as an inhibitor and a driver for adoption in emerging and developed markets. It is projected that security will further drive adoption within the next five years due to cloud service providers (CPS) devoting more resources to security than typical IT organisation's department facing budget cuts (Cisco/Intel study, 2013; Ernst and Young, 2010). This argument is also supported by Alecu (2010) who suggested that with centralised

data storage, monitoring data access, virtualisation and logging, organisations are able to effectively manage resources to secure their data. Assuncao et al (2009) also lend credence to the above argument by stating the benefits of virtualisation; amongst them is enhanced security through the creation of sandboxes for running application with uncertain reliability. Thus, with virtualisation security issues intrinsic to the sharing of resources among multiple computing locations are minimised.

Furthermore, the method of cloud provisioning seems attractive to both developers and other end-users including HEIs. It allows for self-deployment of computing resources like servers, networks, storage and various application infrastructures thereby limiting the complexities while being able to monitor and manage dynamic infrastructure and platform requirements (Rimal et al, 2010; Kizza, 2013).

Other drivers or enablers of cloud adoption which in effect, are the key attributes of cloud computing have also been discussed and summarised in section 2.5 and figure 5.

2.10 Higher Education and the IT Infrastructure

The demand for higher education is increasing due to a number of factors e.g. growth in the world's population. Staff and students mobility are also on the increase due to globalisation. Therefore, IT plays a significant role in ameliorating the pressure on the demand for places in higher institutions and the associated increase in cost (Allison et al, 2012). In order for higher institutions to gain competitive advantage in response to the demands of globalisation, they are increasingly enhancing their strategic profile which includes the development of international pedagogy that can appeal to the international students. This demand has also affected the method of teaching, learning and delivery with much reliance on IT in order to enhance online courses in content and availability (Mellors-Bourne et al, 2013). Major challenges facing educational institutions in the UK as identified in the 2011 Horizon Report (Johnson and Adams, 2011) in relation to technology are:

- Economic pressures and new ways of education have necessitated a change in the way education is delivered e.g. streaming of introductory courses. Thus, institutions are challenged in supporting continuous growth and engagement with the students by the use of the tools.
- Teachers are increasingly expected to teach digital citizenship. However, there is no consensus as what constitutes online etiquette as it varies from community to community or culture to culture.

- Current technologies do not adequately support the demand for personalised learning.
- Financial gap exists among students and the various institutions. Thus, not all students and institutions are able to afford the current technologies.
- Lack of training means that institutions are not availing themselves of the opportunities that the current trends in technology provide.
- Digital literacy is vital in every profession. However, rapid changes and developments in technology mean that institutions are unable to keep pace.

Besides teaching, learning and the method of delivery, ubiquitous nature of IT infrastructure has also affected every facet of our living. Students are increasingly personalising their studies and learning choices through the use of these devices (Mattila, 2015). It is imperative to note that this trend in modern education is only feasible and delivered via the web. Therefore, HE institutions are constantly availing themselves of the opportunities to exploit and share teaching capabilities, learning resources and content management through their online presence (Allison et al, 2012). Similarly, with the use of IT and delivering of online classes more students are reached who may not otherwise have the opportunity of HE considering the distance. IT in HE can also be used to solve such problems as teaching a large group and issues associated with face-to-face teaching and learning methods (Risqueuz and Moore, 2013).

Despite the perceived advantages of using IT in HE such as the ability to reach a wider audience, personalised learning contents and choices, the ability to deliver classes synchronously and asynchronously; and dealing with problem associated with large group, the use of IT in HE is not without criticisms. Critics are of the opinion that the use of IT in HE has not delivered the level of impact that was initially envisaged. Rather, human interaction associated with face-to-face method of teaching and learning is gradually being eliminated; and technology and resource costs are also similar to the conventional teaching (Risqueuz and Moore, 2013). Further, they identified inability of the teaching staff to adapt to the rapid changes in technology, perceptions and attitude towards technology and change, security issues, propensity to focus on IT problems rather than course contents and design; and fear of the unknown as some of the challenges especially as regards to adoption of new technology. Likewise, Riliskis and Osipov (2013) are of the opinion that the current IT infrastructures are ineffective and inadequate to cater for the increasing demands despite the increased cost of purchase and maintenance.

2.11 Relationship between E-learning, IT and Cloud Computing

The term e-learning denotes learning conducted through electronic media usually the internet and its emergence has transformed the academic landscape. Notwithstanding the obvious advantages, e-learning have shortcomings e.g. the lack of scalability and inability to deal with dynamic demand of storage (Dong et al, 2009) especially consider the demand for online education. Phaphoom (2012) points out the high costs involved in infrastructure, bandwidth, installation and integration. These limitations and other issues associated with e-learning have given rise to new techniques, methodologies and processes that cloud provides and are being adopted by higher institutions (Masud and Huang, 2012). Cloud overcomes the complexities involved with hardware and software configuration in e-learning and is interoperable. Furthermore, it has the potential to deliver dynamic mobile interactive computational services by exploiting and leveraging integrated IT infrastructure as well as ability to be metered like gas and electricity which are not obtainable in the current e-learning systems (Ivanov, 2011; Feuerlicht et al, 2010). Communication and collaborations have become integral parts of modern HE process. Thus cloud's social interactivity and collaborative features make it suited and attractive to virtual communities of educators, researchers and practitioners alike for organising teaching portfolio, presentation, critical review and evaluation and self-reporting of e-portfolios. For example, researches and projects are increasingly involving more business units across multiple locations thus, more emphasis on collaboration at various stages of project development (Thomas, 2011). Gonzalez-Martinez et al (2015) categorised the benefits of cloud as it affects educational practitioners, students, IT staff and the educational institutions. Similarly, Masud et al (2012) categorised the impact of cloud on education for students, teachers and research.

E-learning on the one hand is regarded as an upgrade of the conventional face-to-face method of teaching and learning. On the other hand, cloud can be viewed as the future. IT however, lies at the intersection linking HE institutions with various technologies for teaching, learning and research; connecting the past, present and the future. Martin et al (2011) in their research on new technology trends in education noted that new technology have influenced all aspects of human endeavour including education. They are of the opinion that education has improved and this improvements is not necessarily determined by technology but researchers appear to focus more attention on improving education using new technology. They identified social web (the use of web 2.0 and social networks) and mobile devices as essential technologies for the future of education. The figure below illustrates the relationship between e-learning, IT and cloud computing in relation to HE. It shows that IT is a common factor

linking HEIs and their e-learning platforms. On the other hand cloud is linked to current trends and advancement in IT (see also section 2.5) thus, has its foundations in IT. It could therefore be argued that without IT there will be no relationship between HEIs, e-learning and cloud computing.

Figure 8: IT as a linkage between HEIs, e-learning and cloud computing (Source: own)

Notwithstanding that cloud have the potentials to bridge the gap and alleviate some of the problems with e-learning, it also has its shortcomings. With increased options and features of evolving technologies like cloud, comes confusion and perhaps resistance to change by the HE institutions (Ivanov, 2012). Most of the limitations and factors affecting adoption of cloud computing for e-learning are discussed in chapter 7.

In conclusion, this chapter discussed e-learning systems and tools as well as their categorisation. Thereafter, it presented detailed description of cloud computing concepts, services and deployment models. Finally, it discussed the benefits of using cloud computing for e-learning, role of IT infrastructure in higher education as well as relationship between e-learning, IT and cloud computing.

CHAPTER 3- RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to formulate the primary research questions, the main objectives of the research are examined. In this chapter various research methods, the appropriateness of the chosen method and justification are discussed. What immediately follows this paragraph is a discussion of the key objectives and research questions in order to justify the chosen methodology.

3.1 Key Research Objectives

The aim of the research is to investigate factors affecting adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE with a view to developing and empirically testing a cloud adoption model for e-learning in HE.

Factors affecting technology use are complex and they include personal aspects such as cognitive, affective and contextual factors (Straub, 2009). User acceptance of IT is a fundamental factor in technology adoption and implementation (Hammed et al 2012). It is therefore imperative to consider a framework that encompasses cognitive, affective and contextual factors in adoption and implementation of cloud computing in HE. A research model appropriate for the factors considered critical in adoption and implementation of cloud computing in HE was formulated.

3.1.1 Key Research Questions

There are three main elements on which this research is focused – adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE, assessing how cloud computing will efficiently support e-learning; the factors that will influence adoption of cloud computing for e-learning; and how the factors will be combined to develop a model for cloud adoption. Thus, the research questions formulated are as follows:

1. What factors are likely to influence the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE?
2. How can these factors be combined to develop a theoretical model that can address the use of cloud computing for e-learning in HE?

3.2 Ontological and Epistemological Justification

The ontological perspective of this research is that the phenomenon under study is viewed objectively. Furthermore, several factors influence adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE (discussed in a later chapter). Thus, these factors that influence outcome, utility of interventions, understanding the predictors of outcome and to test theory or explanations are better suited to quantitative approach (Creswell, 2014 transfer event). This

study is underpinned by positivist paradigms. As previously discussed the aim of the research is to investigate factors affecting adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE with a view to developing and empirically testing a cloud adoption model for e-learning in HE. Thus, from the ontological perspective all evidences that will lend credence to the aims of the research were examined independent of the researcher's perceptions. In effect, when analysed they will also help determine if the formulated hypotheses holds or otherwise.

The epistemological view of this research is aligned with positivist stance except at the pilot study stage when the investigation was exploratory (section 5.3). The survey sampling covered a wide geographical location limited to specific sections of the population thus, have ramifications on how the knowledge is obtained. Data are acquired for this study through surveying multiple sources from the population.

3.3 Research Paradigms

In this section the underlying methodologies that could be used to answer the research questions are discussed. There are different beliefs, norms and values otherwise known as paradigms on which researches are based. Therefore, these beliefs, assumptions, types of research being undertaken, personal experiences and the audience that the research is being carried out for will influence the approach adopted by the researcher (Creswell, 2014). In other words, paradigm represents a set of beliefs or values upon which the researcher justifies his or her research choices. A research paradigm sets the limits for the research method that develops within a given paradigm. However, ontology is generally regarded as the starting point for researchers.

Ontology describes the nature of physical and social reality or entities, i.e. the nature of reality (Oates, 2010; Bryman and Bell, 2011) and how each researcher differs in their beliefs (Creswell, 2016). In other words, ontology is mainly concerned with *what* exists. It is imperative however, for the researcher to decide if the social realities or entities are considered to be objective entities, external to the researcher, or socially constructed based on his perception (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Epistemology describes the nature of knowledge and answers a key question of *how* it can be obtained (Oates, 2010). In other words, it describes the relationship between the researcher and what is being researched (Creswell, 2016).

Besides ontological and epistemological assumptions, this study also examines the axiological and methodology questions that are bordering it. Axiology describes beliefs in the use of values and bias of both the researcher and what is being researched and how they

differ from paradigm to paradigm (Creswell, 2016). Methodology relates to the research process and how they vary from the one that is being adopted for a particular study (Creswell, 2016). Modern research methods are classified into two broad categories: positivist and interpretivist.

3.3.1 Positivism

Positivism describes objectivity or existence of order in the universe. In other words, it is predicated on assumption and objectivity rather than investigation (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Since positivism is characterised by scientific methods - observation, formulation and testing of theory and hypotheses - observing results, confirming or refuting hypotheses as well as modifying or rejecting theory (Oates, 2010), it is sometimes referred to as *scientific*.

From positivist's *ontological* assumptions, social realities are detached from the researcher. Thus, only one reality exists irrespective of the researcher's perceptions or beliefs (Collis and Hussey, 2014). From *epistemological* point of view, positivists believe in the validity of knowledge if it can be replicated, repeated and non-refuted. The phenomena under study must be observable and measurable (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Although intervention is possible, the researcher must be objective and not influence the study and the participants in any way. In other words, the researcher is neutral and reports only the facts irrespective of his or her personal values and beliefs (*axiology*). Through a *positivist methodology*, the researcher formulates and tests the hypotheses to determine if they hold or not. Positivism is not without criticisms.

Reductionism: sometimes the phenomenon being studied is so complex that trying to capture it at once may lead to missing the big picture (Oates, 2010). It is not always possible for everybody to view things the same way; therefore, it is imperative to understand how people view and interpret their world by examining the perceptions they have of their activities (Collis and Hussey, 2014; Oates, 2010).

3.3.2 Interpretivism

The *ontological* perspective of the interpretivists is that social reality is not objective but subjective and constructed by people based on their perception (Collis and Hussey, 2014); as such, there are multiple realities. From the *epistemological* viewpoint, the researcher situates and interacts themselves as closely as possible with what is being researched since it is impossible to make a distinction between the social phenomenon and the thoughts of the researcher (Creswell, 2014). That is, the researcher cannot be detached from the subject being

researched as there is a link between the two. In distinguishing the interpretivist paradigm from the positivist paradigm, interpretivist tends to investigate and explain the complexity of social reality in order to gain understanding of the interdependencies of the social settings (Collis and Hussey, 2014; Oates, 2014), whereas positivism is focused on determining social phenomenon (Collis and Hussey, 2014). The *axiological* assumption is that researches are value-laden since the researcher cannot be detached from what is being researched. Therefore, these values, experiences and participants' views, coupled with interactions from that of the researcher help to draw interpretations and analysis. From the *methodological* point of view, patterns and/or theories can only be developed through analysing respondents' responses from the survey.

Table 10: Assumptions of the two main research paradigms, Creswell (2014).

Philosophical Assumptions	Positivism	Interpretivism
Ontological assumptions (the nature of reality)	Social reality is objective and external to the researcher.	Social reality is subjective and socially constructed.
	There is only one reality.	There are multiple realities.
Epistemological assumptions (what constitutes valid knowledge)	Knowledge comes from objective evidence about observable and measurable phenomena.	Knowledge comes from subjective evidence from participants.
	The researcher is distance from phenomena under study.	The researcher interacts with phenomena.
Axiological assumptions (the role of values)	The research is independent from phenomena under study.	The research acknowledges that the research is subjective.
	The results are unbiased and value-free.	Findings are biased and value-laden.
Rhetorical assumption (the language of the research)	The researcher uses passive voice, accepted quantitative words and set definitions.	The researcher uses personal voice, accepted qualitative terms and

		limited a priori definitions.
Methodological assumptions	The researcher takes a deductive approach.	The researcher takes inductive approach.
	The researcher studies cause and effect, and uses a static design where categories are identified in advance.	The researcher studies topic within its context and uses an emerging design where categories are identified during the process.
	Generalisation leads to prediction, explanation and understanding.	Patter and/or theories are developed for understanding.
	Results are accurate and reliable through validity and reliability.	Findings are accurate reliable through verification.

The research paradigms and methodologies discussed herein give a general overview of how different paradigms and methodologies relate to different types of research and research approach; and how they are used to answer research questions. Comparing the paradigms also helps to present a paradigm that suits the type of research being undertaking. It also explains how the phenomenon under study is viewed and influenced by the researcher and the outcome of the research. The next section explains chosen methodology and the justification as it specifically relates to this research.

3.4 Chosen Methodology

Before discussing the actual methodology adopted for this research, it is important to distinguish between methodology and method. Methodology is the approach to the process of the research, including the methods while method is the actual technique or procedure employed for collecting and/or analysing of data (Collis and Hussey, 2014). The three main methods are: quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods.

Quantitative Methods: These methods are normally used in studies that tend to test a theory. They specify hypotheses and the collection of data to support or disprove the hypotheses.

Data are usually collected using instruments that measure attitudes and are analysed using statistical procedures and hypotheses testing (Creswell, 2014). This method is favoured by the positivists.

Qualitative methods: Unlike quantitative methods, qualitative methods provide extensive explanation for behaviour and attitudes. In order to understand phenomenon being studied, the researcher uses participants and data collection is by observing participants' behaviour during activity interaction and engagement.

Mixed methods: Mixed methods involve integration of both quantitative and qualitative methods. They incorporate both open-ended and closed-ended questions and data are collected from multiple sources. The basic idea behind mixed methods is to overcome the shortcomings of data from either quantitative or qualitative methods respectively (Creswell, 2014). The table below shows the three main methods based in data collection.

Table 11: Quantitative, mixed and qualitative research methods, Creswell, 2014.

Quantitative Methods	Mixed Methods	Qualitative Methods
Pre-determined	Both predetermined and emerging methods	Emerging methods
Instrument based questions	Both open and close-ended questions	Open-ended questions
Performance data, attitude data, observational data and census data	Multiple forms of data drawing on all possibilities	Interview data, observation data, document data and audiovisual data
Statistical analysis	Statistical and text analysis	Text and image analysis
Statistical interpretation	Across database interpretation	Themes, patterns interpretation

Several research methodologies have been identified in literatures. The table below summarises different methodologies, their characteristics and the associated paradigms (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

Table 12: Summary of design, characteristics and associated research paradigms. (Adapted from Collis and Hussy, 2014), pp. 60-71.

Type of design	Characteristics	Associated paradigms
Experimental studies	Involves investigating the relationships between variables, independent variables are manipulated in order to observe the effect on dependent variable. Field experiments are usually carried out in a real world (lab, office, factory etc).	Positivist
Surveys	Normally used to collect both primary and secondary data, results are generalised. Descriptive survey offer a true account at one point or various times. Attitudes, behaviours of respondents are collected. Analytical survey is used to determine if there is a relationship between variables.	Positivist/Interpretivist
Cross-sectional studies	Usually provides data in different context over the same period. Used when there is a time or resource constraints, provides a short and snappy research of the phenomenon in question.	Positivist
Longitudinal study	Used to study variables or group of subjects over a long period of time. Interpretivist paradigm focuses on qualitative data.	Positivist/Interpretivist
Hermeneutics	Involves interpretation and understanding of historical texts.	Interpretivist
Ethnography	Involves the use of pooled resources (knowledge) in order to understand patterns of activity in humans. Data collection is through observation; study takes a long time and is carried out in natural world or settings.	Interpretivist

Participative enquiry	It engages participants as fully as possible throughout the research process.	Interpretivist
Action research	Used in an effort to effect a change in partially controlled setting. The researcher and the research are part of the ever constantly changing social setting.	Interpretivist
Case studies	Usually used to study and understand a phenomenon in their natural world by obtaining knowledge through a variety of sources.	Interpretivist/Positivist
Grounded theory	Involves collection, coding and analysis of data using logical techniques to develop an inductively derived theory .Data formed from the study is used to develop a theory.	Interpretivist
Feminist, gender and ethnicity studies	Involves studying and understand a phenomenon from the feminist point of view. Gender is focused on both male and female while ethnicity focuses on ethnic groups.	Interpretivist

3.4.1 Justification for the Chosen Methodology: Survey

Besides the research design type and the associated paradigms, the methodology adopted by a researcher is in many ways influenced by his beliefs and assumptions as previously discussed. Most researchers adopt either the positivist or the interpretive methods for their work depending on the nature of their research and what they intend to achieve but it does not mean that a combination of different methods cannot be used. The current research comes under the IS area and the positivist paradigm has been used successfully in IS for producing quantifiable outputs (Chen and Hirschhein, 2004; Sanders et al, 2007; Sabi et al, 2016).

Considering the nature of this research and other researches that involve adoption of IS within an organisation, survey method was adopted utilizing quantitative technique. Survey methodology was deemed appropriate for this research to collect data to build a model that will measure all the constructs needed in this study. It is also widely used and accepted

methodology in IS research (Oates, 2010), therefore, suitable for developing a predictive model (Palvia et al, 2004).

Furthermore, Creswell (2014) noted that specific problems call for specific approaches. For instance, identification of factors that influence an outcome, the utility of intervention and understanding the predictors of outcomes, quantitative approach best suits as it is also used to test a theory or explanation. Qualitative approaches are used when the variables to be examined are unknown or the topic is new, unexplored or previously have not been addresses by theories.

Survey methodology is usually associated with positivist paradigm. However, they are also being used in interpretivist paradigms. Surveys can be used to collect both primary and secondary data, systematically analysed and patterns identified in the results can be generalised (Oates, 2010, Collis and Hussey, 2014). It was Collis and Hussey (2014) who distinguished two types of surveys - descriptive survey and analytical survey. *Descriptive survey* provides a precise account of a phenomenon at certain times. An example is the views and attitudes of employees to new products. *Analytical survey* on the other hand deals with variables and their relationships.

Creswell (2014) discussed survey design extensively and included in his discussion the rationale, data collection procedure, whether data will be collected once or over time and specifying how it will be collected e.g. by mail, telephone, interviews, internet etc. Oates (2010) elaborated on the need to design survey based on the type of data the researcher is expected to generate. Bernard (2013) is of the opinion that there is no ideal data collection method. Rather, the method should be tailored and dictated by the needs of the research. However, employing a particular method of data collection depends on a number of factors. For example, self-administered questionnaires may be ideal if the respondents are educated and literate; then there is possibility of getting up to 70% response rate. Telephone interviews will be ideal if the higher percentage of the sample population has telephones. The next section discusses the resources used.

From the foregoing paragraph, this study will be adopting quantitative approach considering how the data will be gathered, analysed and interpreted in addition to the kind of results it tends to achieve. Similarly, the relationship between different variables and how they affect adoption of cloud computing for e-learning would be examined. Furthermore, previous

studies that have used the same models and theories equally adopted same approach (Low et al, 2011)

3.4.2 Identifying Resources Needed

Based on the nature of the research it was imperative to limit the study to a particular area of higher education thus, data gathering was limited to 15 universities. The 15 universities were selected so as to cover all geographical locations while also not limiting the study only to the new or older universities. It is also important to note that the actual sampling does not involve all the university community and population, rather a section of the population who are better placed to give opinion on the subject matter. Thus, the sampling population used in this study was limited to the following categories:

- University management staff
- Technical staff (ICT)
- Academic staff (computing/IT, teaching/research)
- Other IT staff

The survey was conducted electronically using Google forms and data extracted were analysed using SPSS.

The table below categorises the studied institutions based year of foundation, year of royal charter, academic schools/faculties, number of staff (full time and part time) and the student number (undergraduate and postgraduate).

Table 13: Characteristics of surveyed institutions (Source: adapted from HESA, 2014/15 session)

<i>Institution</i>	<i>Found ation</i>	<i>Royal charte r</i>	<i>No. of sch.</i>	<i>No. of staff</i>			<i>No. of students</i>		
				<i>F/T</i>	<i>P/T</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>U/G</i>	<i>P/G</i>	<i>Total</i>
Edinburgh Napier University	1964	1992	6	505	345	850	10805	2320	13125
Glasgow Caledonian University	1875	1993	3	620	150	770	14095	2840	16930
Heriot-Watt University	1821	1966	6	765	30	795	7040	3665	10705
Queen Margaret	1875	2007	2	160	85	250	3600	1670	5270

University									
The Robert Gordon University	1750	1992	11	480	265	754	9100	4140	13240
The University of Aberdeen	1495	1860	4	1260	405	1665	10055	3985	14035
The University of Edinburgh	1582	1582	20	3495	785	4280	20100	8780	28880
University of Abertay Dundee	1888	1994	4	185	25	210	3875	350	4220
University of Dundee	1881	1967	9	1275	260	1535	10200	4980	15180
University of Glasgow	1451	1451	20	2360	820	3175	19160	7655	26815
University of St Andrews	1410	1413	24	1020	140	1160	7930	2730	10660
University of Stirling	1967	1967	6	545	400	940	7995	3105	11100
University of Strathclyde	1769	1964	4	1200	225	1430	14670	6540	21210
University of the Highlands and Islands	2001	2011	4	30	5	35	7415	440	7850
University of the West of Scotland	1836	2007	6	560	50	610	12900	1835	14730

3.4.3. Data Collection Methods

Data collection is an integral part of any research process. This section discusses the method used for data collection and analysis with particular emphasis on the chosen method. As discussed earlier in section 3.4, method is the actual technique or procedure employed for collecting and/or analysing of data (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Different data collection methods include observation, interviews and questionnaires.

Figure 9: Data collection methods

The choices of methods are determined by the type of information the research is seeking, from whom and under what circumstances (Robson and McCartan 2016). Following this section is the explanation of the different data collection methods mentioned above.

Questionnaire

Questionnaire has been widely used in research for data collection. Some authors refer to it based on their mode of completion. For example, Bryman and Bell (2011) described it based on the fact it can be self-administered, posted or mailed. Rowley (2014) referred to it based on the type of questions: open ended and close ended, methods of distribution including face-to-face by hand. Oates (2010) described questionnaire as pre-defined set of questions (items) in pre-determined order. Furthermore, it could be self-administered or researcher administered. But it was Gillham (2011) who described questionnaire as one of the many ways of obtaining information from people or to answer our research questions directly or indirectly.

Generally, there are two different types of questions in questionnaire - open ended and close ended questions. Such questions about age, sex, salary, attitude, beliefs, behaviours or experiences may be included in questionnaires (Rowley, 2014). Close ended questions are the type of questions with answers already predetermined e.g. structured interview (Gillham, 2011). Structured interview is very popular with researchers as they find them easy to analyse. Open ended questions are more difficult to analyse as respondents have to write their answers instead of choosing predetermined ones. Gillham further argued that close ended questions are likely to give a better representation of opinions, beliefs or judgement because they are a small range of answers. Open ended question will lead to greater discovery since respondents are not restricted in their responses.

Questionnaires are commonly used in carrying out quantitative research and in survey situations where a large number of data between 100 and 1000 are required (Rowley, 2014). They are appropriate for studies where large volumes of data are required, for standardised data, easy for respondents to read; understand and respond to and require fewer resources - time and money (Oates, 2010 and Gillham, 2011). However, questionnaire based research are not without drawbacks. The major drawbacks are issue with literacy skills and handicaps especially in self-administered questionnaire, low response rate, lack of truthfulness, honesty and seriousness especially if the answers are close ended questions, and the wording may have effect on the answers depending on the perception and understanding of the respondents (Oates, 2010 and Gillham, 2011).

This method of data collection is commonly used in information systems adoption. It also appears to be very popular particularly in adoption of cloud computing. Related studies exist that have used questionnaire and quantitative methodology for data collection in cloud adoption studies were carried out by Sabi et al (2015); Low et al (2011); Gangwar et al (2015); Senyo et al (2016); Aharony (2014); Aharony (2015); Yuvaraj (2015); Safari et al (2015) and Hew and Kadir (2016). Considering that related studies that have adopted questionnaire and also the need for greater discovery, this research will adopt questionnaire incorporating both close and open ended questions.

Interview

Interview is one of the methods of data collection that is commonly used in research. According to Oates (2010), an interview is a particular kind of discussion or exchange between two people. Interviews can be used to elicit detailed information not found on historical data, complex questions, sensitive or privileged information. Researchers normally use interview to explore opinions and experiences that respondents may not provide through written communications or questionnaires (Oates, 2010; Bird, 2016). In fact, Bird (2016) described interview as an important tool that should be present in a researcher's toolbox.

Interviews are classified based on their structure and here are three types of interviews: structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews. In structured interviews the questions are identical and pre-determined usually with short answers. Unstructured interviews on the other hand give the interviewee a free hand to answer freely on the topic of discussion while the interviewer adapts the questions based on the answers given. In semi-structured

interviews, the interviewee also discusses freely but with a degree of adaptation of the questions as the interview progresses (Rowley, 2012, Oates, 2010).

Interview as a method of data collection does not fit into the purpose of this research as it is mainly used for qualitative study. Considering the geographical location of the universities, conducting interviews will involve huge cost and time wasting. Additionally, questionnaire will cover a more representative sample of the population compared to interviews.

Observation

Observation is a method used to obtain qualitative data whereby a researcher observes people in a natural settings e.g. fieldwork and laboratories (Collis and Hussey 2014). Collis and Hussey went further to discuss two types of observational methods: non-participant observation and participant observation. In a non-participant observation the researcher is not involved in the study but observes and records the activities of the participant. In other words, the researcher is concerned with monitoring and recording the activities of the participants rather than being involved. In the participant observation, the researcher is completely and actively involved with the participants and the phenomenon being studied.

As discussed in the previous section (3.4.3 questionnaire), cost considerations will be enormous and also involves considerable amount of time in trying to obtain empirical data for the study from all the universities in Scotland.

3.5 Ethical Issues

Ethical issues associated with research deals with the conduct of the research and the manner of reporting findings (Collis and Hussey, 2014). The ethical considerations for this research include the right not to be harmed, informed consent, right to privacy, confidentiality and anonymity. Furthermore, participants were informed of the purpose of research. The survey instrument was duly approved by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee before data collection commenced.

In conclusion, this chapter discussed the key research objectives and different research paradigms. Research methodology and justification for a chosen method (survey) and how it was conducted were also discussed. The chapter was concluded with a discussion on the different data collection methods and as well as ethics.

CHAPTER 4- CONCEPTUAL MODEL DEVELOPMENT

In this chapter, the process of developing a conceptual model of adoption of cloud computing for e-learning is presented. This research aims to develop a model that may enhance the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE. It will consider the impact of human and organisational factors that are likely to influence adoption. These include but not limited to: how the users perceive the current e-learning technologies, their acceptability and likelihood of adopting new methods and techniques. Another important factor is the characteristics of the organisation introducing the technology (Behrend et al, 2011).

Adoption as a concept has been described differently and used interchangeably by different scholars and authors. For example, attitude, intention, acceptance, adoption and diffusion have all been used as an indicator to measure adoption by various authors in different contexts. Most of these studies did not define the terms acceptance, adoption and diffusion but describes adoption as covering both intention and actual use (Wang et al, 2011). Likewise, different models have been proposed with no general model for adoption of cloud computing. TAM for example deals with individual adoption while TOE deals with organisational adoption.

TAM (PEOU and PU) is of significance for individual intention to accept and use technology within institutions (Davies, 1989), implementation is typified by individual adoption pattern (Straub, 2009) and integration is dealt with at organisational level. This research however attempts to develop a model that can be used for adoption in general whether at individual or organisational level. This was done by combining four known models and theories: TAM (PEOU, PU), TOE, DOI and CSE.

Many IT/IS adoption research using a number of models are mainly focusing on perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness with much less focus on behaviour that are associated with adoption. The actions of individual adopters and the environment (institution) within which they adopt and use these technologies and how they influence or are influenced by the institution will be applied in the context of this research.

4.1 Defining Overall Hypotheses

The overall hypotheses as used in this research are defined below:

H₁: represents the overall hypotheses of technological factors of adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. They include: perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, relative advantage,

complexity, compatibility and security. The technological factors of adoption are hypothesised as follows:

There are significant positive relationships between technology and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_2 : represents the overall hypotheses of organisational factors of adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. They include: technology readiness, top management support, institution size and cost. The organisational factors of adoption are hypothesised as follows:

There are significant positive relationships between organisation and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_3 : represents the overall hypotheses of environmental factors of adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. They include: competitive pressure and trading partner pressure. The environmental factors of adoption are hypothesised as follows:

There are significant relationships between environment and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_4 : represents the overall hypotheses of factors of innovation and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. They include: trialability and observability and is hypothesised as follows:

There is a positive relationship between diffusion of innovation and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_5 : measured only a single factor thus has no overall representation.

4.2 Presentation of the Conceptual Model and the Hypotheses

Literature on IT adoption suggests that most researchers conduct studies by integrating theories used in information system with frameworks that cover the contextual antecedents. A theoretical model for adoption of IT may consist of a combination of innovation adoption theories and contextual framework of IT adoption. Hence, no single theory or model can be used to explain attitude, behaviour and various determinants in the context of IT adoption (Hameed et al 2012). On the other hand, Low et al, (2011) advocated the combining of different frameworks and models for a better understanding of IT adoption.

Figure 10: Underpinning theories (Source: own)

In the context of this research, a combination of various approaches, models and frameworks will be adopted as major studies in e-learning have established the importance of these frameworks in technology adoption as discussed in section 2.4.

Furthermore, several studies have been carried out in relation to individuals' acceptance and adoption of IT, thus, leading to a number of models proposed and constructs developed. These studies reveal perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and self-reported system use intention to use, attitudes, subjective norms, system design features, attitude towards using, actual system use, user training, computer experience, organisational support, end user support, system quality, variety of use, innovative characteristics (including relative advantage), perceived voluntariness, current use, future use, intentions, computer experience, image, compatibility, system rating relative advantage, enjoyment, attitude, satisfaction, usage, computer self-efficacy, perceptions of external control, computer anxiety, computer playfulness, perceived enjoyment, objective usability, and behavioural intentions (Davis, 1989; Davis, 1993; Igbaria et al, 1995; Agarwal and Prasad, 1997; Venkatesh, 2000) are important in any technology adoption.

Sidorova et al (2013) however, categorised the factors into three major groups: individuals' perception of the system characteristics (usefulness, ease of use, control etc), individual characteristics (expertise, personality traits, self-efficacy, computer anxiety etc) and external factors influencing individual perceptions (training, management support, task characteristics etc.)

Figure 11: Classification of major factors influencing individuals' acceptance and adoption of IT (adapted from Sidovora et al, 2013)

A number of constructs and frameworks are adopted from existing models in order to build constructs for this model: *Perceived Ease of Use*, *Perceived Usefulness (TAM)*, *Relative Advantage*, *Complexity*, *Compatibility*, *Top Management Support*, *Technology Readiness*, *Firm Size*, *Competitive Pressure*, *Trading Partner Pressure (TOE)*, *Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE)* *Triability and Observability (DOI)*. These constructs may be viewed as factors that can facilitate and affect the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

It is hoped that these combinations will help to develop a model that will be used to explain the low adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in higher education. The rest of this section presents the arguments used to derive the constructs and develop the research model.

4.2.1 Technology Acceptance Model

There are several theories and models on the individuals' acceptance and adoption of IT and TAM appears to be the most widely used. TAM was first introduced by Davies in 1989 though it was adapted from the theory of reasoned action TRA (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975). TAM has undergone several extensions and modifications while still being very popular in IS research. The popularity of TAM also stems from extensive validations, applications and replications over the years to predict the use of information systems (Lu et al, 2003). Despite its popularity TAM is not without criticisms as there remain controversies on how PEOU does affect either self-reported use or intended use of IT (Gefan and Straub, 2000). TAM evolved offering insight into the factors of computer acceptance that is general, while also explaining how users behave when using a wide range of computer technologies and user populations. Measures that predict and explain use is important to explain what causes people to accept or reject information technology (Hendrickson et al, 1993).

On one the hand it may be argued that TAM deals with an individual's adoption of technology. However, Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) are of relevance for individuals' intention to accept and use technology in organisations (Davies 1989). These two determinants according to TAM are fundamentally important for attitude towards using a particular system and also determine intention to use and the actual usage behaviour. On the other hand, the decision to integrate any technology within an organisation or the institution lies with the management of the institution. However, successful implementation is exemplified by individual adoption pattern (Straub, 2009). Thus, it is important to understand what influences individuals' adoption pattern thus, the integration of PEOU and PU from TAM construct in building the research model.

Perceived Ease of Use

Perceived ease of use is the extent to which a person believes on how effortless using a system would be (Davies et al, 1989). In other words, the simpler the technology is to use, the more likely the technology is to be adopted (see also complexity). Similarly, an easy to use technology is likely to be perceived as less intimidating (Moon and Kim, 2001), thus having a greater chance of being adopted. At the early stage of user's contact with the system the PEOU is strong but becomes stronger as the user gets more comfortable and familiar with the system (Davies, 1989, 1993; Venkatesh, 2000). If cloud technology is seen as less intimidating, perceived as easy to use and less complex, institutions of higher learning should be willing to adopt it for e-learning.

We can therefore hypothesise that:

H_{1a}: Perceived ease of use of cloud technology is positively related to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness is the degree to which a user believes that using the technology will improve his or her work performance (Davies et al, 1989). PEOU and PU have been found to be important perceptions that determine IT adoption. Researchers argue that a new IT is adopted mainly because it is vital in achieving tasks that are not inherent in the use of the IT itself (Gefen and Straub, 2000). Therefore, PU is considered an important antecedent in IT adoption. In other words, relative advantage plays an essential role in the adoption of any new IT or innovation. Studies have shown that perceived usefulness positively affects user's perceptions and behavioural intentions (Park and Chen, 2007). In this study, perceived usefulness is the degree to which a user believes that the use of cloud computing for e-learning will enhance their learning thus it may have a similar positive effect on their attitude towards adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. By enhancing learning it therefore means that cloud technology has characteristics that are perceived to be better than other e-learning solutions thus, likely to be adopted (see also relative advantage)

We can therefore hypothesise that:

H_{1b}: Perceived usefulness of cloud technology will be positively related to the intention to adopt cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

4.2.2 Technology-Organisation-Environment

In the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework, Tornatsky and Fleischer, (1990) identified three main features that affect technology adoption. These factors have significant impact on institution's intention to adopt an innovative technology which ultimately affects innovation and organisational performance. Detailed description of these feature are given in the next section.

Technology

The technological context describes existing and new technologies relevant to the firm. Though PEOU and PU are TAM variables, they are also directly related to the technology context of TOE. In order to avoid repetition, detailed description of PEOU and PU are given in this section.

A number of IS related studies have been used to empirically validate TOE framework for the adoption of innovative IT solutions. Kuan and Chau (2001) used it to study the electronic data interchange (EDI) in small business. Zhu et al (2004) accessed the value of e-business while Lin and Lin (2008) studied e-business diffusion also with TOE. Furthermore this framework has also been used to study e-business adoption in EU (Oliveira and Martins, 2010), organisational adoption of virtual worlds (Yoon and George, 2013) and adoption of electronic signature in hospital information department (Chang et al, 2007). Since TOE framework has been used in various IS adoption researches, it is considered suitable for this type of study thus, it will be applied in this research.

From the foregoing, we can draw the following hypothesis:

H₁: There are significant positive relationships between technology and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Relative Advantage

Relative advantage refers to the perception that particular innovation will be better or worse than similar innovations or ideas (Rogers, 2003). Thus, a perception that better innovations are expected to be adopted faster than others. In other words, cloud computing is perceived to be better than previous technologies. The relative advantages of cloud computing amongst others include: on-demand self-service, broad network access, resource pooling, rapid elasticity and measured service (NITS, 2011).

From the foregoing, we can hypothesise that:

H_{1c}: There is a positive relationship between relative advantage and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Complexity

The perception of how difficult it is to comprehend or understand the innovation is referred to as complexity (Rogers 2003). Therefore the more complex an innovation is the less would the rate of adoption of such innovation be. Thus, if cloud computing is perceived as complex, institutions may not be willing to adopt it.

From the foregoing we can hypothesise that

H_{1d}: Complexity is negatively related to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Compatibility

The perception that innovation is similar and can fit into existing systems, values, experiences, needs or environment of potential adapters is termed compatibility (Rogers 2003). Therefore, innovations that are considered compatible with existing systems are likely to be adopted. Rogers et al (1997) reports that those innovations that are not compatible with already existing ones are usually slow to diffuse into the existing values and standards.

From the foregoing we can hypothesise that

H_{1e}: There is a positive relationship between compatibility and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Security

Security is the absence of unauthorized access to, or handling of the system state (Sun et al, 2011). For the purpose of this research, we defined security as the ability of the institution to safeguard against unauthorised access to cloud computing services including availability, integrity, confidentiality and privacy of data.

Gartner (2016) estimates that global IT security spending has increased by 7.9% reaching \$81.6 billion in 2016. This indicates the level of investment and spending by organisations in protecting their critical information resources (Hwang et al; 2017). Data security has been one of the main areas of concern in cloud computing (Antonopoulos and Gillam 2010; Shaikh and Haider 2011; Gutierrez et al, 2015) and IT in general, yet researchers and authors are still not in agreement as to the extent of security of data in the cloud (Armbrust et al, 2009; Buyaa et al, 2009). Security inhibits and also drives adoption due to resources being devoted by the cloud service providers (Ernst and Young, 2010; Shaikh and Haider, 2011). Alecu (2012) and Assuncao et al (2009) suggested that with centralised data storage, monitoring data access, virtualisation and logging, organisations are able to effectively manage resources and minimise security issues inherent in the sharing of resources among multiple computing locations.

Youseff et al (2009) argue that lack of standard is hindering cloud vendors from addressing security issues due to different approaches by different providers. Shaikh and Haider (2011) reviewed eleven (11) research papers dealing with security and privacy of data in the cloud. Their findings indicate that nine (9) of the reviewed papers proposed a model or tool of dealing with the issues, thus lending credence to Youseff et al's suggestion about lack of standards. However, in recent years a number of bodies have been set up specifically to deal

with practices, regulations, as well as confidentiality and privacy issues. The Cloud Security Alliance (CSA) was set up to provide security assurance for both the users and Cloud Service Providers (CSPs). European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA) was commissioned by European Parliament to harmonise privacy laws and provide a benchmarking model for effective evaluation of cloud service offerings based on standard set of controls (Ernst and Young, 2010). Cloud Computing Interoperability Group and Multi-Agency Cloud Computing Forum have also been seeking ways to efficiently control and secure data in the cloud (Onwubiko, 2010).

Gutierrez et al (2015) also acknowledged the existence of security issues in the cloud but went further to detail ways in which institutions are trying to overcome them. An example is the integration and the use of Web 2.0 and social networking technologies with cloud and testing cloud vulnerability with less sensitive information before storing more sensitive data. Similarly, Hwang et al (2017) also highlighted further measures being taken by institutions to prevent security breaches like restricting access to sensitive data by unauthorised persons as well as security awareness, policies and implications of breaches.

Despite the perceived improved security in the cloud, some researchers are still sceptical (Youseff et al, 2009; Rimal et al, 2010; Sun et al, 2011; Teneyuca, 2011; Salleh et al, 2012; Kizza, 2013). Furthermore, Ernst and Young (2010) argued that management of third party cloud vendors will create fresh issues and challenges and shared infrastructures will create further risks since users are not in control of their data. However, it was Onwubiko (2010) who suggested proper evaluation of traditional networks in relation to cloud computing since there are inherent risks associated with it. He argued that cloud computing is an emerging technology thus, risks are still evolving and rather unfamiliar. Research indicates that availability, confidentiality, integrity and privacy are some of the major security issues associated with cloud adoption (Onwubiko, 2010; Sun et al, 2011; Salleh et al, 2012; Oguande and Mehnen, 2013). Helmbrecht (2010) recommended areas that consumers should pay attention to when dealing with cloud vendors to ensure the security and privacy of their data in the cloud. Yuvaraj (2015) categorised security and risk issues in the cloud which are summarised in the table below.

Table 14: Cloud security categorisation (Yuvaraj, 2015)

<i>Cloud Security Issues</i>	<i>Type of Breaches</i>
Top Security Risks	Data breaches
	Data loss
	Account or service traffic hijacking
	Insecure interfaces and application programme interfaces
	Denial of Service attacks (DoS)
	Malicious insiders
	Abuse of cloud services
	Shared technology vulnerabilities
Policy and Organisational Risks	Lock-in
	Loss of governance
	Compliance challenges
	Cloud service termination or failure
	Supply chain failure
Technical Risks	Isolation failure
	Resource exhaustion
	Intercepting data in transit
	Insecure or ineffective deletion of data
Legal Risks	Issues due to jurisdiction
	Data protection risks
Other Risks	Unauthorised access
	Theft of equipment
	Natural disasters

From the foregoing, it is evident that if adopting institutions are confident that their data are secure, available when needed, privacy and confidentiality of data are protected and access are granted only to the authorised personnel, then they are more likely to adopt cloud computing.

We can therefore hypothesise that:

H_{1f}: Security is significantly and positively related to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Organisation

Organisational context of TOE describes the characteristics of the organisation such as scope, size, complexity and management structure.

H₂: There are significant positive relationships between organisation and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Technology Readiness

The readiness to adopt an innovation more commonly goes beyond the financial but involves technical resources. Snyder-Halpern (2001) proposed knowledge readiness, staffing readiness, technical readiness, operational readiness, process readiness, resources readiness, and value and goal readiness as sub-dimensions of readiness that could possibly affect the adoption of information technology. Similarly, a firm's technology readiness involves technological infrastructure and IT human resources (Kuan and Chau, 2001; To and Ngai, 2006; Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Pan and Jang, 2008; Wang et al., 2010; Zhu et al., 2006). According to Wang et al (2010) technological infrastructure refers to the platform upon which the network is installed while the skills and the knowledge are provided by the IT human resources. Low et al (2011) however, are of the opinion that cloud computing can be a part of the value chain but only if the required infrastructure and technical skills are put in place by institutions.

From the foregoing, we can hypothesise that:

H_{2a}: There is a positive relationship between institutions' technology readiness and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Top Management Support

Top management support is needed in order for an innovation to be adopted in an organisation. The support of the top management in an organisation varies from financial slack (Nystrom et al, 2002) to creating a conducive environment for any innovation to occur (Lee and Kim, 2007; Pyke, 2009). The integration of resources and reengineering processes involved in the implementation of cloud computing makes top management support even more imperative (Low and Chen, 2011).

From the foregoing, we can hypothesise that:

H_{2b}: There is a positive relationship between top management support and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Institution Size

Size as a factor that affects adoption of innovation has also been widely studied (Chen and Fu, 2001; Shefer and Frenkel, 2005; Fernandes et al, 2006; Damanpour, 2010). Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990) describe firm size in terms of number of employees, annual revenue, value added etc. However, they argued that the underlying organisational factors and specifics have not been identified other than the general term. Therefore they concluded that size cannot be used as a generic measure but as an alternative for many inter organisational variables.

Some researchers argue that larger firms are more likely to adopt innovations as they have greater flexibility and resources, thus more likely to take risks compared to smaller firms (Low et al, 2011) Larger firms are also more likely to assume high fixed costs associated with innovative activities, generate funds for risky innovative projects through the capital markets and make returns on investment due to bigger market power (Pérez-Cano, 2013). On the other hand, Oliveira and Martins (2010) are of the opinion that larger firms are less flexible than smaller firms and the structural inertia and administrative bottle-necks may indeed slow down adoption.

From the aforementioned paragraph, we can hypothesise:

H_{2c}: Institution's size is significantly and positively related to institution's ability to adopt cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Cost

In terms of adoption of technological innovations, cost deals with affordability of the technology. Therefore the system for adopting cloud computing for e-learning in HE should be affordable in many respects such as when compared to the already existing systems and the expected return on investment (ROI) if and when the new technological innovation is adopted, implemented and fully operational.

Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990) measured the effect of cost as it affects organisational adoption of technological innovations using slack resources. However, they argued that slack resources though helpful and desirable are neither necessary nor sufficient for innovation to occur. It was Premkumar and Roberts (1999) and Kuan and Chuau (2001) who argued that

the cost of adoption and implementation must be within allotted resources, commensurate and relative to the expected benefits of the technology. Kuan and Chuau (2001) however, identified cost and technical knowledge as two of the major factors that may hinder IT growth in small organisations. If cloud technology is not complex but compatible and have advantages over already existing technologies and with top management in support, it should be accepted and adopted for e-learning in HE.

H_{2d}: There is a positive relationship between cost considerations and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Environment

The environmental context of TOE framework (Tornatsky and Fleischer, 1990) describes the arena in which the firm operates and conducts its business including the industry, competitors, and dealings with government. These factors have significant impact on institution's intention to adopt an innovative technology which ultimately affects innovation and organisational performance. Sawang and Unsworth (2011) argue that not only does the environment exert pressure on firms to adopt but affects the degree to which such innovations are available and/or needed.

We can therefore hypothesise that:

H₃: There are significant relationships between environment and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Competitive Pressure

Zhu et al. (2002) describe competitive pressure as the degree of pressure from competitors, which is an external power pressing a firm to adopt new technology in order to avoid competitive decline. However, To and Ngai (2006) as well as Oliveira and Martins (2010) describe competitive pressure as the level of pressure felt by the firms from competitors within the industry. IT industry is constantly changing and evolving while the business environment is getting tougher. Institutions therefore must continue to reinvent themselves and constantly look for ways to outperform their competitors in order to remain relevant in the market. Therefore being able to innovate and adopt latest technological innovations may be seen as an essential part of the process.

From the foregoing, we can hypothesise that

H_{3a}: There is a positive relationship between competitive pressure and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Trading Partner Pressure

Apart from pressure to adopt innovation due to competition, customers, suppliers and network can also influence organisations to adopt innovations (Sawang and Unsworth, 2011). According to Swanson (1995), complex IT innovation requires facilitating technology portfolio, organisational structure and emphasis on environmental strategy. Organisations however, may depend on their trading partners for their IT design and application tasks (Pan and Jang, 2008).

From the foregoing, we can hypothesise that:

H_{3b}: There is a positive relationship between trading partner pressure and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

4.2.3 Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Innovation is an idea, practice or object that is perceived as new by individual or other unit of adoption (Rogers, 1995). Innovation does not have to be new or better but rather the perception of novelty. Five characteristics of innovation as identified by Rogers that can influence adoption of an innovation are: relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, trialability and observability. In order to avoid repetition, this section however, will focus mainly on trialability and observability when using DOI, as relative advantage, compatibility and complexity have been previously discussed under the TOE framework (section 4.2.2).

Though Rogers' (1995) DOI formed the basis for adoption and diffusion theory, subsequent theories of diffusion that have been used in various studies also identified characteristics that are consistent with that of Rogers. Lin and Chen (2012) investigated the perception, attitude and adoption of cloud computing as an innovation by IT professional using the DOI. The results show that IT managers are concerned about the compatibility of cloud with the existing systems and environment. Agarwal and Prasad (1998) studied the antecedents of user perceptions in information technology adoption also using DOI. The results appear to be consistent with characteristics identified by Rogers (1995). Furthermore, Yu and Toa (2009) used both TAM and DOI to study the business-level adoption of innovation IT/IS technology.

Diffusion of technological innovations refers to the spread of use of new methods, processes or production systems (Rogers, 1995). In other words, it is the process of penetration or spreading through the organisation or a particular population. IT innovations have been found to be critical elements in an effort to drive business forward and improve efficiencies and competitive advantage. Thus, its diffusion within institutions will continue to enhance business processes. Straub (2009) points out that in some cases, adoption is not only about the choice to accept an innovation but the extent to which they are integrated.

Having established a relationship and similarities with technological context of TOE (relative advantage, complexity and compatibility) in the preceding section 4.2.2, we can therefore hypothesise that:

H₄: There is a positive relationship between diffusion of innovation and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Trialability

Trialability refers to accessibility of an innovation by an individual for experimentation before deciding whether to adopt that innovation or not (Rogers, 1995). Trialability could be said to be directly related to actual system use or ease of use and in effect to adoption of cloud computing thus, may facilitate the adoption of an innovation.

H_{4a}: There is a positive relationship between trying out a technology and adoption of that technology. Therefore, trialability will be positively related to the previous use of that system.

Observability

Observability is the perception that when an innovation is visible and available and everyone has it, the individuals are more likely to adopt the innovation. At a point when it becomes pervasive, those who would not normally adopt such innovation may consider adopting it. Frambach and Schillewaert (2002) questioned if the model was broad enough to evaluate organisational decision to adopt but could be improved with additional internal organisational characteristics and external factors. However, Heilesen and Josephsen (2008) argued that characteristics already have both external and internal dimensions. According to them, the external dimension on the one hand can be quantified and measured while the internal dimension the view is relative to the individual. Therefore factors including economic and technological, and perhaps the perception of the end users (staff and students), seem to be

consistent with the external dimension of Rogers' attributes. Factors affecting technology use are complex and no single model caters for personal aspects such as cognitive, affective and contextual factors (Straub, 2009). Similarly, Hammed et al (2012) also notes that adoption procedures and user acceptance of IT are essential factors in adoption and implementation. However, they stated that no single model exists to explain the IT innovation adoption procedure and how users may accept IT in an organisation. For example factors such as innovation characteristics, social, organisational and psychological variables affect the rate of adoption (Butler and Sellbom, 2002). Thus, observability could be used to explain the acceptance and adoption of cloud computing.

From the forgoing, we can hypothesise the following:

H_{4b}: Observability and the pervasive nature of a technology are positively related to the adoption of that technology.

4.2.4 Computer Self-Efficacy

CSE will be used to examine human behavioural factors that are likely to affect computer use, which in effect may influence the adoption of cloud computing. CSE has been used to show relationships between uses of new technologies. (Barling and Beatie, 1983; Bandura et al, 1977, cited by Rex, 2000; Zhang and Espinoza 1998, cited by Shu et al, 2011; Igbaria and Iivari 1995; Behrend et al, 2011; Park and Chen 2007, Teo, 2009). CSE refers to individuals' belief in their capabilities to use computer in diverse situations (Compeau and Higgins 1995). It has also been empirically tested that CSE affects perceived use (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) (Vankatesh and Davies, 2000; Davies et al, 1989).

One's judgement whether or not to adopt new technologies with emphasis on individuals' perception of the technology and how it affects such technology usage can be influenced by a number of factors. Some individuals perceive themselves as capable (high in self-efficacy) of performing certain tasks and are likely to attempt the execution of such tasks. Others that are less capable (low in self-efficacy) are less likely to attempt execution of tasks (Barling and Beatie, 1983; Bandura et al, 1977, cited by Rex, 2000).

From the aforementioned paragraph it could be inferred that perceived self-efficacy affects individual motivation and behavioural intentions. Individuals that are confident in their own ability are more likely to be motivated and perceive the technology easier to use than less confident individuals. Similarly, individuals with positive self-efficacy may tend to learn new skills and are more likely to adopt and use new technologies, while those with negative self-

efficacy may create resistance in operative capabilities (Zhang and Espinoza, 1998; cited by Shu et al, 2011).

Furthermore, individual's ability to adopt new technology is a major factor in their willingness to accept new technology (Igbaria and Iivari 1995). Research have also identified fear of computers, confidence and ability, resistance to new technology, perceived difficulty of use, not understanding the importance of technology and lack of motivation to adopt new technology as some of the factors affecting the acceptance and use of computers by individuals (Igbaria and Iivari 1995). It could therefore be argued that the aforementioned factors may have far reaching implications on managerial decisions in organisations, as those unlikely to use them are also unlikely to recommend them for adoption by their organisations.

Strategic IT and management decisions in organisations are increasingly involving non-IT employees, thus their prior knowledge and perception of these technologies are critical in the adoption of such technologies (Borgman et al, 2013). Thus, getting strategic IT decisions right is critical to survival in the current business environment and the use of computer could also benefit and aid management decisions but may be hindered due to poor acceptance of users of the technology (Igbaria and Iivari, 1995). In addition, it was Bell and Bell (2005) who identified involvement of administrative and support staff as potentially critical to the success of adoption of innovation in HE. According to them, there is more engagement problems that may be addressed if institution-wide response are highlighted and it aids the identification and dissemination of good practice.

Some technology users may be anxious and apprehensive at the first instance but constant usage and experiences reduce the level of anxiety (Simsek, 2011). In other words, prior knowledge and effort to learn more may increase perceived self-efficacy and lower anxiety, while negative self-efficacy may negatively influence usage and adoption of technologies.

Apart from individuals' perceptions in their own ability to perform tasks using computers, CSE however, can also be used to influence and predict future or subsequent task-specific performance; i.e. intentions for future use of computers (Bandura, 1997; Gist and Mitchell, 1992, cited by Rex, 2000; Marakas et al, 1988).

CSE has been widely used to empirically study the acceptance and adoption of various technological innovations. A study by Behrend et al (2011) indicates that self-efficacy has a major role to play in the adoption of various technological innovations like cloud computing. Igbaria and Iivari (1995) studied the effect of self-efficacy on computer usage and found that

organisational support led to higher self-efficacy. Thus, they suggested that encouragement, showing interest and awareness of problems by management can help influence users' perceptions and beliefs regarding the use of computer in the workplace.

Furthermore, Park and Chen (2007) used CSE, TAM and DOI to investigate acceptance and adoption of smartphone among medical doctors and nurses. They found that attitude, PU and CSE played a significant role in the acceptance and adoption of smartphones among medical doctors and nurses. Lam et al (2007) combined TRA, Perceived IT Beliefs, TAM Attitude, Self-Efficacy and Subjective norm to investigate hotel employee behavioural intentions towards adoption of information technology. The result showed that self-efficacy was the most important factor affecting behavioural intentions of adopting IT. Schillewaert et al (2005) also investigated the adoption of information technology in the sales force combining CSE with other constructs and models. Teo (2009) also combined variables and examined their relationships as it affect technology acceptance among pre-service teachers at a teacher training institute in Singapore. The result showed that perceived usefulness, attitude and computer self-efficacy directly affects pre-service teachers' technology acceptance.

From the foregoing, we can hypothesise that:

H₅: There is a positive relationship between individuals' belief in their capabilities to use technology and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Figure 12: High level conceptual model

Figure 13: Decomposed conceptual model

4.3 Mapping Hypotheses to Research Questions

Table 16 below shows the mapping of hypotheses to research questions and in relation to research framework.

Table 15: mapping hypotheses into research questions.

Construct	Variable	Hypotheses	Research question addressed
Technology		*H ₁	Grouping technological factors helps to address question 2.
TAM	PEOU	H _{1a}	Research question 1
	PU	H _{1b}	Research question 1
TOE	Relative advantage	H _{1c}	Research question 1
	Complexity	H _{1d}	Research question 1
	Compatibility	H _{1e}	Research question 1
	Security	H _{1f}	Research question 1
Organisation		*H ₂	Grouping organisational factors helps to address question 2.
	Technology readiness	H _{2a}	Research question 1
	Top mgt. support	H _{2b}	Research question 1
	Institution size	H _{2c}	Research question 1
	Cost	H _{2d}	Research question 1
Environment		*H ₃	Grouping environmental factors helps to address question 2.
	Competitive pressure	H _{3a}	Research question 1
	Trading partner pressure	H _{3b}	Research question 1
Diffusion of innovation		*H ₄	Grouping DOI factors helps to address question 2.
	Trialability	H _{4a}	Research question 1
	Observability	H _{4b}	Research question 1
Computer self-efficacy		H ₅	Research question 1 and 2

NB: * represents high level hypotheses of technology, organisation, environment and diffusion of innovation before their decomposition.

In conclusion, this chapter has detailed how the conceptual model was derived by combining TAM, TOE, DOI and CSE models and frameworks. It also presented details on how the hypotheses were derived. Finally, it presented the list of hypotheses, figure of high level conceptual model (figure 12) and decomposed conceptual model (figure 13).

CHAPTER 5- DATA COLLECTON

This chapter discusses the methods used for data collection and analysis. A survey was specifically developed to empirically evaluate how HE can adopt cloud computing for e-learning and what factors if any, affect adoption of cloud computing. Data collection was carried out by sending questionnaire survey to the selected sample population and subsequently face to face meetings were carried out in order to increase the number of respondents.

5.1 Survey Design

In order to answer the research questions, the survey was designed using a 5-point Likert scale (described in the next section) to measure different constructs in the research model. The essence of questionnaire is to elicit reliable response from people or group of people and when analysed will help answer the research question. Therefore, clarity of the questions and the quality of the design and presentation will help in achieving this (Oates, 2010; Gillham, 2011). The figure below shows the sequence of steps taken to obtain the empirical data, answer the research questions and achieve the overall objectives of the research.

Figure 14: Model of survey of data collection process (adapted from Robson and McCartan, 2016), pp 259.

The preceding chapter has already specified method of data collection and its justification. A well-designed questionnaire is the starting point in helping to achieve the objectives of any research. The questionnaire used for this research was designed and developed using a combination of sources including information gathered from interview and adaptations from literature sources and previous works. Literature sources were particularly important because they have been validated with previous researches and information from the interview also helped to consolidate validated existing instruments from previous researches.

There is no hard and fast rule on how to construct a research tool. However, the guiding principle is relating questions to the objectives of the study (Kumar, 2012). Thus, the survey instrument was designed with the research questions and objectives in mind. Table 16, section 5.2. also provide details of questionnaire items and their sources.

5.1.1 Likert Scale

Likert (1932) in his published work “a technique for the measurement of attitudes” developed a scale to measure attitudes as part of a wider study undertaken by Garner Murphy in 1929. This scale is commonly used till this day in quantitative research. Likert scale was developed due to complexity in measuring personality traits and social attitudes. The initial Likert scale was a 5-point alternative response: strongly approved, approved, undecided, disapprove and strongly disapprove. However, Likert scale has become very popular and undergone extensive extensions and modifications over the years. Boone and Boone (2012) in their article “analysing Likert data” detailed some of the most recent Likert adaptations.

This study used a 5-point Likert scale ranging from ‘strongly disagree’ to ‘strongly agree’. Below is an example of a 5-point Likert scale as used in this study.

Technical challenges may hinder or prevent my institution from adopting cloud technologies

- *Strongly disagree*
- *Disagree*
- *Neutral*
- *Agree*
- *Strongly agree*

It should be noted that to enhance accurate responses, two questions were reverse-coded to ensure that the respondents reflect their thoughts on their answers.

5.2 Operationalisation of Variables

Operationalisation entails devising measures of the concepts in which the researcher is interested (Bryman and Bell 2011). Similarly, Bernard (2013) defined operational definition as specifying exactly what the researcher has to do to measure something that has been defined conceptually. All responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, where (1) is *strongly disagree*, (2) is *disagree*, (3) is *neutral*, (4) is *agree* and (5) is *strongly agree*. Thus, following this paragraph is the mapping of operational definitions into questionnaire items.

Table 16: Operationalisation of variables (Source: own)

Constructs	Variable	Operationalisation	Item	Sources
Demographics		What is the name of your institution?	1	
		What is your gender?	2	
		What is your age bracket?	3	
		What is your department?	4	
		What is your job title	5	
		What is your highest level of qualification?	6	
		What is your current job experience?	7	
		What is your total working experience?	8	
Adoption and use of cloud		Which of the following cloud service models do you use?	9	Own
		Which of the following best describes your use cloud based services?	10	
TAM	PEOU	It is easy to understand and familiarise oneself with our institution's cloud technology.	G1	Davies (1989)
		Becoming skilful at using cloud technology was easy.	G2	
	PU	Using cloud technology improves my job performance.	G3	Argawal and Prasad (1998)
		Using cloud technology gives me greater control over my work.	G4	
		Using cloud technology enhances my job effectiveness.	G5	
TOE	Relative advantage	My institution's adoption of cloud will enable me to access data quicker than usual.	G6	Borgman et al (2013); Low et al (2011); Chong et al, (2009); Yu-hui (2008); Wang et al (2010); Yoon and George (2013).
		My institution's adoption of cloud technology will enable us to have more flexibility in managing our data.	G7	
	Security	With cloud technology I have no concern with data security.	G8	Own
	Relative advantage	Cloud based services are reliable.	G9	Borgman et al (2013); Low et al (2011); Chong et al, (2009); Yu-hui (2008); Wang et al (2010); Yoon and George (2013).
		With cloud technology I can perform more functions as a user.	G10	
	Competitive pressure	My institution's adoption of cloud will enable us to be competitive with other higher institutions	G11	Yu-hui (2008); Oliveira and Martins (2010);

				Borgman et al (2013); Chong et al, (2009); Low et al (2011); Wang et al (2010); Yoon and George (2013).
	Institution size	The number of employees in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology.	G12	Oliveira and Martins (2010); Borgman et al (2013); Low et al (2011); Wang et al (2010); Del Aguila-Obra and Padilla-Melendez (2006); Yoon and George (2013); Zhu et al (2004).
		The number of students in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology.	G13	
	Observability	The opportunity to observe and talk to those that have used cloud technology will help me to decide whether to adopt it or not.	G14	Park and Chen (2007)
CSE		I am confident that I have the necessary skills to use cloud technology.	G15	Campeau and Higgins (1995)
		I am confident of using any form of cloud technology even if I had never used it before.	G16	
Other factors		Please can you list other factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud computing	G17	
		To what extent do you agree that the factors that you listed in G17 above will influence adoption of cloud computing?	G18	
Respondent's suitability		Which of the following best describes your position in your institution?	G19	
TOE	Complexity	The use of cloud technologies is not as easy as I first thought.	T1	Borgman et al (2013); Low et al (2011); Wang et al (2010); Yu-hui (2008).
		Technical challenges may hinder or prevent my institution from adopting cloud technologies.	T2	
		New technologies are more difficult to use than already existing technologies.	T3	
	Compatibility	Cloud technology is compatible with other software.	T4	Borgman et al (2013); Lin and Lin (2008); Yu-
		Cloud technology adoption is compatible	T5	

		with my institution's information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure.		hui (2008); Chong et al, (2009); Low et al (2011); Oliveira and Martins (2010); Wang et al (2010); Yoon and George (2013).
	Cost	My institution will adopt cloud technology if it is affordable and cost effective.	T6	Researcher's own adapted from Misra and Mondal (2011); Zhu et al (2004).
		My institution will consider the cost of adopting and implementing new innovation compared to the already existing ones before a decision to adopt that innovation can be made.	T7	
		My institution is likely to consider long term operational and maintenance cost savings from existing technologies before deciding to adopt a new technological innovation like cloud computing.	T8	
	Tech readiness	My institution has the infrastructural capabilities to adopt and deploy cloud based services.	T9	Yu-hui (2008); Oliveira and Martins (2010); Low et al (2011); Zhu et al (2004), Own.
	Trialability	It is important to properly try it out before deciding on whether or not to adopt.	T10	Park and Chen (2007)
	Trading partner pressure	IT organisations like Microsoft, Oracle, Cisco, CIW etc. that accredit IT courses in institutions require us to adopt cloud computing.	T11	Kuan and Chau (2011); Lin and Lin (2008); Low et al (2011); Oliveira and Martins (2010); Wang et al (2010)
Other technical factors		Please can you list other technical factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud computing	T12	
		To what extent do you agree that the factors that you listed in T12 above will influence adoption of cloud computing?	T13	
TOE	Cost	My institution will adopt cloud technology if it is affordable and cost effective	M1	Researcher's Own adapted from Misra and

				Mondal (2011); Zhu et al (2004).
	Tech readines s	Cloud technology fits in with my institution's business strategy	M2	Yu-hui (2008); Oliveira and Martins (2010); Low et al (2011); Zhu et al (2004), Own.
	Top mgt. Support	Top management in my institution will support cloud technology adoption	M3	Borgman et al (2013); Low et al (2011); Chong et al, (2009); Wang et al (2010); Del Aguila- Obra and Padilla- Melendez (2006); Yoon and George (2013).
	Cost	My institution will consider the cost of adopting and implementing new innovation compared to the already existing ones before a decision to adopt that innovation can be made.	M4	Researcher's own backed by Misra and Mondal (2011); Zhu et al (2004).
		My institution is likely to consider long term operational and maintenance cost savings from existing technologies before deciding to adopt a new technological innovation like cloud computing.	M5	
	Trading partner pressure	IT organisations like Microsoft, Oracle, Cisco, CIW etc. that accredit IT courses in institutions require us to adopt cloud computing.	M6	Kuan and Chau (2011); Lin and Lin (2008); Low et al (2011); Oliveira and Martins (2010); Wang et al (2010)
Other management Factors		Please can you list other management factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud computing	M7	
		To what extent do you agree that the factors that you listed in M7 above will influence adoption of cloud computing?	M8	

5.2.1. Structure

Data reliability and accuracy depend on amongst others, how the questions are sequenced and how prompted responses are given (Brace, 2004). The questionnaire is divided into five categories: introduction, demography, general, technical and management categories.

Introduction: this section introduces the researcher to the prospective respondents, stating the essence of the research and how the data gathered will be used and a proof that the research has been ethically approved by the ethics committee.

Demography: this section of the questionnaire was designed to ascertain the sex, age range, department, job title, level of qualification, current job experience, total working experience and the type of cloud service models that the respondents use or have used.

General: this section was designed to make sure that all respondents answer the same questions that are not specific to the technical and management respondents but with sufficient knowledge to provide the right information to test the constructs in the research model.

Technical: this section was specifically designed to elicit technical information from a section of the sample population with technical knowledge considering the complexities of cloud computing.

Management: the final decision to adopt or not to adopt any technology or indeed cloud computing lies with the management of every institution thus, this section. The table below summarises the structure of the questionnaire.

Table 17: Questionnaire structure

<i>Introduction</i>	<p>I am a PhD research student of School of Engineering and Computing at the University of the West of Scotland. My research is on adoption of cloud computing in higher education. The aim is to investigate the factors that can influence more adoption of cloud computing in higher education as the current adoption rate is low when compared to other sectors. The survey is divided into general, technical and management sections. Please spare a few minutes to complete the general section and any other section relevant to you.</p> <p>The findings will contribute to the wider IS/IT research and specifically on the adoption and use of cloud computing in higher</p>
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	<p>education. Furthermore, it will aid institutions of higher learning to make informed strategic decisions for the future.</p> <p>Please find below the link to the survey: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/17BYQDINvBdx28_WJgoriK2TwVpSNsBg_gh9usbzd4kE/viewform</p> <p>I understand that you may not be in the position to take this survey. I would appreciate if you could help me pass on this information. Be assured that your response will be treated with strict confidentiality. If you want the summary of the findings to be communicated to you, please e-mail me: isaiah.ewuzie@uws.ac.uk</p> <p>Please ignore if you have previously responded to this survey. Attached herewith is an ethical approval letter.</p> <p>Yours sincerely, Isaiah Ewuzie.</p>
<i>Demographics</i>	<p>What is the name of your institution?</p> <p>What is your gender?</p> <p>What is your age bracket?</p> <p>What is your department?</p> <p>What is your job title?</p> <p>What is your highest level of qualification?</p> <p>What is your current job experience?</p> <p>What is your total working experience?</p> <p>Which cloud service models do you use?</p> <p>Which of the following describes you use of cloud based services (select all that apply)</p> <p>Which of the following best describes your position in your institution?</p>
<p><i>General section</i></p> <p>TAM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEOU • PU <p>TOE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relative advantage • Size • Competitive pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ It is easier to understand and familiarise oneself with our institution's cloud technology. ❖ Becoming skilful at using cloud technology was easy. ❖ Using cloud technology improves my job performance. ❖ Using cloud technology enhances my job effectiveness. ❖ My institution's adoption of cloud technology will enable me to access data quicker than usual. ❖ My institution's adoption of cloud technology will

<p>DOI</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observability <p>CSE</p>	<p>enable us to be more competitive with other institutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The number of employees in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology. ❖ The number of students in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology. ❖ The opportunity to observe and talk to those that have used cloud technology will help me to decide whether to adopt it or not. ❖ I am confident I have the necessary skills to use cloud technology. ❖ I am confident of using any form of cloud technology even if I have never used it before. ❖ Please can list other factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud computing. ❖ To what extent do you agree with factors listed above?
<p><i>Technical section</i></p> <p>TAM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEOU <p>TOE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity • Compatibility • <i>Security</i> • Technology readiness • Trialability • Trading partner pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The use of cloud technology is not as easy as I first thought. ❖ Technical challenges may hinder or prevent my institution from adopting cloud technologies ❖ New technologies are more difficult to use than already existing technologies. ❖ With cloud technology I have no concern with data security. ❖ Cloud technology is compatible with other software. ❖ Cloud technology is compatible with my institution's information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructures. ❖ My institution will adopt cloud technology if it is affordable and cost effective. ❖ My institution will consider the cost of adopting and implementing new innovation compared to the already existing ones before a decision to adopt that innovation can be made.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ My institution is likely to consider long term operational and maintenance cost savings from existing technologies before deciding to adopt a new technology like cloud computing. ❖ My institution has the infrastructural capabilities to adopt and deploy cloud based services. ❖ It is important to properly try it out before deciding on whether or not to adopt. ❖ IT organisations such as Microsoft, Oracle, Cisco, CIW that accredit IT courses in institutions require us to adopt cloud computing. ❖ Please can list other technical factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud computing. ❖ To what extent do you agree with technical factors listed above?
<p><i>Management section</i></p> <p>TOE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost • Technology readiness • Top management support • Trading partner pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ My institution will adopt cloud technology if it is affordable and cost effective. ❖ Cloud technology fit in with my institution’s business strategy. ❖ Top management in my institution will support cloud technology. ❖ My institution will consider the cost of adopting and implementing new innovation compared to the already existing ones before a decision to adopt that innovation can be made. ❖ My institution is likely to consider long term operational and maintenance cost savings from existing technologies before deciding to adopt a new technology like cloud computing. ❖ IT organisations such as Microsoft, Oracle, Cisco, CIW that accredit IT courses in institutions require us to adopt cloud computing. ❖ Please can list other management factors that you think

	<p>may influence adoption of cloud computing.</p> <p>❖ To what extent do you agree with management factors listed above?</p>
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5.3 Pilot Study

Pilot study deals with conducting a preliminary study or investigation before finally committing to the main study (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Pilot study is mainly conducted with a very small group of about 2-3 people preferably those who are likely to be part of the final study. The researcher monitors the group during the process and answers any queries that they may have and later incorporates their comments into the final version of the questionnaire (Gillham, 2011).

Pilot study is undertaken with a view to ascertaining if the procedures and instruments are adequate for a bigger study, thus giving a sense of practicality in the main study. They can be used to make estimates of response rates, non-response items, and how well they measure the concepts as intended (Dilman et al, 2009).

In the context of this research, pilot study was conducted in the form of interviews that involved 5 senior members of ICT department of UWS (see appendix 2 for email transcripts for interview request). The initial approach for interview with ICT department was on Friday the 11th of January 2013. Subsequently, interviews were conducted on Tuesday the 15th, Wednesday the 16th and Thursday the 24th of January 2013 at the ICT department of UWS.

The interview was centred on UWS e-learning projects, cloud computing in general and the feasibility of adopting cloud by institutions of higher learning. The essence was to gather as much information as possible about cloud and related projects that the university has or is undertaking. Their experiences, difficulties, attractions, advantages, disadvantages, issues, ideas, opinions, expectations, data security etc, were also discussed.

Specifically, further discussions were centred on the technical and operational difficulties that were being experienced while working on the ATMOS-EMC shared storage with other Universities in Scotland. In the end, information gathered helped in refining and reshaping this research. Furthermore, feedback from conference presentation (2012 IEEE Second Symposium on Network Cloud Computing and Application, 3-4 Dec, 2012) also helped to refocus the study.

5.4 Pilot Testing

Pilot testing on the other hand deals with improving data collection plans in terms of content and their validity, format, scales and procedures (Creswell, 2014; Robson and McCartan, 2016). Pilot testing has become an essential part of a modern research process. Thus, its importance cannot be overemphasised. The essence however, is to evaluate and establish linkages between questions, questionnaire and the implementation procedures (Dillman et al 2009). Furthermore, Dillman et al (2009) also noted that pretesting gives the researcher the opportunity to obtain expert advice from survey population on the potential problems of the questionnaire. Although pilot study will attempt to point out potential problems with questionnaire and its implementation procedures, they can be used for quantitative estimate of the response rate; identify item non-response problems and the steps to remedy them.

In this research however, questionnaire used in this study was pilot tested with two different groups of the intended respondents. The first group involved management and technical respondents from the University of the West of Scotland ICT department (2 senior managers and 3 technical staff). The second group involved academic staff (2 lecturers, a post doctorate student and 4 research students) from the School of Engineering and Computing all from the University of the West of Scotland.

Random sampling was used for the pilot test. This was done by contacting the ITDS department and appointment was made to drop off hard copies of the questionnaire for staff members to fill out. Out of the 10 copies of questionnaire dropped off, 7 were filled and 5 were found to be usable. For the second group, the researcher distributed the copies by hand at random.

The characteristics of the pilot matched closely with those of the final samples in terms of age and work experience. For example, the age is between 30-49 years and work experience of between 1-5 years. This indicates that those sampled are in the peak of their working lives and are experienced in their roles too. The pilot testing provided some interesting comments which helped to refine the final version of the questionnaire.

Below are some of the comments and feedbacks from the pilot test:

1. *I have gone through the questions and they look good. However, I will advise that you divide the questionnaire into different segments since you will be dealing with different types of respondents e.g. technical and management.*

2. *I have reviewed your questionnaire and they appear to be ok. The questions are simple therefore, I expect your respondents to answer the questions considering it's a specialty area.*
3. *They are ok for me. However, include a confidentiality statement; and that the result of the study will be communicated to them if they require and approximately how long it will take to complete the survey.*

5.5 Sample Selection

Sample consists of all unit of the population that are drawn for inclusion in the survey (Dillman et al, 2009). Population is the body of people or objects under consideration for statistical purposes (Collis and Hussey 2014). As stated earlier in chapter 3 (section 3.4.2), this study is limited to a particular area of higher education, the universities. It is impossible to include all the university population in the survey. This is because not all members of the university community are experts and are in a position to give opinion on the subject matter under investigation. However, it is imperative to have a sample that would give a proper representation of the population that is being studied (see also 5.4).

Thus, the sampling population used in this study was limited to the following categories:

- University management staff
- Technical staff (ICT)
- Academic staff (computing/IT, teaching/research)
- Other IT staff

5.5.1. Data Gathering

This section discusses the specific procedures employed to obtain data for the research. The actual request for assistance in helping to complete survey was accompanied by introduction of the research with ethical approval letter from the University of the West of Scotland. Data were collected using a web-based self-completion questionnaire survey. The web-based survey was designed using Google forms. The link to the survey was distributed to the respondents via emails.

Table 18: Total number of respondents

<i>Name of University</i>	<i>Initial request</i>	<i>Follow Up Request</i>	<i>Total number of Respondents</i>
St Andrews	7	4	2
Glasgow	90	1	12
Edinburgh	26	21	11
Aberdeen	19	14	2
Strathclyde	4	8	2
Heriot-Watt	84	84	10
University of Dundee	55	55	3
University of Stirling	41	42	10
Edinburgh Napier University	91	88	9
The Robert Gordon University	56	54	16
Glasgow Caledonian University	41	34	2
University of Abertay Dundee	12	10	2
Queen Margaret University	1	2	0
University of the West of Scotland	95	71	15
University of the Highlands and the Islands	3	3	3
Total	625	491	99

The table 19 above indicates that a total of 625 were initially sent out. Due to slow response rate, a total of 491 follow up and reminders were also sent out, yielding a total of 99 responses. As stated earlier (section 3.4.2), this method of data collection was adopted because it is impossible to cover all the location of 15 Universities interviewing people. Moreover, similar studies also adopted the same method (Low et al, 2011). The table below shows sample characteristic of the studied institutions.

Table 19: Institution categorisation based on staff and student numbers (Source: HESA, 2014/15 session).

<i>Institution</i>	<i>Academic Staff</i>			<i>Total non-academic staff</i>	<i>Total atypical staff</i>	<i>Number of students</i>				
	<i>FT</i>	<i>PT</i>	<i>Total</i>			<i>UG</i>		<i>PG</i>		<i>Total</i>
						<i>FT</i>	<i>PT</i>	<i>FT</i>	<i>PT</i>	
Edinburgh Napier University	505	345	850	885	5	1150	1170	9310	1495	13125
Glasgow Caledonian University	620	150	770	840	710	1645	1195	11910	2185	16935
Heriot-Watt University	765	30	795	1105	290	2015	1560	6595	450	10620
The Robert Gordon University	480	265	745	840	0	1650	2490	7530	1575	13245
University of Aberdeen	1260	405	1665	1880	320	2415	1570	9395	650	14030
University of Dundee	1275	260	1535	1745	885	1665	3315	8770	1430	15180
University of Edinburgh	3495	785	4280	4525	3760	6655	2125	19315	780	28875
University of Glasgow	2360	820	3175	3585	1640	5725	1930	16985	2180	26820
University of St Andrews	1020	140	1160	1370	730	2400	330	7020	910	10660
University of Stirling	545	40	940	1150	0	1885	1220	7370	625	12935
University of Strathclyde	1200	225	1430	1935	1460	3965	2575	12205	2460	21205
University of the Highlands and the Islands	30	5	35	185	5	100	135	5020	2395	7650
University of the West of Scotland	560	50	610	895	175	835	1000	9855	3045	14735

University of Abertey Dundee	185	25	210	335	150	185	160	3630	245	4220
Queen Margaret University	160	85	250	225	310	495	1175	3030	565	5265

5.5.2 Improving Response Rate

The rate of response in research is affected by different factors. These factors include: the nature of the sample, length of questionnaire type of survey and other related factors (de Vaus, 2014). In addition to the use of web-based self-completion questionnaire, other methods were also employed with a view to increasing the response rate in this research. Specifically, follow up email reminders, telephone calls, visits to different Universities were undertaken in an effort to increase the response rate. However, the researcher is of the opinion that the response rate may have been higher had it not been for the period of absence due to personal reasons. Therefore, inability to immediately follow up respondents could have affected the rate of response.

5.6 UWS Digital Strategy

In UWS, different digital units are headed by different heads. However these units are facilitated by ITDS. From strategic view point for example, head of education features is tasked with the overall strategy of delivering learning and teaching in the digital age. Security is considered to be one of the major attractions in cloud adoption. It is interesting to know that ability to harmonise data storage in a single platform was also considered to be attractive because in this way institution is able take control of their data, monitor data access thus, effectively manage resources and minimise security issues inherent in the sharing of resources among multiple locations.

Currently the university is making use of Microsoft 365 for cloud sharing and file storage. Syncplicity, a flexible, scalable, and secure cloud platform for file sharing is also being considered. This came about because the data centre server storage in Hamilton campus is due for renewal thus; it provided opportunity for the university to consider other file sharing options. Going forward, the data centre in Hamilton will be shot and purpose-built data centre is planned for Paisley campus with disaster recovery (DR) capabilities.

There are other digital platforms specifically designed for certain purposes. For instance my PGR platform was designed to monitor the progress of PhD students from inception to completion. Pure Research on the other hand was designed for the academics to upload their scholarly works, update their profiles as well as for reference purposes. Furthermore the Student Hub a one stop access point for inquiries was designed as a centre point for all help desk activities using top desk product. The top desk product allows the hub to co-ordinate the activities of all other help desk centrally.

In conclusion, this chapter presented the methods used in data collection. It went further to operationalise the variables as well as discussion on the structure of the questionnaire. It also presented details of the pilot testing; and sample selection and justification. Furthermore, it presented details of the surveyed institutions, the number of respondents from each institution (table 18) and categorised the institutions by staff (table 19 above) and how response rate could be improved. Finally, the chapter is concluded with a discussion on the digital strategy of UWS.

CHAPTER 6- DATA ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the demographic characteristics, detailed analysis and the results of the research data. Finally hypotheses are tested with significant and insignificant results also presented.

6.1 Data Preparation

Data obtained for the research was prepared in readiness for analysis before the actual analysis was performed. At this stage, questions that were negatively worded in the questionnaire were reverse coded before data analysis commenced. The figure below shows the processes involved in preparation of data before analysis.

Figure 15: Processes of data preparation and analysis

This research adhered to the procedures of preparing data before analysing as recommended by Pallant (2013). These are: preparing data file, defining and labelling variables, entering data, screening and cleaning the data and the actual data analysis (figure 15).

6.2 Demographic Study

As stated in section 5.5.1 the survey was conducted online using Google Forms where respondents completed the questionnaire by following the link in their email. Before analysis, data was checked for errors and incompleteness. After data cleaning, 89 of the 99 responses were found to be usable and 10 were discarded due to incomplete or missing values. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24 was used to analyse the data.

6.3 Participants

The participants for this study were drawn from 15 universities across Scotland with varying numbers of respondents completing the questionnaire. The universities surveyed in this research are: University of St Andrews, University of Glasgow, University of Edinburgh, University of Aberdeen, University of Strathclyde, Heriot-Watt University, University of Dundee, University of Stirling, Edinburgh Napier University, The Robert Gordon University, Glasgow Caledonian University, University of Abertay Dundee, Queen Margaret University, University of the West of Scotland and University of the Highlands and Islands.

The request to participate in the survey was emailed individually to the participants. The email included ethical approval letter and the link to the Google Form where the participants can access the survey. As discussed previously in chapter (section 5.5), the sample population was selected because they were deemed to be knowledgeable in the subject matter being researched and were in a position to give their opinion.

Besides, respondents answered to the request to participate in the survey differently. Some responded immediately and passed the request to other colleagues, some request came back via automatic replies and some respondents even doubted the authenticity of the ethical approval. The table 20 below summarises how respondents responded to the request to participate in the survey. The names and contact details of the respondents have been blurred to protect their anonymity and confidentiality.

Table 20: Some respondents' reply for request to take part in the survey (Source: own)

No	Respondent's reply
1	<p>Hello Isaiah</p> <p>Thanks for your email. I've answered the survey and passed onto colleagues too.</p> <p>Good luck</p> <p>Xxx</p>
2	<p>Dear Isaiah</p> <p>Thanks for the e-mail. I am currently looking for someone to forward this to and will get back to you as soon as I can.</p> <p>Best wishes,</p> <p>Xxxxx</p>
3	<p>Dear Isiah</p> <p>I suspect you should be sending this sort of survey to computer support officers, and heads of department. For xxxxxxxx that would be xxx@xx.xxxx.ac.uk</p>

	<p>(computer support group) and xxx@xx.xxxx.ac.uk (prof Xxxxxx Xxxxxx).</p> <p>Best wishes, Xxxxxx</p>
4	<p>I will be on maternity leave until May 2017.</p> <p>Should your enquiry relate to the Researcher Development Training Programme, please contact Xxx XxxXxx Xxx.XxxXxx@xxx.ac.uk</p> <p>Should your enquiry relate to Academic Writing, please contact Xxxxx Xxxxxxx: Xxxxxx.Xxxxxx@xxx.ac.uk</p> <p>For all other Graduate School enquiries please contact Prof Xxxxxx Xxxxxx:X.Xxxxxx@xxx.ac.uk</p>
5	<p>Since you are doing research ... can I suggest that you start by looking at our staff pages, research pages and staff publications and then target your email.</p> <p>Cheers</p> <p>Xxxxxxx</p>
6	<p>Hi</p> <p>I can receive attachments - if you send me through the ethics approval I can see if I can pass on.</p> <p>Xxxxxxx</p>

Data was collected from 99 respondents that included the management staff, technical staff, academic staff (computing/IT, teaching/research) and other IT staff members of the various universities. The study started by analysing the demographics as respondents involved different types of staff with varying degrees of experience and knowledge and have used or made use of different cloud models for different purposes. Thus, demographics were considered to be significant in this study.

6.3.1 Breakdown of Participants by Institutions

The table below shows the breakdown of participants by universities and the number of respondents by section of the questionnaire. The table indicates that usable responses were collected from 13 of the 15 universities surveyed with the exception of Glasgow Caledonian University and Queen Margaret University. Only one respondent from the University of the Highlands and the Island completed the management section of the questionnaire. Inadequate responses from the management section of the questionnaire means analysis could not be carried out as inference cannot be made with only one response. In effect, the management group was eliminated before analysis. Furthermore, all respondents answered the general

section before proceeding to technical or management section. Thus, the column of total respondents is equivalent to the total number of respondents in the general section column in the table below.

Table 21: Breakdown of participants by the Universities

<i>Name of the Institution</i>	<i>Section of the Questionnaire Answered by Respondents</i>			<i>Total respondents</i>
	<i>General section</i>	<i>Technical section</i>	<i>Management section</i>	
Edinburgh Napier University	9	9	0	n = 9
Heriot-Watt University	10	10	0	n = 10
The Robert Gordon University	13	13	0	n = 13
University of Aberdeen	2	2	0	n = 2
University of Dundee	3	3	0	n = 3
University of Edinburgh	11	11	0	n = 11
University of Glasgow	12	12	0	n = 12
University of St Andrews	1	1	0	n = 1
University of Stirling	10	10	0	n = 10
University of Strathclyde	2	2	0	n = 2
* *University of the Highlands and the Islands	2	1	1	n = 1
University of the West of Scotland	13	13	0	n = 13
University of Abertey Dundee	2	2	0	n = 2
<i>Total by section of questionnaire</i>	<i>*90</i>	<i>89</i>	<i>*1</i>	<i>n = 89</i>

** One of the respondents answered management section. However, since the number is not enough to make inference, it was not used in data analysis thus; total number of respondents is one instead of two.

* 90 represent the total number respondents in the general section. Though 89 were analysed because one response is not enough to make inference as stated earlier thus was eliminated from the analysis. Management section has only 1 response and was eliminated before analysis was performed.

Surveyed Institutions

Figure 16: Participating institutions

Table 22: Surveyed institutions

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Edinburgh Napier University	9	10.1	10.1	10.1
Herriot-Watt University	10	11.2	11.2	21.3
The Robert Gordon University	13	14.6	14.6	36.0
University of Aberdeen	2	2.2	2.2	38.2
University of Dundee	3	3.4	3.4	41.6
University of Edinburgh	11	12.4	12.4	53.9
University of Glasgow	12	13.5	13.5	67.4
University of St Andrews	1	1.1	1.1	68.5
University of Stirling	10	11.2	11.2	79.8
University of Strathclyde	2	2.2	2.2	82.0
University of the Highlands and the Islands	1	1.1	1.1	83.1
University of the West of Scotland	13	14.6	14.6	97.8
University of Abertay Dundee	2	2.2	2.2	100.0
Total	89	100.0	100.0	

The table above indicates that the highest responses of 15% were obtained from the Robert Gordon University and the University of the West of Scotland. The University of St Andrews and the University of the Highland and the Island accounted for the lowest response rate of 2% and 1% respectively. The response rate may have been affected by a number of factors details of which have been explained in section 5.5.2.

6.3.2 Gender

The table below shows that the participants were mainly males (75) representing 87.2% and (11) females representing 12.4% of the surveyed population. It therefore shows that a relatively small fraction of females completed the survey when compared to males. This result also reflects the dominance of males in the IT industry (Smith, 2013).

Table 23: Respondents gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	75	84.3	87.2	87.2
Female	11	12.4	12.8	100.0
Total	86	96.6	100.0	
Missing System	3	3.4		
Total	89	100.0		

6.3.3 Age Bracket

The figure below (histogram) indicates that the greater percentage of the respondents was between ages of 40-49 followed by 30-39 age range. It shows that majority of the respondents are in the peak of their working lives which also indicates the level of experience acquired by these age ranges. The age range of 20-29 is the lowest which indicated that they may have less experience and at the beginning of their working lives. Very few respondents aged 60 plus took part and accounted for 13.5% of the overall figures.

Figure 17: Age brackets of respondents

6.3.4 Respondents' Departments

The table below indicates that 43.8% of the surveyed population was from Computer Science Department followed by IT services with 14.6%. Just over 11% of the respondents were from Computer Science and Mathematics Department and Engineering accounted for 10% while Computing Science and Digital Media, Informatics and other comprised of 13.5%. Bearing in mind that cloud computing is a speciality area in IT, the data obtained cut across departments relevant to the study.

Table 24: Respondents departments

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Computer Science	39	43.8	47.0	47.0
	Computer Science and Mathematics	10	11.2	12.0	59.0
	Computing Science and Digital Media	3	3.4	3.6	62.7
	Informatics	6	6.7	7.2	69.9
	IT Services	13	14.6	15.7	85.5
	Engineering	9	10.1	10.8	96.4
	Other	3	3.4	3.6	100.0
	Total	83	93.3	100.0	
Missing Values		6	6.7		
Total		89	100.0		

The table below indicates how the respondents' departments were grouped.

Table 25: Department grouping

Your Department	Actual Grouping
Computer Science	Computer Science
Computer and Information Sciences	Computer Science
Computing	Computer Science
Computer Science and Mathematics	Computer Science and Mathematics
Computing Science and Digital Media	Computing Science and Digital Media
Informatics	Informatics
IT Services	IT Services
ITDS	IT Services
Learning and Information Services	IT Services
Research Information Systems	IT Services
Learning Innovation	IT Services
Engineering	Engineering
Science Engineering and Technology	Engineering
Engineering and Physical Sciences	Engineering

Physics	Other
Philosophy	Other
Estate Solutions	Other

6.3.5 Job Title

The table below indicates that respondents with job title grouping of technical staff are made up of 22.5% while academic staff grouping comprised of 77.5% of the surveyed population. Table 28 below shows the grouping of respondent's job title.

Table 26: Respondents job title

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Valid Technical Staff	20	22.5	22.5	22.5
Academic Staff	69	77.5	77.5	100.0
Total	89	100.0	100.0	

The table below shows how the actual grouping of respondents by their job titles

Table 27: Job title grouping

Job Title	Actual Grouping
Management Staff	Systems Manager
	Manager Computing
	IT Customer Relationship Manager
	Information Solutions Manager
	Head of School
	Head of IT and Strategy Governance
	Director of LIS
	Director of Teaching
	Associate Dean Learning, Teaching and Quality
	Software Engineering Manager
	Head of IT Services
Technical Staff	IT Analyst
	Database Administrator
	E-learning Technologist
	Systems Developer
	Technical Officer
	Technician
	Senior Systems Analyst
	Senior Technician
	Senior Infrastructure Analyst
	Analyst/Programmer
Academic staff	Lecturer
	Senior Lecturer

	Professor
	Research Fellow
	Research Assistants
	Associate Professor
	Research Associate
	IT Tutor
	Reader
	PhD Student
	Senior Research Assistant
	Senior Research Fellow
	Chancellor's Fellow
	Pg Student
Other	PRDA

Job Title

Figure 18: Job title

6.3.6 Highest Qualification

The pie chart below shows that 61% of the respondents have the highest qualification of PhD. 14% obtained MSc/M.Eng/MBA/Med and further 14% were educated to the level of B.Sc. Those with PgD qualification accounted for 7%, HND/HNC was made up of 2% while other qualifications (Scottish Higher and SVQ Level 3) was made up of 2%. In general, 89% of the respondents were educated to Bachelor's degree and above. It shows that respondents are well educated and knowledgeable, thus an indication of the quality of data obtained.

Figure 19: Highest qualification

6.3.7 Current Work Experience

The table below indicates that majority of the respondents have 1-5, 6-10 and above 26 years of experience in their current jobs. Only 10% of respondents have less than 1 year experience in their current jobs. Generally, it is an indication that respondents have very high level of experience in their current positions and therefore can give valid opinion on the subject matter.

Table 28: Respondents current work experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 1 year	9	10.1	10.8	10.8
	1-5 years	24	27.0	28.9	39.8
	6-10 years	12	13.5	14.5	54.2
	11-15 years	8	9.0	9.6	63.9
	16-20 years	8	9.0	9.6	73.5
	21- 25 years	9	10.1	10.8	84.3
	26 years and above	13	14.6	15.7	100.0
	Total	83	93.3	100.0	
Total	Missing Values	6	6.7		
		89	100.0		

Figure 20: Current job experience

6.3.8 Total Working Experience

The table below shows that cumulative year of working experience of respondents are very high. More than 30% of the surveyed population have accumulated more than 26 years of working experience. Only 1% of the population have less than 1 year of cumulative working experience.

Table 29: Total working experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 1 year	1	1.1	1.2	1.2
	1-5 years	6	6.7	7.0	8.1
	6-16 years	11	12.4	12.8	20.9
	11-15 years	12	13.5	14.0	34.9
	16-20 years	12	13.5	14.0	48.8
	21-25 years	15	16.9	17.4	66.3
	26 years and above	29	32.6	33.7	100.0
	Total	86	96.6	100.0	
Missing	System	3	3.4		
Total		89	100.0		

Figure 21: Total working experience

6.4 Research Credibility

6.4.1 Reliability and Validity

Reliability describes the degree of consistency of results over time. It shows how free it is from random error (Pallant, 2013). Reliability is important because in its absence it may not be possible to associate validity of the scores of the scales. Test retest reliability (temporal stability) and internal consistency are the two frequently used indicators of scale reliability. Test retest reliability is obtained by calculating correlation from two scores administered on the same people at two different times. Internal consistency describes the extent to which items that make up the scale are all measuring attributes. Internal consistency is measured in different of ways. Cronbach's coefficient alpha is generally used in statistics (Pallant, 2013).

Cronbach's alpha measures the internal consistency (measures if a set of items in a group are related or otherwise). It is regarded as the measure of scale of reliability. The nature and purpose of scale may determine the level of reliability but 0.7 or higher is deemed acceptable (DeVillis, 2012; Nunnally, 1978). The table below shows the result of Cronbach's coefficient alpha test.

Table 30: Reliability statistics

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.605	.711	15

The above result of Cronbach's coefficient test indicates that reliability is below 0.7 but a value slightly below 0.7 are still acceptable (Adams and Lawrence, 2015) but could be abandoned if is below 0.35 (Chang et al, 2007). The table above indicates that reliability is above 0.35 thus, usable for the research. Cronbach's Alpha formula is shown below:

$$\alpha = \frac{N\bar{r}}{(1-(N-1)\bar{r}}$$

N = number of items

\bar{r} = mean inter-items correlation

With increase in the number of items, Cronbach's alpha increases. Consequently, average low inter-item correlation also means low alpha while increase in the average inter-item correlation results in increase in Cronbach's alpha.

Reliability scores could vary due to sample and the wording of the instruments (Pallant, 2013). Other factors such as duration between the time of administration and collection of data as well as nature of sampling population (heterogeneous or homogeneous) could also affect the reliability scores (Krabbe, 2016). When some of the items of the instruments were reduced by half, Cronbach's coefficient of about 0.7 was achieved. However, achieving higher Cronbach's alpha requires adding new items that are a representation of the construct though it may lead to low interitem correlations (Krabbe, 2016). Cronbach (2004) noted that many incomplete items could affect reliability. However, he suggested that such data may still be used only if it is to trim the data set and incomplete data set have been eliminated. Reliability is viewed as consistency within measurements and there are arguments about the concept of reliability as a correlation of an instrument with itself and others as a parallel test. For example, when instruments are being applied twice the respondents may be unchanged even without recalling the first response. Therefore, the consistencies of the two identical instruments will indicate uncertainty due to measurement error (Cronbach, 2004). According to Cronbach:

“The formal definitions of the concept of reliability have not considered internal consistency of an instrument as equivalent to reliability; therefore, internal consistency formulas are suspect” (p. 395).

He went further to say that these arguments are still unresolved. It therefore means that there appears to be no agreed criteria for measuring acceptable level of reliability.

From the foregoing, it has been established that reliability could be affected by a number of factors. Thus, in the context of this research, data was collected over a period of time (September to December 2015, October to December 2016 and February 2017); and after reminders were sent out to the respondents. Therefore the researcher is confident that the instrument used in this study can be used again to measure the same phenomenon

6.4.2 Validity

Validity is the extent to which instrument measures what it was intended to measure. There is no hard and fast rule about the scales of validity, rather it involves gathering of empirical data

(Pallant, 2013). There are different forms of validity that are used in both qualitative and quantitative research. Those relevant to this research are discussed in the next section.

Face Validity

Face validity is the extent to which items are judged to be appropriate to the construct of the study by respondents. Sometimes face validity and content validity are used interchangeably since they both measure appropriateness and representation of the construct (Hardesty and Bearden 2004). The questionnaire items were checked for face validity before and after a pilot study that involved both technical (Information Technology and Digital Services ITDS) and academic staff of UWS. Their response and feedback helped to reshape the constructs and the items (section 5.2.4).

Content Validity

Content validity checks for accurate representation of the theoretical construct of the items. This research is underpinned by a combination of theories and models. Section 5.2 (table 16) shows construct items and operationalisation of the survey instruments with supporting literatures. It is also worth mentioning here that some questions were introduced to customise the research instruments to the context of the study. There are also cases of existing questions in that needed to be customised.

Construct Validity

Construct validity seeks to understand the relationships between constructs. This can be assessed in two ways convergent or discriminatory validity. Construct validity tests theoretical concepts and hypotheses of the variable or constructs (Pallant 2013). In other words, it entails testing attributes that are not operationally clear.

The table below shows 52 questions were checked for validity. Some questions were eliminated because they are not measuring what they were intended to measure in terms of content or construct thus, deemed not suitable for the research.

Table 31: Questionnaire before checking for validity

<i>Perceived Ease of Use</i>

- | |
|---|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. It is easy to understand and familiarise oneself with our institution's cloud technology.2. It is easy to get used to our institution's cloud technology.3. Becoming skilful at using cloud technology was easy. |
|---|

Perceived Usefulness

4. Using cloud technology enables me to accomplish tasks easily.
5. Using cloud technology improves my job performance.
6. Using cloud technology gives me greater control over my work.
7. Using cloud technology improves my productivity
8. Using cloud technology enhances my job effectiveness
9. I find using cloud technology useful in my job.

Relative Advantage

10. My institution's use of cloud technology will enable me to perform specific tasks more quickly.
11. My institution's adoption of cloud will enable me to access data quicker.
12. My institution's adoption of cloud will enable us to have more flexibility in the day-to-day running of the institution.
13. The adoption of cloud technologies by institutions of higher learning will lead to more operational effectiveness and efficiency.
14. My institution's adoption of cloud will give me more storage space that I require to do my jobs.
15. Cloud technology provides me with more functionality that I require in my job.
16. With cloud technology I can perform more functions as a user.
17. I would convince my institution of the advantages of cloud based services.

Complexity

18. The use of cloud technologies is not as easy as I first thought.
19. Technical challenges may hinder or prevent my institution from adopting cloud technologies.
20. New technologies are more complex to understand and use than already existing technologies?
21. New technologies are more difficult to understand and use than already existing technologies?

Compatibility

22. The use of cloud is compatible with all aspects of my work.
23. Cloud technology fits well with my current work situation and activities.
24. Cloud technology is compatible with other software.
25. Cloud technology adoption is compatible with my institution's information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure.

Security

26. With cloud technology have no concern with data security

Cost

- 27. I consider cloud technology to be cost effective.
- 28. My institution will consider the cost of adopting and implementing new innovation compared to the already existing ones before a decision to adopt that innovation can be made.
- 29. My institution is likely to consider long term operational and maintenance cost savings from existing technologies before deciding to adopt a new technological innovation like cloud computing.
- 30. Expected return on investment (ROI) would be considered before adopting a technological innovation.
- 31. My institution will adopt cloud technology if it is affordable.

Technology Readiness

- 32. Cloud technology fits in with my institution's business strategy.
- 33. My institution has the infrastructural capabilities to adopt and deploy cloud services.

Top Management Support

- 34. Top management in my institution is interested in adopting cloud technologies.
- 35. Top management in my institution considers cloud adoption important.
- 36. Top management in my institution has shown support for cloud adoption

Firm Size

- 37. The number of employees in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology.
- 38. The number of students in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology.

Competitive Pressure

- 39. My institution's adoption of cloud will enable us to be competitive with other higher institutions.
- 40. My institution's adoption of innovative technology like cloud will be appealing to more people and may attract more students.
- 41. Inability of my institution to adopt and deploy latest technologies like cloud may lead to students changing to institutions with such latest technologies.

Trading Partner Pressure

- 42. IT organisations like Microsoft, Oracle, Cisco, CIW etc. that accredit IT courses in institutions require us to adopt cloud computing.

Trialability

- 43. I would need to use a trial version before adopting cloud computing.
- 44. It is important to properly try it out before deciding on whether or not to adopt.
- 45. The opportunity to talk to those that have used it will help me to decide

Observability

- 46. The opportunity to observe others using cloud will help me to decide whether to adopt it or not.
- 47. I have had the opportunity to see how cloud computing is being used at my work place.
- 48. I have had the opportunity to know the benefits of cloud computing.

Self-efficacy

- 49. I feel confident using any form of cloud technology in my daily job.
- 50. I am confident that I have the necessary skill to use cloud technology.
- 51. I feel confident of using cloud technology even if I had never used it before.
- 52. I am confident of using cloud technology by just seeing someone using it before I try it myself.

6.5 Relationships between Constructs Technology-Organisation-Environment, Diffusion of Innovation and Computer Self-Efficacy

Before testing for relationship between variables, the two main types of statistical tests (parametric and non-parametric) are discussed with justification for the type of test chosen.

Parametric Test

Parametric test is a statistical test based on the assumption that certain parameters of the population are normally distributed (Pallant, 2013). For instance t-test and analysis of variance assumed the population to be normally distributed or with equal variances. Parametric test are used for interval data i.e. numeric data. Numeric data are the type of data where the order and difference between the values are known. For instance, the difference between 70cm and 50cm is 20cm. In the above example, the order and the difference between the two values are known; 20cm.

Test of Normality

To determine normality, histograms of the sample are plotted and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests are conducted. Normality is therefore measured depending on the skewness and kurtosis of the values (Pallan, 2013). Skewness deals with how symmetrical the scores of the distribution

are and kurtosis deals with the degree of the peaks of the distribution (Adams and Lawrence, 2015). Similarly, Pallant (2013) noted that skewness of score sometimes depends on the nature of the construct being measured and not necessarily a problem with scale.

The result of the significance of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test will determine if the normality assumption is violated or not. For a non-significant result (sig. value of $>.05$) indicates normality. However, the table below indicates sig. values of $.000$ thus, normality assumption is violated because the sig. value obtained is less than $.05$. The table below shows that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is non-significant thus; there is a violation of the normality assumption. Normality violation can also be determined from the skewness and kurtosis (Pallant, 2013).

Table 32: Test of normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
PEOU	.318	89	.000	.826	89	.000
PU	.294	89	.000	.853	89	.000
RELATIVE ADVANTAGE	.330	89	.000	.807	89	.000
COMPLEXITY	.253	89	.000	.850	89	.000
COMPATIBILITY	.318	89	.000	.785	89	.000
SECURITY	.300	89	.000	.845	89	.000
TECHNOLOGY READINESS	.339	87	.000	.805	87	.000
INSTITUTION SIZE	.217	88	.000	.901	88	.000
COST	.276	89	.000	.844	89	.000
COMPETITIVE PRESSURE	.246	88	.000	.880	88	.000
TRADING PARTNER PRESSURE	.272	88	.000	.877	88	.000
TRIALABILITY	.317	88	.000	.773	88	.000
OBSERVABILITY	.245	86	.000	.887	86	.000
COMPUTER SELF-EFFICACY	.288	89	.000	.805	89	.000
ADOPTION	.193	87	.000	.911	87	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Since this research does not meet parametric assumptions and it deals with ordinal ranked data non-parametric test is used.

Non-parametric Test

Non-parametric test on the other hand is the type of test where no assumptions are made e.g. Spearman's rho, Mann-Whitney U, Chi-square and Kruskal-Wallis. Non-parametric tests are used for categorical and ordinal ranked data. Furthermore, they are used when data does not meet parametric assumptions (Pallant, 2013). Categorical data are data that are grouped in categories e.g. people being grouped into race, age, sex etc. Ordinal scales are usually used to measure non-numeric concepts where the difference between the orders of the values is not well known. For instance, using cloud technology enhances my job effectiveness:

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

The above example indicates that there is a difference between strongly disagree and disagree; and between agree and strongly agree, such a difference could not be quantified numerically as cloud is a non-numeric concept. The determining factor in the type of statistics to be conducted is the scale of measurement used in the variables rather than the type of research design (Adams and Lawrence, 2015).

A non-parametric test, Spearman rho was used to test the relationships among the variables. Spearman rho is generally used in non-parametric statistics to analyse the relationships between two ordinal variables. The correlation coefficient ranges in values of -1.0 to +1.0. Absolute values closer to 1.0 indicate a positive relationship while values closer to -1.0 indicate a negative relationship. Values of 0.0 are a reflection of little or no relationship (Lawrence and Adams 2015). It was Cohen et al (2007) who grouped the scales into small, medium and large and suggested the range of values in each of the groups as shown in the table below.

Table 33: Scale of correlation

Small	r=.10 to .29
Medium	r=.30 to .49
Large	r=.5 to .1

6.6 Correlation

Correlation deals with relationships and also tends to identify patterns between variables. Since relationships and their strength between factors that affect adoption of cloud computing are vital in this study, Spearman correlation is used in the investigation to determine the positivity or negativity of the values as well as the relationships between Technology-Organisation-Environment, Diffusion of Innovation and Computer Self-Efficacy. The table below shows the correlation matrix of the all variables and constructs.

Table 34: Correlation matrix

			ADOP TION	TECH	ORG	ENV	DOI	CSE
Spearman's rho	ADOPTION	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.295**	.043	.071	.130	.165
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.006	.696	.573	.242	.145
		N	87	86	84	65	83	80
	TECH	Correlation Coefficient	.295**	1.000	-.026	-.111	.001	.107
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.	.811	.371	.992	.340
		N	86	88	86	67	85	82
	ORG	Correlation Coefficient	.043	-.026	1.000	-.243*	-.039	-.053
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.696	.811	.	.050	.724	.640
		N	84	86	86	66	83	80
	ENV	Correlation Coefficient	.071	-.111	-.243*	1.000	.060	-.072
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.573	.371	.050	.	.634	.574
		N	65	67	66	67	66	63
	DOI	Correlation Coefficient	.130	.001	-.039	.060	1.000	.073
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.242	.992	.724	.634	.	.523
		N	83	85	83	66	85	79
	CSE	Correlation Coefficient	.165	.107	-.053	-.072	.073	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.145	.340	.640	.574	.523	.
		N	80	82	80	63	79	82

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 35: Correlation analysis

Constructs		Hypotheses	Correlation Co-efficient	Significance of Correlation
Technology	<i>Adoption of Cloud Computing</i>	H ₁	.128	.238
Organisation		H ₂	.075	.490
Environment		H ₃	-.014	.703
Diffusion of innovation		H ₄	.092	.398
Computer self-efficacy		H ₅	.239*	.026
*.Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

There are six variables in the Technology construct, four in the organisation construct, two in the environment construct and two in the diffusion of innovation construct. The overall hypotheses as shown in table 35 above were obtained by computing the mean scores of the constituent variables. These mean scores were then used to create a single variable for technology, organisation, environment, diffusion of innovation to obtain the overall hypotheses.

6.7 Further Analysis

Judging from the correlation matrix (appendix 5), it appears that some constructs and variables show high correlations indicating relationships with adoption of cloud computing thus, it requires a more detailed analysis.

Before further analysis is performed, it is important to classify the data into different subgroups. In other words, the constructs are examined as a group and analysed depending on variations between dependent and independent variables. Generally, cluster analysis is used in classifying data into homogeneous cases and subgroups. Thus, they are analysed in such a way that those in the same group or cluster are similar to each other than those in other clusters.

In this research, the dependent variable is the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning while independent variables are the TAM, TOE, DOI and CSE factors that affect adoption of cloud computing. The independent variables ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree

are regarded as being in different groups thus, not suitable for cluster analysis. From the foregoing for example, it can be argued that respondents who strongly disagree on technology could be considered as belonging to a group and those who disagree or are neutral, agree or strongly agree could be considered as belonging to another group and so on. Such an approach of performing analysis based on classifying data into subgroups is referred to as planned groups tool (Pallant, 2013) and has been successfully applied in adoption of new technology research (Godoe and Johansen 2012).

In the 7-point Likert scale some groups are merged to form a new group. For example slightly disagree and disagree were merged with disagree while slightly agree were merged with agree. Neutral cannot be merged as it does not logically belong to either group. However, if the results of neutral are significant for a particular option it will be reported. Some researchers have used a 7-point Likert scale (Yoon and George, 2013; Yu and Tao, 2009).

In the context of this research, the independent variables of TOE, DOI, and CSE were measured using a 5-point Likert scale (in ascending order). This is because of the complexities involved in the analysis and interpretation. Besides, similar research used a 5-point Likert scale (Godoe and Johansen, 2012; Low et al, 2011, Chang et al 2007; Butler and Sellbom, 2002).

Table 36: 5 Point Likert scale group

Group	Scale
1	Strongly disagree
2	Disagree
3	Neutral
4	Agree
5	Strongly agree

The table below shows the new groupings.

Table 37: New groupings

Group	Scale
1	Strongly disagree
2	Disagree
3	Agree
4	Strongly agree

Having established that parametric assumption was violated (section 6.5), non-parametric test is therefore performed. This research carried out Kruskal-Wallis test as it allows for comparison of mean scores with one variable with at least three groups (Pallant, 2013; Adams and Lawrence, 2015). From the foregoing, the mean value of adoption of cloud computing will be analysed to determine whether the groupings (table 37) above showed relationships and the type of relationships with the dependent variables.

6.8 Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses testing are usually carried out to determine the probability of achieving a result or set of results (Adams and Lawrence, 2015).

6.8.1 Technology and Adoption of Cloud Computing

To verify the relationships between the independent variables (TOE, DOI and CSE) and the dependent variable (adoption of cloud computing), hypotheses were formulated (see appendix 1) and are discussed in the rest of the section.

As stated in section 6.7, Kruskal-Wallis test allows for comparison of mean scores with one variable with at least three groups thus, it is considered suitable for this research. Table 38 below shows the output generated by forming Kruskal-Wallis test. The observed Chi-square as indicated in the table is 8.444; df is 3 and significance level of .038. The critical value of df 3 is 7.81. The observed value higher than the critical value indicates relationship between variables (Field, 2009) and less than .05 indicates a statistically significant difference across the group (Pallant, 2015). Since the observed value 8.444 is higher than the critical value 7.81, then there is a significant relationship between technology and adoption of cloud computing. Consequently, the significance level for df 3 is .038 (at $p=.05$), indicates statistically significant difference in the group.

Table 38 shows that the mean rank increases with increase across the groups of technological variables slightly decreasing in the strongly agree group. Thus, there is a significant relationship between technology adoption of cloud computing.

Table 38: Technology and mean of adoption

Technology	Mean rank of adoption
Strongly disagree	28.42
Disagree	43.28
Agree	54.13
Strongly agree	45.17
Chi-square= 8.444; df=3 and p=0.38	

From the foregoing, it has been established that technology is significantly related to adoption of cloud computing. However, further analysis will be carried out on the different components that make up technology variables to determine the extent and the overall effect across the group.

Table 39 below shows the mean rank of adoption with change in levels across variables that make up technological components in the adoption process. It shows increasing level of consistency from strongly disagree to strongly agree in five of the variables (PEOU, PU, RA, Compatibility and Security) with the exception of complexity. The complexity variable shows a decrease in the mean rank and then increase. For instance, the mean of adoption in complexity variable decreases from 58.67 in the strongly disagree group to 43.44 in the disagree group. It then increases again from 34.19 in the agree group to 44.50 in the strongly agree group. It therefore shows that all six variables contributed to adoption of cloud computing with complexity perhaps having the least effect in terms of how technology affects adoption.

Table 39: Adoption for different variables of technology

Levels	Adoption and mean rank					
	Perceived ease of use	Perceived usefulness	Relative advantage	Complexity	Compatibility	Security
Strongly disagree	36.24	18.13	15.50	58.67	32.99	34.39
Disagree	38.50	38.94	29.35	43.44	34.88	36.67
Agree	39.28	38.78	41.19	34.19	42.13	39.14
Strongly agree	42.50	44.23	54.82	44.50	53.75	42.50

6.8.2 Organisation and Adoption of Cloud Computing

The relationship between organisation and adoption of cloud computing was hypothesized (see appendix 1).

As with the preceding section, Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to test the relationship between organisation and adoption of cloud computing. The output generated is shown in table 40 below. The observed Chi-square value is 1.483 and the df is 3. The critical value for df=3 at p=.05 is 7.81. With the observed value (1.483) less than the critical value (7.81), it means there is an insignificant relationship between organisation and adoption of cloud computing.

A critical examination of the mean rank values of adoption indicates no clear pattern. For example, the values increased from 31.17 in the strongly disagree group to 43.96 in the disagree group. It then decreased to 42.94 in the agree group before slightly decreasing further to 42.44 in the strongly agree group. Besides the significant increase from strongly disagree to disagree, the mean rank value obtained from agree to strongly agree is negligible, thus organisation has no relationships and does not confirm the hypotheses.

Table 40: Organisation and mean of adoption

Organisation	Mean rank of adoption
Strongly disagree	31.17
Disagree	43.96
Agree	42.94
Strongly agree	42.44
Chi-square= 1.183; df=3 and p=.686	

Further analysis will be carried out on the different components that make up organisation variables to determine the extent and the overall effect across the group. Before determining the overall effect of the individual variables, it is pertinent to note that a number of factors could have affected the results in this group. For example, preliminary analysis shows that only one respondent answered the management section of the questionnaire. The research concluded that one response is not a good enough number to make any inference from the data (see section 6.3.1). Thus, it could be argued that such will have effect on the mean scores across the variables of organisation.

Organisation is made up of technology readiness, top management support, institution size and cost variables. However, top management support was excluded from the analysis due to lack of data as stated earlier. In order to analyse whether cost has an effect on the institutions' intention to adopt cloud computing, further analysis was carried out with technology readiness and institution size to ascertain if relationship exists with adoption. Table 41 shows that removal of cost still indicates an insignificant result with adoption of cloud computing thus cost does not affect the outcome.

Table 41: Test statistics of organisation without cost variable

Test statistics
Chi-square = 1.241; df = 3 and p = .743

Table 42 of mean of adoption shows that with the exception of technology readiness, there is no pattern or consistency in the mean rank. While cost showed increase from 36.95 to 38.03 between agree and strongly agree group, the same cannot be said of institution size. Since technology readiness has a relationship with adoption of cloud computing, it suggests that those institutions that are technologically ready will adopt cloud computing.

Table 42: Levels of organisation and mean of adoption

Levels	Mean of adoption for		
	Tech. readiness	Size	Cost
Strongly disagree	34.14	36.50	
Disagree	36.88	24.76	52.25
Agree		29.38	36.95
Strongly agree	40.00	28.17	38.03

6.8.3 Environment and Adoption of Cloud Computing

The relationship between environment and adoption of cloud computing was hypothesized (see appendix 1).

As with the preceding section, Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to test the relationship between environment and adoption of cloud computing. The output generated is shown in table 43 below. The observed Chi-square is 2.603 with df of 3; $p = .05$ and the critical value of 7.81. It indicates no significant relationship between environment and adoption of cloud computing since the observed value is less than the critical value.

Table 43: Environment and mean of adoption

Environment	Mean rank of adoption
Strongly disagree	17.83
Disagree	35.03
Agree	32.55
Strongly agree	37.75
Chi-square= 2.603; df=3 and p=.457	

Further, there is no consistency or a clear pattern in the mean rank across all variable components making up the environment construct. The output shows an increase from 17.83 to 35.03 between strongly disagree and the disagree group. There is a slight decrease to 32.55 in the agree group before increasing again to 37.75 in the strongly agree group. These inconsistencies and lack of relationship means that the hypotheses H, H_{3a} and H_{3b} do not hold, thus, they are rejected. Despite the lack of relationship, further analysis will be carried out on the individual variables making up environment to ascertain if they have any kind of relationship and their overall effect

Table 44: Levels of Environment and mean of adoption

Levels	Mean of adoption for	
	Competitive Pressure	Trading Partner Pressure
Strongly disagree	2.50	19.70
Disagree	28.50	20.55
Agree	24.37	20.88
Strongly agree	23.83	19.83

Table 44 above shows increase in the mean rank of adoption against each component of environment from strongly disagree to disagree. While competitive pressure shows consistency in decrease in the mean, such cannot be said of trading partner pressure. For example trading partner pressure showed an infinitesimal increase from 20.55 in the disagree group to 20.88 in the agree group before decreasing to 19.83 in the strongly agree group. These inconsistencies are reflected in the environment construct, thus, indicating no clear relationship with adoption in this study.

6.8.4 Diffusion of Innovation and Adoption of Cloud Computing

The relationship between DOI and adoption of cloud computing was hypothesized (see appendix 1).

Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to test the relationship between DOI and adoption of cloud computing. The output generated is shown in table 45 below. The observed Chi-square is 2.609 with df of 2; $p = .05$ and critical value of 5.99. It indicates no significant relationship between DOI and adoption of cloud computing since the observed value is less than the critical value. The table shows a consistent increase in the mean rank across the groups. Disagree group has a mean of 37.85 which increased to 45.94 in the agree group and 48.04 in the strongly agree group.

Table 45: DOI and mean of adoption

DOI	Mean rank of adoption
Disagree	37.85
Agree	45.94
Strongly agree	48.04
Chi-square= 2.609; df=2 and p=.271	

Table 45 above indicates that the mean rank increases across the group. However, further analysis is needed to ascertain the extent of such relationships and their overall effect with adoption. Table 47 below shows that while trialability increased from 40.55 to 44.44 between agree and strongly agree the same cannot be said of observability. For example, observability decreased from 34.50 to 20.90 between the strongly disagree and disagree groups before further increasing from 29.83 to 33.44 between agree and strongly agree groups respectively. Therefore, analysis of the individual variables indicates that hypothesis H_{4a} has a positive relationship while H_{4b} showed no clear relationship. The overall effect is that hypothesis H has a positive relationship thus, it holds.

Table 46: Levels of DOI and mean of adoption

Levels	Mean of adoption for	
	Trialability	Observability
Strongly disagree		34.50
Disagree		20.90
Agree	40.55	29.83
Strongly agree	44.44	33.44

6.8.5 Computer Self-Efficacy and Adoption of Cloud Computing

The relationship between CSE and adoption of cloud computing was hypothesized (see appendix 1).

Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to test the relationship between CSE and adoption of cloud computing. The output generated is shown in table 47 below. The observed Chi-square is 2.806 with df of 3; $p = .05$ and critical value of 7.81. It indicates no significant relationship between CSE and adoption of cloud computing since the observed value is less than the critical value. However, it shows a consistent increase in the mean rank across the groups. Strongly disagree group has a mean of 15.50 which increases to 30.75 in disagree group and from 39.40 to 45.20 in agree and strongly agree groups respectively.

Table 47: CSE and mean of adoption

CSE	Mean rank of adoption
Strongly disagree	15.50
Disagree	30.75
Agree	39.10
Strongly agree	45.20
Chi-square= 2.806; df=3 and p=.422	

Further analysis was performed on the individual variables to determine if they have relationships and to what extent. Table 48 below indicates consistencies and increase in the mean rank across the variables. However, having the necessary skills to use cloud technology and the confidence to use any form of cloud technology showed a positive relationship with adoption of cloud computing thus, the hypothesis was accepted.

Table 48: Level of CSE and mean of adoption

Levels	Mean of adoption for	
	Having necessary skills to use cloud	Having confidence to use any form of cloud
Strongly disagree		13.00
Disagree	28.50	24.33
Agree	37.04	33.05
Strongly agree	41.96	40.88

6.8.6 Adoption of Cloud Computing

To determine the actual cloud computing usage, the following two questionnaire items were used by calculating the frequencies.

- i. Which of the following cloud services do you use (please select all that apply)?
 - a. Software as a service (SaaS)
 - b. Platform as a service (PaaS)
 - c. Infrastructure as a service (IaaS)
 - d. Others (please specify)

- ii. Which of the following best describes your use of cloud based services (please select all that apply).
 - a. Email
 - b. Video streaming/conferencing
 - c. Data management (backup, archiving, replication, storage, etc.)
 - d. Managed networks
 - e. Presentation
 - f. Information security systems
 - g. Enterprise resource management
 - h. Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc.)
 - i. Human resource systems
 - j. Telephony
 - k. Others (please specify)

Table 49: Frequency of use of cloud service models

Cloud Service Models	Frequency of Use
SaaS	61
IaaS	27
PaaS	26
Don't know	11
None/never used	5
Other (RGUcloud, Hybrid)	2

Table 49 above shows SaaS is the most frequently used cloud service model at 68.5%. IaaS and PaaS comprised of 30.4% and 29.2% of the respondents respectively. Only about 0.2% used other types, about 12% and 5% of the respondents do not know or said they have never used cloud.

Table 50: Frequency of use of cloud based services

Cloud based Services	Frequency of Use
Email	74
Video streaming/conferencing	44
Data management (backup, archiving, replication, storage, etc.)	62
Managed networks	12
Presentation	22
Information security systems	8
Enterprise resource management	8
Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc.)	59
Human resource systems	9
Telephony	18
Others (please specify)	18
None/don't know	3

Table 50 above indicates that email 83.2%, data management (backup, archiving, replication, storage, etc.) 69.7% and Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc.) 66.3% are the most frequently used cloud based services by the respondents. However, 20.3% of the respondents uses cloud based services for other activities other than those specified while about 3.4% never used or do not know. The rest of use cuts across the activities listed in the table above.

While significant number of respondents have used cloud based services with different cloud service models (table 49 and 50), they also provided reasons for the low adoption of cloud computing and how it could be improved; details of which can be found in chapter 7.

6.8.7 Summary of Results

From the table (51) below, the observed value is the actual value of the scores obtained. The critical value is the point of the distribution that is compared to the test statistics to determine if the null hypotheses will be rejected, while the p. value is the probability of finding the observed or more extreme result when the null hypotheses is true. The significance level is the probability of rejecting the null hypotheses in a statistical test when it is true.

Table 51: summary of the result

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Observed value</i>	<i>Critical value</i>	<i>Observed > critical?</i>	<i>Significance level</i>	<i>P. value</i>	<i>Significance < P. value?</i>	<i>Outcome</i>
Technology	8.444	7.815 at df 3	Yes	0.038	0.05	Yes	Significant
Organisation	1.44	7.815 at df 3	No	0.686	0.05	No	Insignificant
Environment	2.603	7.815 at df 3	No	0.457	0.05	No	Insignificant
DOI	2.609	5.99 at df 2	No	0.271	0.05	No	Insignificant
CSE	2.806	7.815 at df 3	No	0.422	0.05	No	Insignificant

From the table above, significant result is obtained when the observed value is greater than the critical value and the significance value is less than the p. value. The result obtained indicates that only technology factors were significant while organisation, environment, DOI and CSE factors were found to be insignificant.

6.8.8 Summary of Hypotheses

Table (52) below summarises the hypotheses at high level. Overall, the relationship between technology and adoption of cloud computing was positive and significant and therefore the associated hypothesis (H_1) was upheld. A critical look at all the variables of technology (see table 53) indicates that H_{1a} , H_{1b} , H_{1c} , H_{1d} , H_{1e} and H_{1f} also have positive relationships. However, H_{1d} has a negative relationship thus, confirming the earlier hypothesis.

In organisation, hypothesis H_2 showed no clear relationship with adoption of cloud computing thus, it was rejected. However, H_{2a} is accepted as technology readiness was found to have a positive relationship with adoption of cloud computing. Hypotheses H_{2c} and H_{2d} showed no clear relationship (see table 53), H_{2b} was not considered because there was no sufficient data as stated earlier in section 6.8.2.

In the environment construct, hypotheses H_3 , H_{3a} and H_{3b} were all rejected as they showed no clear relationships with adoption of cloud computing (see section 6.8.3 and table 53). Analyses of component (competitive pressure and trading technical partner pressure) variables also proved inconclusive thus, indicating no clear relationship.

In the DOI, hypotheses H₄, H_{4a} were accepted as they showed clear relationships judging by the mean rank values obtained (section 6.8.4, table 45). However, hypothesis H_{4b} showed no clear relationship with adoption of cloud computing. Table 46 also indicates that the values obtained for the variables increased steadily with the exception of the strongly disagree group. However, the overall effect was a positive relationship with adoption thus, the hypotheses were accepted.

A positive relationship was obtained for hypothesis H₅ (section 6.8.5). Further analysis also showed that for individual items, positive relationships were obtained as the values for the mean rank in table 47 showed.

The table 52 below summarises the hypotheses, outcomes and relationships of the constructs with adoption of cloud computing at high level. It shows that technology, DOI and CSE all have positive relationships thus, and hypotheses that proposed a significant relationship between them were accepted. Organisation and environment showed no clear relationships thus, they were rejected.

Table 52: High level summary of hypotheses

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Hypotheses</i>	<i>Outcome</i>	<i>Relationship</i>
Technology	H ₁	Accepted	Positive
Organisation	H ₂	Rejected	No clear relationship
Environment	H ₃	Rejected	No clear relationship
DOI	H ₄	Accepted	Positive
CSE	H ₅	Accepted	Positive

Table 53 below shows a detailed summary of all the hypotheses. It indicates that all the variables of the technology construct have positive relationships with adoption. Relationship (positive and negative) in the table shows how different variables and factors relate to adoption. In organisation, technology readiness showed positive relationship with institution size and cost showing no clear relationships. The environment constructs indicate no clear relationships at all. In DOI, trialability variable indicates a positive relationship with observability having no clear relationship. CSE on the other hand, indicates a positive relationship with adoption of cloud computing.

Table 53: Detailed summary of hypotheses and outcomes

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Variables</i>	<i>Hypotheses</i>	<i>Outcome</i>	<i>Significance</i>	<i>Relationship</i>
Technology		H ₁	Accepted	<i>Significant</i>	Positive
	Perceived ease of use	H _{1a}	Accepted	Significant	Positive
	Perceived usefulness	H _{1b}	Accepted	Significant	Positive
	Relative advantage	H _{1c}	Accepted	Significant	Positive
	Complexity	H _{1d}	Accepted	Significant	Negative
	Compatibility	H _{1e}	Accepted	Significant	Positive
	Security	H _{1f}	Accepted	Significant	Positive
Organisation		H ₂	Rejected	<i>Insignificant</i>	No clear relationship
	Tech. readiness	H _{2a}	Accepted	Significant	Positive
	Mgt. support	H _{2b}	*	*	*
	Size	H _{2c}	Rejected	Insignificant	No clear relationship
	Cost	H _{2d}	Rejected	Insignificant	No clear relationship
Environment		H ₃	Rejected	<i>Insignificant</i>	No clear relationship
	Comp. pressure	H _{3a}	Rejected	Insignificant	No clear relationship
	Trading partner pressure	H _{3b}	Rejected	Insignificant	No clear relationship
DOI		H ₄	Accepted	<i>Insignificant</i>	Positive
	Trialability	H _{4a}	Accepted	Insignificant	Positive
	Observability	H _{4b}	Rejected	Insignificant	No clear relationship
CSE		H ₅	Accepted	<i>Insignificant</i>	Positive

*: available data is not enough to make inference.

In this chapter, the demographic characteristics of the study were analysed and presented. The credibility of the research was also discussed. Parametric test was conducted to ascertain if assumptions would be met. Having not met parametric assumptions, non-parametric tests

were conducted to ascertain the relationships with adoption. However, the inconclusive nature of some results warranted further analysis by grouping data in each of the constructs into four levels: strongly disagree, disagree, agree and strongly agree. Finally, hypotheses were tested and the means of adoption examined with summary presented in tables 52 and 53.

CHAPTER 7- DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the research findings as they relate to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE more detail. Data was collected from 15 universities across Scotland but not all the data were usable. Following this section is the detailed discussion of the results of these four models and theories in an attempt to answer the research questions with the help of a revised and a valid research model. Furthermore, factors that inhibited or accelerated the adoption of cloud computing by institutions are also discussed.

7.1 Findings:

7.1.1 Technological Factors of Adoption of Cloud Computing

Result indicates that overall technology hypotheses H_1 was accepted (see table 53). Data analysis also shows that technology dimensions (individual or organisational) are vitally important in technology adoption and in the context of this study showed significant results and relationships with adoption of cloud computing (see section 6.8.1). It implies that institutions understand the important roles that individual factors play and how they contribute in helping them to make adoption decisions.

Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness

In table 53 above, hypotheses H_{1a} and H_{1b} were accepted and found to have significant positive relationship with adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in higher education. This finding is also consistent with prior research on technology adoption (Sabi et al, 2016; Behrend et al, 2011; Lee et al, 2010; Oliveira and Martins, 2010). This implies that institutions found cloud computing both easy to use and useful as it enhances their teaching and day to day management of the internal and external activities.

Relative Advantage

Table 53 above indicates that hypotheses H_{1c} was accepted and found to have significant positive relationship with adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. This is also consistent with previous research findings (Sabi et al, 2016, Senyo et al, 2016; Safari et al, 2014; Alshamaila et al, 2012; Huag et al, 2008; Ramdani et al, 2009; Carnaghan and Klassen, 2007; Scupola, 2009). It therefore implies that institutions understand the advantages that cloud computing offers. These could be in terms of better management of institution's data, scalability, collaboration opportunities etc.

Complexity

Table 53 indicates that hypotheses H_{1d} was accepted. However, it was found to have significant negative relationship thus, inconsistent with prior research findings (Wang et al, 2010; Oliveira and Martins, 2010). It may suggest that prior research was conducted with a more technically oriented manufacturing and e-business with better understanding of new technological complexities than higher institutions with less technical understanding thus, the inconsistencies. On the other the finding is consistent with previous research work of Low et al, (2011) indicating that high tech industries sees complex technologies as a barrier to adoption.

Compatibility

Table 53 shows that hypotheses H_{1e} was accepted and was found to have a significant positive relationship with adoption. It is also consistent with prior research findings (Wang et al, 2010; Huang et al, 2008; Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Lin and Chen, 2012; Safari et al, 2014; Sabi et al, 2016). One of the possible explanations or implications could be that when institutions have changed technology platforms in the past e.g. Blackboard, Moodle etc, they have been compatible with institutions' ICT infrastructures. Thus, cloud computing could be compatible too when adopted. Therefore, compatibility of cloud computing with institution's existing infrastructures would aid adoption by institutions.

Security

Table 53 shows that hypotheses H_{1f} was accepted was found to be significant with adoption of cloud computing. This finding is consistent line with prior research (Shin, 2010; Safari et al, 2014; Senyo et al, 2016). It implies that the perception that if data held or transferred through technology is secure, then individuals or institutions would tend to adopt that technology.

7.1.2 Organisational Factors of Adoption of Cloud Computing

Result of the analysis (table 53) indicates that overall organisation hypotheses H_2 was rejected and it showed no clear relationship with adoption from the surveyed institutions. It is pertinent to note that this is in the context of this research. It does not imply that institutions do not value organisational support. Hypothesis H_{2b} was excluded from the analysis due to inadequate availability of data (see sections 6.3.1 and 6.8.2). It therefore means that the

combined effects of rejected individual hypotheses may have caused the rejection of the organisational factors.

Technology Readiness

The result of the analysis indicates that technology readiness H_{2a} was accepted (table 53 and is significant with adoption of cloud. The findings are also consistent with previous research findings (Senyo et al, 2016; Gutierrez et al, 2015; Lian et al, 2014; Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Zhu et al, 2006; Pan and Jang, 2008). This is an indication that institutions acknowledge and understand the importance of technology capabilities in cloud computing adoption.

Size

Hypothesis H_{2c} (table 53) was rejected and found to be insignificant with no clear relationship with adoption. The findings was found to be consistent with some previous findings (Hsu et al, 2014; Low et al, 2011; Wang et al, 2010; Ramdani et al, 2009; Pan and Jang, 2008).

The implication is that institutions could adopt any technology they wish to adopt if other factors are considered rather than base adoption decision of the staff or student number.

Cost

Hypothesis H_{2d} (table 53) was rejected and found to be insignificant with no clear relationship with adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. The result was found to be inconsistent with the findings of Lian et al (2014). One probable reason was that Lian et al (2014) findings were based on hospitals where they deal with different kinds of data that may require different investment and cost outlay in systems adoption, implementation and integration from those in higher institutions. It could also mean that institutions with less students and staff have limited budgets and therefore are unlikely to adopt cloud computing. It therefore suggests that cost is not considered a major issue in adoption. Scottish universities may have multiple sources of funding thus, are able to fund adoption of latest technologies for their institutions.

Management support

Previous research indicates that management support is significant in any technology adoption at organisational level (Low et al, 2011; Huang et al, 2008; Ramdani, 2009; Carnaghan and Klassen, 2007; Scupola, 2009).

In this research, management variable was not analysed as discussed earlier (see section 6.3.1, 6.8.2). This is because only one usable response was obtained thus, not a high enough number to make any inference. Thus, it may have resulted in the inconsistencies with the organisational dimensions. However, error in research design, unreliability of scores, invalid constructs and unclear questionnaire could also affect results thus lead to rejection of hypotheses. Reliability could be affected by a number of factors as discussed in (section 6.4.1). However, proper procedures were followed in conducting this research thus reliability and validity were found to be acceptable. Further, pilot testing was conducted with a group similar to the actual respondents; with all the feedback taken on board (section 5.4). Thus, the research is also confident that pilot testing was conducted with actual representative samples therefore hypotheses H_2 , H_{2c} and H_{2d} were validated. Hypothesis H_{2d} could not be validated due to lack of data from the top management

It could therefore be argued that overall effect of no clear relationship between size and adoption as well as cost and adoption contributed to the rejection of the organisational hypotheses.

7.1.3 Environmental Factors of Adoption of Cloud Computing

In the context of this research, result of the analysis (table 53) indicates that overall environment hypothesis H_3 was rejected. It also showed insignificant result with no clear relationship between the environmental factors and adoption of cloud computing with the surveyed institutions. The findings are inconsistent with previous research findings (Low et al, 2011; Scupola, 2009, Lin and Lin; 2008).

Competitive Pressure and Trading Partner Pressure

Examinations of the constituent variables indicate that both hypotheses H_{3a} and H_{3b} were rejected (see table 53). The results were also insignificant and showed no clear relationship with adoption. These findings are inconsistent with previous research findings (Senyo et al, 2016; Low et al, 2011; Scupola, 2009, Lin and Lin; 2008). The only possible explanation to the inconsistencies appears to be that the study by Scupola (2009) involved small business enterprises (SMEs) while those of Low et al (2011) involved high technology industries and Senyo et al (2012) involved a variety of industries.

However, it could be argued that HEIs will not be classed as high technology industry and the findings may not be generalised. Though every industry faces competition, the levels of competition faced by HEIs are not comparable to those high technology industries.

In the context of this research, the result suggest that institutions may adopt technology if they wish to but not compelled to do so by partners or due to competition by other institutions thus, the rejection of the hypotheses. Therefore institutions may still not adopt new technology irrespective of environmental pressures, in this case, other institutions and technical partners.

7.1.4 Diffusion of Innovation Factors of Adoption of Cloud Computing

Table 53 above indicates that hypothesis H_4 was accepted. It also showed that DOI has positive relationship with adoption but with insignificant result

Trialability and Observability

Examinations of the constituent variables indicate that hypothesis H_{4a} (trialability) was accepted (table 53). It also indicates that trialability has a positive relationship with adoption but with insignificant result. The finding hereof is consistent with the findings of Lin and Chen (2012) even though their study was interview based.

Observability on the other hand indicates that H_{4b} was rejected (table 53). It also indicates insignificant result with no clear relationship with adoption. The findings of this research are consistent with those of Ramdani et al (2009). It may be argued that since cloud computing is not a physical item or object for instance mobile devices or tablets, it may be difficult to observe such technology.

The implication however, is that institutions are more likely to adopt technology that they have tried and may reject any technology that cannot be physically observed considering that is not a physical item. Thus, hypothesis H_{4a} was accepted and H_{4b} was rejected.

7.1.5 Computer Self-Efficacy Factors of Adoption of Cloud Computing

Table 53 above indicates that hypothesis H_5 was accepted. It also indicates positive relationship with adoption but with insignificant result. The findings are inconsistent with the studies by Shiau and Chau (2016) and Tarhini et al (2017). The inconsistency may be explained by the fact that this study dealt with experienced demographic population with a better understanding of the concept of cloud computing than data from college students that use cloud to facilitate study who may feel the CSE is not important.

Tarhini et al (2017) conducted their studies with data from hotels. It may be argued that hotels' IT systems are managed by third party vendors with better understanding of cloud computing than those surveyed thus, the inconsistencies.

The implication is that if institutions decide to adopt cloud, they have confidence that their staff have the skill set and ability to use any form of cloud computing to improve their institution’s e-learning systems.

In summary,

- Technology construct was found to be positively and significantly related to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. Complexity however showed negative but significant relationship.
- Organisation was found to be insignificant, however, technology readiness showed positive relationship.
- Environment showed no clear relationship.
- DOI showed insignificant but positive relationship. Observability however, showed negative relationship.
- CSE showed insignificant but positive relationship with adoption of cloud computing for e-learning.

In conclusion, lack of technical skills and support affects technology adoption (section 1.2). Various research findings (sections 2.4 and 2.8; tables 5 and 9) also underline the importance of technical support and technological factors in technology adoption. However, in the context of this research, results and findings indicate that technological factors of adoption are significant in adoption of cloud computing. Therefore, the surveyed HEIs also understands the importance that technological factors, capabilities, skills, and support in adoption thus, the significant results. These significant technological factors were then combined to develop the research model for cloud computing adoption for e-learning.

Table 54: Summary of Results in Relation to Other Research

Factors	Previous Findings	References
PU and PEOU	Consistent	Behrend et al (2011)
	Inconsistent	Sabi et al (2016); Oliveira and Martins (2010),
Relative advantage	Consistent	Sabi et al (2016); Ramdani et al (2009); Safari et al (2014); Alshamaila et al (2012); Senyo et al (2016).
	Inconsistent	Lin and Chen (2012)
Complexity	Consistent	Low et al (2011); Gutierrez et al (2015).

	Inconsistent	Wang et al (2010); Oliveira and Martins (2010)
Compatibility	Consistent	Wang et al (2010); Oliveira and Martins (2010); Safari et al (2014); Alshamaila et al (2012); Gutierrez et al (2015); Lin and Chen (2012).
	Inconsistent	Senyo et al (2016).
Security	Consistent	Shin (2010); Safari et al (2014); Senyo et al (2016).
Technology readiness	Consistent	Oliveira and Martins (2010); Zhu et al (2006); Pan and Jang (2008); Senyo et al (2016); Lian et al (2014); Gutierrez et al (2015).
**Mgt. Support	N/A	N/A
Size	Consistent	Senyo et al (2016).
	Inconsistent	Hsu et al (2014); Low et al (2011); Wang et al (2010); Ramdani et al (2009); Pan and Jang (2008)
Cost	Inconsistent	Lian et al (2014)
Competitive pressure	Consistent	Senyo et al (2016).
	Inconsistent	Low et al (2011); Scupola (2009), Lin and Lin 2008); Alshamaila et al (2012); Lin and Chen (2012).
Trading partner pressure	Consistent	Senyo et al (2016); Gutierrez et al (2015).
	Inconsistent	Low et al (2011); Scupola (2009), Lin and Lin 2008).
Trialability	Consistent	Lin and Chen (2012); Safari et al (2014); Alshamaila et al (2012).
Observability	Consistent	Ramdani et al (2009); Safari et al (2014).
CSE	Inconsistent	Shiau and Chau (2016) and Tarhini et al (2017); Lin and Chen (2012);

7.2 Factors Influencing Adoption of Cloud Computing for E-learning

Organisational adoption process is influenced by a variety of factors. The complex nature of technologies has also made researchers to have different perspectives on the degree of adoption and use (Salleh et al 2012). Factors influencing adoption of cloud computing are classified into technological organisational and environmental context (Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990). Furthermore, they have also been classified as either accelerants or inhibitors (Ernst and Young, 2010). Accelerants are those factors that may aid adoption while inhibitors are the factors that may hinder adoption. However, what influences organisational

and environmental factors of cloud adoption vary from industry to industry (Low et al 2011). Following this paragraph is the detailed discussion on identified factor that influences adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

Security as a factor of adoption has been extensively researched and this has been discussed (sections 2.9 and 4.2.2). There are arguments and counter arguments as to whether security inhibits or accelerates adoption. For instance, on the one hand security is expected drive adoption within the next few years as more resources are expected to be devoted in that area than typical IT departments facing cuts (Ernst and Young, 2010). With centralised data storage, monitoring data access, virtualisation and logging, organisations are able to effectively manage resources to secure their data (Alecu 2010). Furthermore, virtualisation could enhance security through the creation of sandboxes for running applications with uncertain reliability. Thus, security issues intrinsic to the sharing of resources among multiple computing locations are minimised (Assuncao et al 2009).

As one respondent noted:

“While security is a significant issue, cloud suppliers often have much better security, backup and disaster recovery in place that may be affordable on site”.

On the other hand, issues associated with third party vendors could inhibit adoption as there maybe concerns arising from shared IT infrastructure and the associated risks (Ernst and Young, 2010). Data availability, confidentiality, integrity and privacy have been identified as some of the major security issues that could inhibit adoption (Onwubiko, 2010; Sun et al, 2011; Salleh et al, 2012; Oguande and Mehnen, 2013).

As one of the respondents put it:

“According to what I've read, cloud computing poses privacy concerns because the service provider can access the data that is on the cloud at any time. It could accidentally or deliberately alter or even delete information”.

Another remarked that:

“I'm involved in a research project where we are simply not allowed to place any project related files on standard cloud services because they may end up on servers in (for example) the USA, where the information could be subject to different laws. Instead we've had to set up a local own cloud server to share and a sync files between project members”

Cost has previously been discussed (sections 2.9 and 4.2.2). However, research findings suggest that cost is one of the major accelerants of cloud adoption (Berman et al 2012; Salleh et al, 2012; Onwubiko, 2010; Li et al 2009). Cloud adoption will drive down cost thus, saving organisations between 20%-50% of their IT cost (Ernst and Young, 2010). The expected cost savings has been linked to the flexible pricing model (Berman et al 2012). Li et al (2009) argue that cloud benefits must outweigh the cost while achieving maximum efficiency with minimal cost. They posit two main cost considerations for cloud computing: Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) and Utilisation Cost. TCO is commonly used as a means of addressing the real costs ascribed to owning and managing an IT infrastructure in a business. TCO is not limited to but including capital cost and the cost of operating the IT infrastructures thus, making it appropriate for estimating the financial value of cloud investment. Utilisation Cost on the other hand is the real cost associated with individual user of an application. Despite the cost advantages associated with cloud adoption, organisations must be ready to deal with risks and challenges associated with any externally provided services (Heiser and Nicolette, 2008).

In addition, the dynamic nature of business environment makes it essential to align business processes to meet organisational demands. Thus, organisations are continuously seeking ways to improve and meet the changing market needs. The method of cloud provisioning seems attractive to both developers and other end-users. It allows for self-deployment of computing resources like servers, networks, storage and various application infrastructures thereby limiting the complexities while being able to monitor and manage dynamic infrastructure and platform requirements (Rimal et al, 2010; Kizza, 2013).

7.3 Valid Research Model

In validating the research model a number of changes have been made. Overall, technological factors, DOI and CSE have been found to have positive relationships with adoption. However, organisation and environment have no relationships with adoption in the context of this research (section 6.8.8, table 53).

The research conceptual model indicates that technological factors have a significant positive relationship with adoption of cloud computing as represented in hypotheses H₁ (chapter 4, figure 10), H_{1a}, H_{1b}, H_{1c}, H_{1d}, H_{1e} and H_{1f} (section 6.8.8, table 53). Data analysis showed positive relationship between technology and adoption of cloud computing. It therefore suggests that increase or decrease in technological factors consequently affects adoption.

DOI factors showed positive relationships with adoption and are represented as hypothesis H₄ in the research model. It therefore suggests that increase or decrease in DOI factors consequently affects adoption resulting in similar changes.

CSE factors showed positive relationships with adoption and are represented as hypothesis H₅ in the research model. It therefore suggests that increase or decrease in CSE factors will also result in similar changes in adoption.

Changes have been effected in the process of validating the research model. Positive relationships are represented by (+) sign and negative relationships are represented by a (-) sign. The significant changes in the model have resulted in the exclusion of organisation and environment factors hypotheses, H₂ and H₃, as they showed no relationship with adoption. Data analysis also shows there is no relationship between organisation and adoption as well as environment and adoption. A critical examination of organisational factors (section 6.8.2) shows that technology readiness has a positive relationship with adoption. However, the overall effect is no relationship. It therefore means that results obtained do not support organisational and environmental hypotheses H₂ and H₃ respectively.

Figure 22: Research model with significant and insignificant results

Figure 23: Decomposed research model

Figure 24: Valid research model

In conclusion, this chapter discussed the relationships between the various constructs and adoption of cloud computing. Furthermore, it discussed the factors affecting adoption of

cloud computing as elicited from respondents' comments as well as other factors; and they are classified using TOE framework. Finally, prior findings were confirmed and a valid research model was produced.

CHAPTER 8- CONCLUSIONS

This chapter presents contribution to knowledge of this research, opportunities and challenges, the implications for higher institutions, limitations of the study and identified areas for further research.

8.1 Contributions to Knowledge

Modern day business organisations depend on IT for the day-to-day running of their business operations, as it helps them improve efficiencies and gain competitive advantage. Consequently, the current economic landscape is making it even more difficult for businesses to survive. This research therefore contributes distinctively in a variety of ways to cloud computing particularly for e-learning in HE.

- It produced a novel robust hybrid secure model for adoption of cloud computing for e-learning. This was achieved by extending TOE framework by including PU, PEOU and security factors. This is because:
 - i. The predictive powers of both models are limited (Gangwar et al, 2014).
 - ii. External variables of TAM are not well defined.
 - iii. PU and PEOU only explain about 40% of system use (Legris et al, 2003).
 - iv. TAM focuses more on perception with less emphasis on social processes of IS development and implementation.

Although TOE is not well integrated, however, it captures the internal and external variables. Thus, integrating TAM with TOE helps to overcome the limitations of both models. Therefore,

- This model provides opportunity to investigate further variables at organisational levels (technological impacts, size, security, trust, technology readiness, response to market changes etc.) that impacts the value chain in the institutional process. For instance:
 - a) Scalability, metered service and on-demand service helps to save cost.
 - b) The rapid elasticity and instantaneous demand of cloud computing leads to efficiency and saves time in processing information and data.
 - c) For security, managing and processing of institutional data in a safe and secure way also improves the value chain of the institutional process.
- Another important contribution to knowledge is in the models and theories used in the research.

Literatures review shows that most researchers mainly use TAM for individual technology adoption as it deal with adoption at individual level. TOE framework on the other hand is used for organisational adoption as it deals with adoption at organisational level.

- Thus, this research studied factors that affect cloud computing adoption both from individual and organisational perspectives by combining the models and exploring further. This is because organisations are made up of individuals. However, it is individuals that make various recommendations (including technology) to management of organisations because they have, in most cases used such technologies privately.

Since IT is being delivered as a service, it is imperative to develop new models for adopting innovative IT services driven by sound economics and high speed digital networks.

- Overall, this research has combined the strength of the two models to produce a novel hybrid secure model of cloud adoption. Therefore, the development of this model is the major contribution to knowledge of this research, acting as a platform for future research in adoption of innovative educational IT services.

8.2 Opportunities and Challenges

Cloud computing provide opportunities for the HEIs to manage their daily activities more efficiently. Some of the major significant opportunities available to cloud users including the HIEs have been discussed (see section 2.9). For instance, HEIs have the opportunity to use e-learning solutions on cloud provider's infrastructure, develop their own solution by using the provider's interface or use e-learning solution from the provider.

Conversely, there are many challenges and issues that cloud users must deal with before the full potentials of cloud computing could be properly harnessed. One of those issues is security in the cloud which has divided opinions among researchers. However, some HEIs have taken significant steps in overcoming this challenge (see section 5.6).

HEIs, like other industries face the challenge of lack of standards and regulation. Significant steps are being undertaken by to overcome this issue both at national and European level. For instance, the Cloud Security Alliance (CSA) was set up to provide security assurance for both the users and Cloud Service Providers (CSPs). European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA) was commissioned by European Parliament to harmonise privacy laws and

provide a benchmarking model for effective evaluation of cloud service offerings based on standard set of controls (Ernst and Young, 2010). Cloud Computing Interoperability Group and Multi-Agency Cloud Computing Forum have also been seeking ways to efficiently control and secure data in the cloud (Onwubiko, 2010).

8.3 Implications

This research has far reaching implications in practice for higher institutions' management and IT practitioners. With the increasing cost of higher education and less public funding, institutions are constantly seeking ways of reducing costs while improving delivery as well as competitiveness in the global market. Institutions' adoption of cloud computing is seen as a potential solution because it has the capability for end users to seamlessly access data and applications from multiple devices and platforms (Ewuzie and Usoro, 2017). The international higher education market is huge and competitive. Since institutions are realigning themselves with globalisation and internationalisation strategy, the findings of this research will be of particular interest to higher institution's management.

In addition to globalisation and internationalisation strategies, the findings will also help institutions in their technology adoption plans that will include security strategy. Security is part of a wider institution's IT strategy. Having identified security both as an inhibitor and an accelerant to adoption of cloud computing, it will enable institutions to assess and highlight the strong and weak points of their strategies, provide opportunities for improvement before the actual implementation. In essence, it will facilitate the assessment of institution's IT security strategy.

8.3.1 Implications for Higher Institution Management

- Adopted technology should be compatible with already existing infrastructure; that would reduce the down times during transition to a new technology and/or system.
- Institutions should adopt cloud computing because it will provide them with relative advantage over existing technologies (in terms of security, scalability and collaboration opportunities).
- Secure technology should be adopted; adopting a secure technology will help the institutions to avoid the consequences of failed or venerable technology/system which includes but not limited to cost and lack of trust from the users.
- Adopting cloud would also help institutions to tailor content to dynamically meet their needs and that of their students.

8.3.2 Implications for Research and Practitioners

For IT practitioners, the research provides an opportunity to evaluate failures or success of their technology adoption plans from the security aspect. Therefore:

- Technicians should evaluate their security procedure to see if it's strong enough. If the security procedure is not adequate, they should develop mechanisms that will help to avoid security failures.
- Security technicians should continuously liaise with managers, architects and developers to tweak and update security requirements even after implementation of such systems.
- Cloud technology that is developed or recommended by technicians to be acquired should be as less complex as possible.

8.3.3 Implications for Research

The implication for research is that it filled a gap in literature by combining four models as recommended by Low et al (2011). Furthermore, it extended technology context of TOE framework and still showed a significant positive relationship with adoption. Thus:

- This research has provided platform for future research by studying adoption from both individual and organisational perspectives.
- Researchers should replicate and test the model outside the boundaries of this research.
- Researchers should build on the model by extending and adapting it suite other environments.

8.4 Limitations

Research limitation describes a systematic bias outside the control or knowledge of the researcher which could affect the result (Price and Murnan, 2004).

- Research bias: the lack of response from a segment –management group - may have affected the results as this group was not part of the analysis and findings.
- The results presented did not categorise data based on cloud services (Paas, IaaS, SaaS and DaaS) and deployment models (private public and hybrid). Thus, future studies should develop models depending on the service and deployment models and their characteristics.

- Scottish Universities (represents developed economy, when applied to developing economy may not be applicable e.g. cost will be a factor but funding are available in developed economies)
- Quantitative survey was used for data collection which is in line with previous studies of this nature. However, of the 625 initial requests and 491 follow up requests for responses, 99 responses were collected (section 5.5, table 19). Out of the 99 responses, 89 were found to be usable and valid (sections 6.3 and 6.3.1). Eighty nine (89) represents a reasonably good number to make inferences. However, a higher number perhaps, could have supported the arguments more strongly. Sabi et al (2016) used only 20 in their research.

Irrespective of these limitations, the study was worthwhile because of the significant contributions it made to knowledge (section 8.1).

8.5 Areas for Future research

A number of areas of further research were identified in the course of this research. They include but not limited to:

- i. The model should be further empirically tested
- ii. This study was conducted from IT, teaching and management staff perspectives. Future studies therefore should consider it from students' perspectives; also, because whatever e-learning platforms that are adopted by any institutions will ultimately be used by the students. Furthermore, more data should be gathered from the management since the final decision to adopt or not to adopt any technology lies with them.
- iii. This study adopted quantitative methods. Future studies should consider a mixed method approach to ascertain if a different result could be obtained and how that affects cloud adoption.
- iv. This research has laid the foundation for future research by looking at cloud adoption from both individual and organisational perspectives. Researchers should build on the model by extending and adapting it outside the boundaries of this research
- v. Further investigation of variables with no clear relationship using other models (adjust the model to fit other environments)

- vi. Test the model in underdeveloped/developing economies to ascertain the effects of cost in adoption

In conclusion, this chapter discussed the major contributions to knowledge of the study - extending the TOE framework. The research studied adoption from both individual and organisational perspectives thus, provided holistic view of factors from both perspectives. It also combined the strength of both models to produce a hybrid model of adoption. Findings indicate that both perspectives are important in relation to this study and if well implemented, will help institutions in their long term e-learning and IT strategy.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1- Summary of identified hypotheses

H₁: There are significant positive relationships between technology and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{1a}: Perceived ease of use of cloud technology is positively related to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{1b}: Perceived usefulness of cloud technology will be positively related to the intention to adopt cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{1c}: There is a positive relationship between relative advantage and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{1d}: Complexity is negatively related to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{1e}: There is a positive relationship between compatibility and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{1f}: Security is significantly and positively related to adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H₂: There are significant positive relationships between organisation and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{2a}: There is a positive relationship between institutions' technology readiness and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{2b}: There is a positive relationship between top management support and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{2c}: Institution's size is significantly and positively related to institution's ability to adopt cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{2d}: There is a positive relationship between cost considerations and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H₃: There are significant relationships between environment and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{3a}: There is a positive relationship between competitive pressure and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{3b}: There is a positive relationship between trading partner pressure and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H₄: There is a positive relationship between diffusion of innovation and adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

H_{4a}: There is a positive relationship between trying out a technology and adoption of that technology. Therefore, trialability will be positively related to the previous use of that system.

H_{4b}: Observability and the pervasive nature of a technology are positively related to the adoption of that technology.

H₅: There is a positive relationship between individuals' belief in their capabilities to use technology and the adoption of cloud computing for e-learning in HE.

APPENDIX 2 – Sample of email responses to interview requests

The names and contact details of the respondents have been blurred to protect their confidentiality.

From: Isaiah Ewuzie
Sent: 14 January 2013 09:55
To: Xxxx Xxxxxx
Subject: Interview

Hi Xxxx,

Regarding a chat we had last Friday about interviewing you and some of your colleagues about my research, wondering if coming around 10.30-11.00 tomorrow morning suits?

Kind regards,

Isaiah.

Isaiah,

That's fine; if you come to the desk i will meet you there.

Regards

Xxxx Xxxxxx

XXXXXXXXXX XXXXXXXXXXXX XXXXXXX XXX XXXXXXX

University of the West of Scotland Paisley Campus PAISLEY PA1 2BE

T: xxxx xxx xxxx

From: Isaiah Ewuzie
Sent: 15 January 2013 12:10
To: Xxxxx Xxxxxx
Subject: Research Interview

Dear Xxxxx,

I am a PhD student researching on adoption and integration of e-learning and IT infrastructures with cloud computing within higher institutions.

I would like to have the opportunity to have a chat with you on the UWS technical development projects, cloud computing and the feasibility of adopting cloud by higher institutions.

My chat today with Xxxx Xxxxxx on the same subject was really helpful. And here is hoping you can be of help too. Please do let me know your availability.

Looking forward to hearing from you.

Kind Regards,
Isaiah.

Isaiah,

I am happy to meet with you for a discussion on the topics below.

This week is out for me but I am happy to meet anytime next week.

I believe you have also approached Xxxxxx Xxxxxxxx who works for me.

As we work in the same team I have agreed with Xxxxxx that I will meet with you to discuss from my angel.

There would probably be no great benefit in meeting us both.

Regards

Xxxxxx

From: Isaiah Ewuzie
Sent: 22 January 2013 12:30
To: Xxxxxx Xxxxxxxx
Subject: RE: Research Interview

Dear Xxxxxx,

Are you available on Thursday 24th January by 11am for the interview as discussed last week?

Kind regards,

Isaiah.

Isaiah,

That's fine by me. I'll get you at the ICT front desk at 11am.

Regards

Xxxxxx

From: Isaiah Ewuzie
Sent: 15 January 2013 12:29
To: Xxxxxx Xxxx
Subject: Research Interview

Dear Xxxxx,

I am a PhD student researching on adoption and integration of e-learning and IT infrastructures with cloud computing within higher institutions.

I would like to have the opportunity to have a chat with you on the UWS e-learning projects, cloud computing and the feasibility of adopting cloud by higher institutions.

My chat today with Xxxx Xxxxxx on the same subject was really helpful. And here is hoping you can be of help too. Please do let me know your availability.

Looking forward to hearing from you.

Kind Regards,
Isaiah.

From: Xxxxx Xxxx
Sent: 15 January 2013 12:47
To: Isaiah Ewuzie
Subject: RE: Research Interview

Hi Isaiah

Yes that's fine with me.

I'm available from 3pm today or tomorrow (apart from 11-12 midday). Then I'm available 28 Jan anytime, most of 29 Jan. I also have availability after this but didn't want to suggest too many days. When would be best for you?

Are any of these any good?

Kind Regards

From: Isaiah Ewuzie
Sent: 15 January 2013 13:08
To: Xxxxx Xxxx
Subject: RE: Research Interview

Hi Xxxxx,

Many thanks for your immediate response.

I will be in tomorrow before 10am.

Kind regards,

Isaiah.

APPENDIX 3 – Ethical approval

School of Engineering
and Computing
Paisley Campus
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland

Tel 0141 848 3101
Fax 0141 848 3404

To Whom It May Concern: Isaiah Ewuzie

This is to confirm that Isaiah Ewuzie is a PhD student of this School and he is undertaking field work on Adoption of Cloud Computing for E-Learning in Higher Education. His field work involves collection of information with questionnaires and interviews. The questions have been validated by the University Ethics Committee. Data collected will be handled in aggregates and confidentially.

I will therefore be grateful if you could assist him and if you have any queries do not hesitate to contact me.

Personal details withheld.

26 February 2015

APPENDIX 3 – Ethical approval continued

School of Engineering
and Computing
Paisley Campus
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland

Tel 0141 848 3101
Fax 0141 848 3404

21st October 2015

To Whom It May Concern

Isaiah Ewuzie

This is to confirm that Isaiah Ewuzie is a PhD Student of the School of Engineering and Computing and he is undertaking field work on Adoption of Cloud Computing for E-Learning in Higher Education. His field involves collection of information with questionnaires and interviews. The questions have been validated by the University Ethics Committee. Data collected will be handled in aggregates and confidentially.

I will therefore be grateful if you could assist him and if you have any queries do not hesitate to contact me.

Yours sincerely

Personal details withheld.

Professor Ian Allison, PhD PgCHE BSc CEng FBCS CIP MIEEE MACM
Dean of School

APPENDIX 4 – The survey

What is the name of your institution? (Please select one)

What is your gender?

Male

Female

What is your age bracket?

Less than 20

20-29

30-39

40-49

50-59

60 and above

What is your department? (Please specify)

What is your job title? (Please specify)

What is your highest level of qualification?

A level

OND

HND

BSc

PgD

MSc

Mphil

PhD

Other

What is your current job experience?

Less than 1 year

1-5 years

6-10 years

11-15 years

16-20 years

21-25 years

26 years and above

What is your total working experience?

Less than 1 year

- 1-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- 16-20 years
- 21-25 years
- 26 years and above

Which of the following cloud service models do you use?*

- Software as a service (SaaS)
- Platform as a service (PaaS)
- Infrastructure as a service (IaaS)
- Other (Please specify)

Which of the following best describes your use of cloud based services* (Select all that apply)

- Email
- Video Streaming/Conferencing
- Data Management (Backup, archiving, replication, storage etc)
- Managed Networks
- Presentation
- Information Security Systems
- Enterprise Resource Management
- Social Media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube etc)
- Human Resource Systems
- Telephony
- Other

GENERAL SECTION (G)

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
G1. It is easy to understand and familiarise oneself with our institution's cloud technology.					
G2. Becoming skilful at using cloud technology was easy.					
G3. Using cloud technology improves my job performance.					
G4. Using cloud technology gives me greater control over my work.					
G5. Using cloud technology enhances my job effectiveness.					

G6. My institution's adoption of cloud technology will enable me to access data quicker than usual.					
G7. My institution's adoption of cloud technology will enable us to have more flexibility in managing our data.					
G8. With cloud technology I have no concern with data security.					
G9. Cloud based services are reliable.					
G10. With cloud technology I can perform more functions as a user.					
G11. My institution's adoption of cloud technology will enable us to be competitive with other higher institutions.					
G12. The number of employees in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology.					
G13. The number of students in my institution may determine if my institution will adopt cloud technology.					
G14. The opportunity to observe and talk to those that have used cloud technology will help me to decide whether to adopt it or not.					
G15. I am confident that I have the necessary skills to use cloud technology.					
G16. I am confident of using any form of cloud technology even if I had never used it before.					
G16. I am confident of using any form of cloud technology even if I had never used it before.					
G17. Please can you list other factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud computing?					
G18. To what extent do you agree that the factors that you have listed in G17 above will influence adoption of cloud computing? Answer this question only if you have answered G17 otherwise proceed to the next question/section.					
<p>Respondent Suitability</p> <p>The purpose of this page is to determine the suitability of respondents. Therefore your response will determine the section of the survey you will be directed to.</p> <p>G19. Which of the following best describes your position in your institution?*</p>					

Management Staff

Technical Staff

Academic Staff (Computing/IT, Teaching/Research)

Other IT Staff

TECHNICAL SECTION (T)

T1. The use of cloud technologies is not as easy as I first thought.

T2. Technical challenges may hinder or prevent my institution from adopting cloud technologies.

T3. New technologies are more difficult to use than already existing technologies.

T4. Cloud technology is compatible with other software.

T5. Cloud technology is compatible with my institution's information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructures.

T6. My institution will adopt cloud technology if it is affordable and cost effective.

T7. My institution will consider the cost of adopting and implementing new innovation compared to the already existing ones before a decision to adopt that innovation can be made.

T8. My institution is likely to consider long term operational and maintenance cost savings from existing technologies before deciding to adopt a new technological innovation like cloud computing.

T9. My institution has the infrastructural capabilities to adopt and deploy cloud based services.

T10. It is important to properly try it out before deciding on whether or not to adopt.

T11. IT organisations such as Microsoft, Oracle, Cisco, CIW that accredit IT courses in institutions require us to adopt cloud computing.

T12. Please can you list other technical factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud

computing?

T13. To what extent do you agree that the factors that you have listed in T12 above will influence adoption of cloud computing? Answer this question only if you have answered T12 otherwise proceed to the next question/section.

MANAGEMENT SECTION (M)

M1. My institution will adopt cloud technology if it is affordable and cost effective.

--	--	--	--	--	--

M2. Cloud technology fits in with my institution's business strategy.

--	--	--	--	--	--

M3. Top management in my institution will support cloud technology adoption.

--	--	--	--	--	--

M4. My institution will consider the cost of adopting and implementing new innovation compared to the already existing ones before a decision to adopt that innovation can be made.

--	--	--	--	--	--

M5. My institution is likely to consider long term operational and maintenance cost savings from existing technologies before deciding to adopt a new technological innovation like cloud computing.

--	--	--	--	--	--

M6. IT organisations such as Microsoft, Oracle, Cisco, CIW that accredit IT courses in institutions require us to adopt cloud computing.

--	--	--	--	--	--

M7. Please can you list other management factors that you think may influence adoption of cloud computing.

M8. To what extent do you agree that the factors that you have listed in M7 above will influence adoption of cloud computing? Answer this question only if you have answered M7 otherwise proceed to end the survey.

APPENDIX 5 - Correlations matrix

		PEOU	PU	RA	CLXTY	COMPTY	SEC	TR	SIZE	COST	CPRSS	TPP	TBLTY	OBSV	CSE	ADPTN
PEOU	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.167	.318**	-.205	.189	.233*	.142	-.007	.239*	.032	.122	.010	-.100	.224*	.034
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.117	.002	.054	.076	.028	.190	.947	.024	.766	.258	.927	.361	.035	.755
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87
PU	Correlation Coefficient	.167	1.000	.617**	.000	.280**	.341**	.128	.061	.204	.358**	.048	-.060	.311**	-.024	.188
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.117	.	.000	.999	.008	.001	.237	.574	.056	.001	.660	.577	.004	.826	.081
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87
RA	Correlation Coefficient	.318**	.617**	1.000	-.120	.362**	.286**	.168	.162	.319**	.358**	.189	-.006	.221*	.066	.275**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.000	.	.264	.000	.007	.120	.133	.002	.001	.078	.959	.041	.540	.010
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87
CLXTY	Correlation Coefficient	-.205	.000	-.120	1.000	.101	-.146	-.089	-.037	.105	.142	-.034	.196	.180	-.490**	-.218*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.054	.999	.264	.	.344	.171	.411	.729	.326	.188	.750	.067	.097	.000	.042
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87
COMPTY	Correlation Coefficient	.189	.280**	.362**	.101	1.000	.195	.255*	.016	.231*	.374**	-.084	.037	.147	-.111	.039
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.076	.008	.000	.344	.	.067	.017	.880	.029	.000	.434	.732	.178	.302	.717
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87

SEC	Correlation Coefficient	.233 ⁺	.341 ^{**}	.286 ^{**}	-.146	.195	1.000	.038	-.007	.045	.176	.055	-.334 ^{**}	.196	.043	.004
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.028	.001	.007	.171	.067	.	.724	.946	.676	.101	.610	.001	.071	.691	.969
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87
TR	Correlation Coefficient	.142	.128	.168	-.089	.255 ⁺	.038	1.000	.156	.320 ^{**}	.134	.070	.143	-.006	.234 ⁺	.030
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.190	.237	.120	.411	.017	.724	.	.150	.002	.220	.517	.186	.959	.029	.783
	N	87	87	87	87	87	87	87	86	87	86	87	87	84	87	85
SIZE	Correlation Coefficient	-.007	.061	.162	-.037	.016	-.007	.156	1.000	.287 ^{**}	.239 ⁺	-.021	.048	.170	-.002	.042
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.947	.574	.133	.729	.880	.946	.150	.	.007	.026	.844	.660	.119	.983	.698
	N	88	88	88	88	88	88	86	88	88	87	87	87	85	88	86
COST	Correlation Coefficient	.239 ⁺	.204	.319 ^{**}	.105	.231 ⁺	.045	.320 ^{**}	.287 ^{**}	1.000	.263 ⁺	.120	.268 ⁺	.267 ⁺	.051	.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024	.056	.002	.326	.029	.676	.002	.007	.	.013	.267	.011	.013	.636	.500
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87
CMRSS	Correlation Coefficient	.032	.358 ^{**}	.358 ^{**}	.142	.374 ^{**}	.176	.134	.239 ⁺	.263 ⁺	1.000	-.044	-.013	.360 ^{**}	-.123	-.027
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.766	.001	.001	.188	.000	.101	.220	.026	.013	.	.685	.908	.001	.255	.805
	N	88	88	88	88	88	88	86	87	88	88	87	87	85	88	86
TPP	Correlation Coefficient	.122	.048	.189	-.034	-.084	.055	.070	-.021	.120	-.044	1.000	.037	-.059	.058	-.031

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.258	.660	.078	.750	.434	.610	.517	.844	.267	.685	.	.731	.595	.594	.776
	N	88	88	88	88	88	88	87	87	88	87	88	88	85	88	86
TBLTY	Correlation Coefficient	.010	-.060	-.006	.196	.037	-.334**	.143	.048	.268*	-.013	.037	1.000	-.007	.178	-.041
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.927	.577	.959	.067	.732	.001	.186	.660	.011	.908	.731	.	.946	.097	.707
	N	88	88	88	88	88	88	87	87	88	87	88	88	85	88	86
OBSV	Correlation Coefficient	-.100	.311**	.221*	.180	.147	.196	-.006	.170	.267*	.360**	-.059	-.007	1.000	-.165	.101
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.361	.004	.041	.097	.178	.071	.959	.119	.013	.001	.595	.946	.	.129	.362
	N	86	86	86	86	86	86	84	85	86	85	85	85	86	86	84
CSE	Correlation Coefficient	.224*	-.024	.066	-.490**	-.111	.043	.234*	-.002	.051	-.123	.058	.178	-.165	1.000	.239*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.035	.826	.540	.000	.302	.691	.029	.983	.636	.255	.594	.097	.129	.	.026
	N	89	89	89	89	89	89	87	88	89	88	88	88	86	89	87
ADPTN	Correlation Coefficient	.034	.188	.275**	-.218*	.039	.004	.030	.042	.073	-.027	-.031	-.041	.101	.239*	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.755	.081	.010	.042	.717	.969	.783	.698	.500	.805	.776	.707	.362	.026	.
	N	87	87	87	87	87	87	85	86	87	86	86	86	84	87	87

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

APPENDIX 6 – Publications

A MODEL FOR ADOPTION OF CLOUD COMPUTING FOR E-LEARNING: A CONCEPTUAL VIEW

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Abstract

The cost of higher education (HE) is constantly increasing with less public funding and yet the demand is increasing causing institutions to search for ways of reducing costs while improving delivery as well as competitiveness in the global market. Cloud Computing (CC) is a potential solution because it has the capability for end users to seamlessly access data and applications from multiple devices and platforms. However, research findings indicate that the rate of adoption and subsequent deployment within higher educational institutions (HEIs) compared to other sectors is low. This study is therefore investigating the responsible factors and their dynamics. As universities readjust to demands due to globalization and internationalization, it is expected that the findings of this research will aid HEIs to make informed strategic decisions about adoption of CC technology.

Keywords: Cloud computing, cloud adoption, e-learning, higher education.

1 INTRODUCTION

Though e-learning presents some challenges, it provides, among others, flexibility of access to learning materials, just-in-time delivery (JIT) and perceived cost effectiveness [1,2]. The shift from the traditional learning methods is mostly accounted to by the use of the internet thereby resulting in changes in the learning content, delivery and modes [3].

Cloud computing (CC) leverages the power of the internet to provide computing resources (software, platform, infrastructure etc.) to the end users on demand. There are four main deployment cloud models: private cloud, community cloud, public cloud and hybrid cloud [4]. Private cloud is provisioned for one organization but may comprise of multiple users. Community cloud is provisioned for exclusive use of a particular community of consumers with shared values and concerns e.g. security, policy compliance confidentiality. Public cloud infrastructure is provisioned for open use by the general public. This cloud model is usually favoured by the academic institutions. Hybrid cloud infrastructure comprises two or more clouds (private, community or public). In hybrid cloud the uniqueness of each of the entities are maintained but with a standardization in technology to enable data application portability [4].

CC can be seen as a new direction that significantly enhances e-learning [5] with new functionalities [6]. These functionalities include storage and collaboration tools which are essential for research, peer-review, critique and publication of materials [7]. However, despite these functionalities, only about 4% of cloud technology use is in the academia with 96% comprising of industrial sectors and services [8]. In order to address the low rate of CC adoption [9] a sound theoretical framework and research model is needed to identify factors and their relationships affecting the adoption of cloud computing (CC) for e-learning in higher education institutions (HEIs). It will also be interesting to ascertain from the study if and how the deployment models may affect adoption by HEIs. Considering that IT is being delivered

as a service, this research will aid the development of a model of adoption of such innovative IT services like CC that is driven by sound economics and high speed digital networks.

The rest of this paper presents method, CC adoption for e-learning, model development and hypotheses, conclusion and future studies.

2 METHODOLOGY

The main research methods are quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods. This research will employ the quantitative method following the positivist paradigm that has been used successfully in Information Systems (IS) research [10]. Primary data will be collected using survey conducted electronically and systematically analyzed using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) to identify results and patterns as well as evaluate the research predictive model [11].

This study is limited to a particular area of higher education (HE): universities in Scotland. All the 15 universities were selected so as to cover all geographical locations. The sampling population will be limited to technical staff (Information and Communications Technology ICT), academic staff (computing/IT, teaching/research) and other IT staff as they are at a better position to give opinion on the subject matter.

3 CLOUD COMPUTING ADOPTION FOR E-LEARNING

Attitude, intention, acceptance, adoption and diffusion have all been used as an indicator to measure adoption in various contexts by different authors. Most of these studies did not define the terms acceptance, adoption and diffusion but describes adoption as covering both intention and actual use [12]. Adoption is defined as the decision to make full use of an innovation as the best course of action available whereas diffusion refers to the accumulated level of users of an innovation in a market [13]. Adoption has also been described in phases that include investigation, research consideration and decision making in order to introduce new innovation in the organization [14], whereas diffusion is the decision to implement the technology after adoption.

From the foregoing, we describe adoption as the decision of the higher education institutions (HEIs) to accept, deploy and make use of innovative technology like CC to facilitate and improve e-learning. This means that the HEIs we study may not use CC but they must at least make a decision to accept, adopt and deploy it. CC leverages an e-learning ecosystem with reliable, flexible, cost-efficient, self-regulated and quality of service (QoS) guaranteed infrastructures [15]. Consequently, HEIs' adoption of CC technology will enable them to access new techniques, methodologies, processes and applications while also meeting their dynamic needs and demands [16].

Models and theories used in IT/IS adoption include but are not limited to Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE), Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI) and Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE). However, it is hoped that the four theories used in this research are adequate for providing variables that would give insight into the factors that have hindered adoption with the aim of facilitating adoption of CC for e-learning. The next section describes in detail how the model was derived.

4 MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Literature on IT adoption suggests that most researchers conduct studies by integrating theories used in information system with frameworks that cover the contextual antecedents. Hence, a theoretical model for adoption of IT in institutions may consist of a combination of innovation adoption theories and contextual framework of IT adoption [17]. Furthermore, a search through the literatures shows that no single theory or model can be used to explain attitude, behavior and various determinants in the context of IT adoption. Hence, by combining theories and models, it is hoped that these

antecedents will be synthesized and developed into a model that may be used to enhance adoption of cloud computing for e-learning.

In this research, four underpinning theories and models were combined to develop the proposed conceptual model of CC adoption for e-learning. This was done by using constructs from existing models that are relevant to the study. The combined theories and models used are TAM: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU), TOE: Relative Advantage, Complexity, Compatibility, Top Management Support, Technology Readiness, Institution Size, Competitive Pressure, Trading Partner Pressure, DOI: Triability, and Observability; and Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE). These theories and how they are combined will be explained in subsequent sections.

On one hand, it may be argued that TAM deals with individual's adoption of technology. However, PU and PEOU are of relevance for individuals' intention to accept and use technology within institutions [18]. These two determinants according to TAM are fundamentally important for attitude towards using a particular system and also determine intention to use and the actual usage behavior. On the other hand, the decision to integrate any technology within an institution lies with the management. However, successful implementation is exemplified by individual adoption pattern [19]. Thus, it is important to understand what influences individuals' adoption pattern thus, the integration of PEOU and PU from TAM construct in building the research model. It may also be difficult to assess certain parameters for e.g. relative advantage. Therefore, respondents would be assessed based on their perception of such parameters e.g. perceived relative advantage.

Figure 1. Underpinning theories

4.1 Technology acceptance model (TAM)

TAM appears to be the most widely used theory of IT adoption. In addition, TAM has also undergone extensive validations, applications and replications over the years to predict the use of information systems [20] and has proven to be very popular in IT/IS adoption. TAM was first introduced [18] after being adapted from the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) [21].

It is pertinent to note that PEOU and PU of TAM were considered relevant to this study as they explain individuals' intention to accept and use technology in organizations [18]. PEOU is the extent to which a person believes how effortless using a system would be. Similarly, PU is the degree to which a user believes that using the technology will improve his or her work performance [22]. We therefore believe that if CC technology is perceived as easy to use and less complex, HEIs should be willing to adopt it for e-learning. From the foregoing, we can hypothesize that:

H_{1a}: There is a positive relationship between PEOU and the intention to adopt CC for e-learning.

H_{1b}: There is a positive relationship between PU and the intention to adopt CC for e-learning.

4.2 Technology-organisation-environment (TOE)

The three features of TOE framework are technological, organizational and environmental contexts [23]. Technological context describes existing and new technologies relevant to the HEIs. Organizational context describes the characteristics of the HEIs such as scope, size, complexity and management structure. Environmental context in relation to HEIs describe the challenges, competition and government regulations.

In technological context, CC is perceived to have advantages over non cloud based systems. For example they are scalable and flexible i.e. services provided to end users can be scalable based on their computing capabilities and individual demands. Computing resources can also be accessed remotely (virtualization) irrespective of place and time. They also offer services that include but not limited to software, platform, infrastructure and data. These perceived advantages also include instantaneous allocation of resources based on demand, and without the need for human interaction, can be accessed via multiple platforms, dynamic facility based on demands as well as capability to be measured and metered [4]. From the foregoing, we can hypothesize that:

H_{1c}: There is a positive relationship between perceived relative advantage and CC adoption for e-learning.

On one hand, easy to use, less complex and compatible systems will facilitate its adoption. Therefore, CC technology should fit into existing systems. On the other hand, innovations that are incompatible with existing ones are slow to integrate within new systems [24]. From the foregoing, we can hypothesize that:

H_{1d}: There is a negative relationship between perceived complexity and CC adoption for e-learning.

H_{1e}: There is a positive relationship between compatibility and CC adoption for e-learning.

Security is the absence of unauthorized access to, or handling of the system state [25]. For the purpose of this research, we defined security as the ability of the institution to safeguard against unauthorized access to cloud computing services including availability, integrity, confidentiality and privacy of data. Global IT security spending has increased by 7.9% reaching \$81.6 Billion in 2016 [26] and data security has been one of the main areas of concern in cloud computing [27,28,29]. Security drives as well as inhibits adoption of cloud due to resources being devoted by the cloud service providers [28]. There appear to be lack of standardization concerning security in the cloud. Different authors and researchers have proposed different models [28]. Despite the lack of consensus [30], more is being done to address the situation [29,31].

From the foregoing, it is evident that if adopting institutions are confident that their data are secure, available when needed, their privacy and confidentiality are protected; and access are granted only to the authorized personnel, then they are more likely to adopt cloud computing. We can therefore hypothesize that:

H_{1f}: Security is significantly and positively related to CC adoption for e-learning.

PEOU is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would be free of physical and mental effort [18]. In the case of CC, cloud vendors provide the infrastructure and the platforms for the end users. The end users do not have to worry about physical machines, intricacies and interconnectivity and maintenance. It can therefore be argued that since all the internal workings have been dealt with by cloud providers, CC maybe perceived to be non-complex and easier for the end users to use them. Thus, we hypothesize that:

H_{1g}: There is a correlation between complexity and PEOU.

PU is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance [18]. If the use of CC would enhance user's performance (in the form of perceived relative advantages over non CC systems), then it could be argued that that a relationship exist between PU and perceived relative advantage. In essence if a systems is perceived to be useful then it may have perceived relative advantages over other systems as that system is seen or perceived to improve user's performance. Thus, we hypothesize that:

H_{1h}: There is a correlation between perceived relative advantage and PU.

We refer to HEIs' technology readiness as the existence of ICT infrastructure. Similarly, technology readiness also includes human resources [32, 33, 34, and 35]. It is expected that CC technology will seamlessly be integrated into these already existing ICT infrastructures.

H_{2a}: There is a positive relationship between institutions' technology readiness and CC adoption for e-learning.

Management support in HEIs comes in different forms, from financial [36] to creation of enabling environment [37,38]. However, integrating resources and reengineering processes involved in the implementation makes management support increasingly important in adoption [9]. Therefore, we hypothesize that:

H_{2b}: There is a positive relationship between HEIs top management support and CC adoption for e-learning.

The impact of size on adoption is still being argued [39]. In this research, we describe size to include number of students, employees and revenue streams of the HEIs [40]. Thus, we believe that HEIs with more students will generate more internal revenues in addition to the external revenues therefore, have greater chances of adopting CC. Thus, we hypothesize that:

H_{2c}: HEI's size is significantly and positively related to institution's ability to adopt CC for e-learning.

The availability of funds to HEIs may impact on their decision to adopt CC technology [40] thus; we extended TOE to include cost. In this research, we describe cost as the expenditure made by HEIs to acquire innovative technologies like CC. it is expected that adoption expenditure and implementation is proportionate to the expected benefits of such technologies [32] thus, CC technology for e-learning should be affordable in comparison to already existing systems. Therefore, we hypothesize that:

H_{2d}: There is a positive relationship between cost and CC adoption for e-learning.

Environmental factors impact on innovation adoption and organizational performance [23]. Similarly, it also impacts on the availability of such innovations and the extent to which they are accepted [41].

We describe competitive pressure as the pressure being exerted by other HEIs or educational and technical partners (IT equipment) like Microsoft, Oracle and Cisco, or from students who require high level of service and support [33]. IT is in a constant flux and in order to be competitive, HEIs must continue to adopt the latest technological innovations as well as reinvent themselves. Thus, we hypothesize that:

H_{3a}: There is a positive relationship between competitive pressure and CC adoption for e-learning.

Trading partners (customers, suppliers and network) can also influence organizations to adopt innovations [41]. For HEIs, trading partners may include software and hardware suppliers and technical partners. A complex IT innovation requires facilitating technology portfolio, organizational structure and emphasis on environmental strategy [42]; organizations however, may depend on their

trading partners for their IT design and application tasks [34]. Therefore, pressure from these partners is expected to have some form of impact on the decision to adopt the technology. Hence, we hypothesize that:

H_{3b}: There is a positive relationship between trading partner pressure and CC adoption for e-learning.

4.3 Diffusion of innovation theory (DOI)

Innovation involves new ideas, practices or artefacts with characteristics (relative advantage, complexity, compatibility, trialability and observability) that can influence its adoption [13]. This section focuses on trialability and observability since relative advantage, compatibility and complexity have already been discussed under TOE framework.

Trialability is the opportunity to test an innovation before deciding to adopt it [13]. Trialability therefore can be said to be directly related to actual system use or ease of use and in effect to adoption of CC. The ability to try out, test or experiment should facilitate the adoption of an innovation.

Observability occurs when an innovation is visible and available and everyone has it, then individuals are more likely to adopt the innovation. At a point when it becomes pervasive, those who would not normally adopt such innovation may consider adopting it. CC technology can be accessed from multiple devices and platforms; and is available over a broad range of networks [4]. Roger's theory shows a positive correlation between observability and adoption. It is believed that when potential adapters observe the new technology being introduced, they are likely to adopt that technology.

Some researchers on one hand argued that the model could still be improved with additional internal organizational characteristics and external factors as it appears limited [43]. On the other hand, some are of the opinion that the model already has both external and internal dimensions [44]. The external dimension can be quantified and measured while in the internal dimension, the perception is relative to the individual. Therefore, factors including economic and technological and perhaps the perception of the end users (staff and students) seem to be consistent with the external dimension of Rogers' attributes. Thus, DOI could be used to explain the acceptance of CC for e-learning.

Though DOI was formed on the basis for adoption and diffusion theory [13], subsequent theories of diffusion that have been used in various studies also identified characteristics that are consistent with that of Rogers about perception, attitude and adoption of CC and IT/Information System IS technologies [45, 46] and it is hoped that these consistencies will be further validated in this research. The foregoing discussion leads to the two hypotheses below:

H_{4a}: There is a positive relationship between trying out a technology and adoption of that technology.

H_{4b}: Observability and the pervasive nature of a technology are positively related to the adoption of that technology.

Furthermore, if end users have the opportunity to test or experiment with CC before adoption, they can explore its characteristics including how easy it may be to use it if they eventually adopt it

. In effect, we hypothesize that:

H_{4c}: There is a correlation between trialability and PEOU.

4.4 Computer self-efficacy (CSE)

Although this research is focused on HEIs adoption of CC for e-learning, CSE has also been used to show uses of new technology [47, 48, 49, and 50] and behavioral factors which in essence may impact on CC adoption. CSE refers to individuals' belief in their capabilities to use computer in diverse situations [51]. However, it is individuals who make up organizations including HEIs. Self-efficacy has

been found to have a major role to play in the adoption of various technological innovations like CC [49].

Individual's capability to adopt new technology is a major factor in the willingness to accept new technology [48]. As stated earlier (section 4), the decision to integrate any technology within an institution lies with the management. However, successful implementation is exemplified by individual adoption pattern [19] thus, it is important to understand what influences individuals' adoption pattern.

Fear of computers, confidence and ability, perceived difficulty of use, not understanding the importance of technology and lack of motivation affect the acceptance and use of computers [48]. It could therefore be argued that the aforementioned factors may affect HEI managerial decisions in institutions, as those unlikely to use them are also unlikely to recommend them for adoption by their institutions. Hence, we can hypothesize that:

H₅: There is a positive relationship between individuals' belief in their capabilities to use technology and CC adoption for e-learning.

The hypotheses presented and discussed in the foregoing pages result in the high level research model at figure 2.

Figure 2: High level model

Figure 3: Detailed research model and hypotheses

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STUDY

The research so far is at conceptual level. To investigate the adoption of CC in e-learning of higher institutions, the study has used as underpinning theories TAM, TOE, DOI and CSE. Variables from these theories have been selected to develop a theoretical model which will be operationalized into a survey questionnaire to empirically test the model. The 15 universities in Scotland will be used for the study. It is hoped that when collected data are analyzed, it will reveal the reasons for the low adoption rate of CC among the HEIs thus, helping them to strategically realign and compete in the current competitive HE market.

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Factors to Consider when Enhancing the Use of Web 2.0 Technologies in Higher Education: Students' and Lecturers' Views for Quality Use

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Abstract

Learning quality enhancement with Web 2.0 tools needs good implementation framework and lessons from best practice. However, there is not much research on what constitutes best practice in the implementation of Web 2.0 in learning activities. This research seeks to contribute to research in this area by seeking the views of students on increased adoption of Web 2.0 social tools in learning activities. The research reports on the observational study carried out in one university in Scotland and a quantitative study carried out in the first stage of the research. The research reveals that an increase in the use of Web 2.0 tools in higher education is positively related to perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, prior knowledge, motivation to use, social factors and performance expectancy. The findings in this research show students and lecturers' views on how increased use of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning in higher education can be achieved.

1. Introduction

Learning quality enhancement with Web 2.0 tools needs good implementation framework [1]. However, there is the need to seek for best ways to have successful implementation and not much research on good practice and its results are reported in literature. It has been observed that since 2005 the main effect of the initiative of technology enhanced learning in England, Scotland and Wales has been to bring to the knowledge of the institutions the relationship between technology provision, the use of technology and its impact on students learning [2]. Research shows that the impact of using technology in learning is hard to distinguish from the effect of other supports that may accompany its use, especially when pedagogical changes that take place have no relationship with technology [2]. It is certain and evident, though, that higher education can be transformed significantly through changes in the way learners and teachers understand and play their roles in learning and teaching activities, with or without technology [3] hence, the need to evaluate learning quality after introducing a new technology. The rest of this paper will present the literature review, the problem

of study, the research questions, the method adopted to answer the questions, data collection, analysis, discussions, key findings, conclusion, limitations and future studies.

2. Literature

2.1 Constructivist view of Learning with Web 2.0 Tools

Learning with technologies make learning more active, social, reflective and in context [4]. However, the gap in knowledge is in the design practice of what should happen and what actually happens in technology enhanced learning [5]. Constructivist's view of learning is useful and promises development in evolving instructional design [6]. Although literature reveals that there are arguments amongst researchers on the validity of the constructivist approach on the use of Web 2.0 technologies, few researchers exist who agree with the constructivist view on learning with technology and they also report effective implementation strategies for students and teachers [1][7][8][9]. This view of learning is important in research because the underlying foundation aligns with the corresponding method that helps learners to make linkages between functional requirements of everyday life and the knowledge gained from potential learning experiences [10][11]. One of the greatest challenges of technology in learning is determining whether it will provide real world contexts that engage learners in complex problem solving. Research has shown that the use of Web 2.0 technologies such as blogs, wikis and podcasts provide learners with opportunities to be involved in their learning, generating connections with their prior knowledge and linking it with the present activity as they communicate, reflect and discuss using blogs, discussion forums or any other platform [12] [4]. Active learning helps learners to develop ideas and this brings about meaningful learning.

2.2. Meaningful Learning

Learning becomes more meaningful when it involves demonstrating competence and increasing participation in contributing to a social community [4]. Thus, meaningful learning can be achieved with the use of dialogue-based Web 2.0 technologies e.g. blogs and discussion forums will increase relationships among groups of learners and also it is a way to enhance the social basis for learning [9]. Meaningful learning occurs when learners engage in active, constructive, intentional, authentic, and cooperative learning and this is the primary and ultimate goal of education [9].

2.3. Reflection in Learning

Reflection in learning is a very important way of supporting learning [4]. Feedback from peers and lecturers can help students to reflect. If reflection is done every day or week it can improve their critical thinking skills [13][14].

Reflection takes place in an individual learner's personal learning or as a part of a broader dialogue, within the context of the class or of social interactions with peers and teachers or trainers. Hence, introducing Web 2.0 tools for learning activities can enhance reflection in a group activity. Driscoll [4] acknowledged that integrating new experiences with prior knowledge and reflecting upon this process helps to build new mental models and create new meanings.

2.4. Web 2.0 Technologies Integration

Redecker et al. [16] confirm that many institutions are integrating Web 2.0 technology tools to support students' learning and to support students' engagement in learning activities. However, integration of these technologies to be used in these institutions will depend on (1) realistic policies; (2) organizational support; and (3) integration planning [16], [17]. Jucevičienė and Valinevičienė [7] observed in their research and concluded that there are four main factors that determine adoption of social network usage in higher education: (1) academic service support, (2) student support (3), social and cooperate learning, and (4) achievement presentation. However, not much research has reported using these implementations strategies and choice of platforms.

2.5. Choice of Platform or Tools to Use

Kennelly's research [8] suggested that decision on the tools to be used for online learning should be based on two criteria: (1) students should be comfortable with an interface; and (2) it should be associated with

their learning styles. Kennelly recommended platform environments such as course management systems as being very useful to enhance the effective use of Web 2.0 technology in learning [8].

3. Problem

Literature reveals that meaningful learning involves demonstrating competence of increasing participation and contribution to a social community. Presently, many young persons are engaging with Web 2.0 technologies for social purpose and rarely transfer these skills for collaborative learning purpose. Hence, three research questions about factors that would increase Web 2.0 technology tools in learning activities in higher education were considered.

3.1. Research Questions

1. What are the views of students regarding the use of Web 2.0 social technologies in learning activities?
2. How can adoption of Web 2.0 tools be increased to achieve better students' learning experience?
3. How can these technologies be used effectively by students?

4. Method

This research used three sources of data collection: answers to closed ended questions, free comments in the survey and data from a focus group's discussion and interviews. A descriptive and content analysis of individual views from students who participated in the complimentary teaching with blogs in a LMS was used to explain their experience following-up on previous quantitative research study [18] in this educational institution. The qualitative data collection was carried out in order to find the extent to which the quantitative and qualitative approaches agree in this research [19]. An observational approach with a focus group and a survey with questionnaire (open and closed ended questions) were used to evaluate the focus group students. The observational study would be discussed in six stages as detailed in the next section.

4.1. Stage 1: Introducing Blogs in Learning Activities

The researchers introduced the use of blogs in a class (made up of college, undergraduate, postgraduate and company staff) in order to complement teaching and also to observe the students' behavior with the use of these tools. The students were told the importance of

interaction and participation in all learning activities and also advised to communicate by asking questions, commenting and responding to posts from the teacher and from each other. The students were also told to look out for an invitation to join the class blog (see the link to the LMS that was set up for the students by the researchers:

https://www.coursesites.com/webapps/login?new_loc=/webapps/portal/frameset.jsp.

4.2. Stage 2: Starting a Group Blog

The students were all registered on this learning management system (LMS) and their login details were generated and sent to them via email.

Figure 1. Login page for the LMS (course site)

Figure 2. Username and password login

Figure 3. Group blog for Oracle database design

Figure 4. Announcements on the LMS

4.3. Stage 3: Posting Blogs

Blogging was used to complement lectures during the teaching of Oracle database and SQL. This medium was used to distribute objectives, summaries, and questions from the lecturer. The researchers started with very simple tasks and progressed to more difficult ones.

4.4. Stage 4: Checking Blogs and Reminding Participants to Post

The instructor also sent announcements and reminders on commenting and posting blogs. The researcher checked for invitation acceptance and also checked for the number of people who commented, read the posts or downloaded the labs and feedbacks. The teacher followed up students' participation (to enhance it) through sending emails to get them to blog. She also asked the students whether they were aware of

blogging and its usefulness in learning. These questions were raised in the class and the majority of them raised their hands, indicating that they know about blogging. The lecturer followed up by asking how many of them blog. Only one hand was up. The students were encouraged to practice their coding in their personal blogs and also post blogs or questions in the class blogs; they were advised to ask questions any time using the group blog. The facilitator continued to post the usual weekly objectives, summary of lectures and questions on the teaching objectives to the LMS.

At the end of the module, out of ten (10) registered students, 3 students dropped out without attending any class and one (1) student was not regular, while six (6) attended classes regularly. At the end of the sixth week, the teacher observed that six (6) students were logged in the LMS every week, but none posted a blog or commented on the teacher's blogs; they rather downloaded their feedback and lab materials.

5. Qualitative Data collection

The lecturer interviewed the students in group discussions after they consented to participate in the research that took place in three universities in the United Kingdom. The group discussed their reasons for not posting blogs or commenting during the learning period using blogs. This discussion was audio recorded and it lasted for one hour. The researcher started with two questions which then led to other questions regarding how the constructs in the research affected their behaviour and how the constructs can be applied to enhance the use of the Web 2.0 tools for learning.

The questions were:

1. What were your reasons for not posting blogs or commenting?
2. What will motivate your participation and enhance your learning with blogs?
3. What support do you think students' need considering active, inactive and non-participatory students?

The questions were answered in a group discussion and their answers were analysed and summarised as discussed in the next section and in tables and figures showing evidence [20].

In analysing the answers, this research adopted a method used for observational study [20]. Four students had similar responses to the first question. They said that their lack of use was because it was not compulsory (no motivation to use) and also because participation with blogging did not attract any score or grade towards the professional certification they were studying for (no performance expectancy). One of them added that he would prefer to look up on the internet for what he does

not understand or ask friends rather than discuss or ask the teacher (facilitating conditions and social factors).

Two students said that participation should have been graded and scores added to their final grades for the module since they were studying to gain university credit (motivation and performance expectancy) which would have served as motivation for quality contributions.

One student did not like the use of social tools for learning and he did not see himself using blogs in future or even using any social tool for learning. He still felt that it was not useful and that he preferred to read and understand rather than discussing with anybody and distracting himself.

In addressing the second question, five students suggested a phone app to make participation easy and quick.

These students suggested it would have been easier to blog with a simple app (ease of use) rather than an LMS. Blogging would have been better on their phones (facilitating conditions) because accessing the LMS always on their laptop before posting a blog was not something that was interesting or exciting (motivation, facilitating condition and ease of use) and there was no motivation especially because it was not compulsory. Two students said that they did not know how to use the platform to access the blogs (prior knowledge) and one added that it was not easy to access the blog tool in the LMS (ease of use and facilitating conditions). They added that if they were guided on how to get to the tools in the LMS platform or how to use the LMS generally they would have been motivated. However, they were not bothered because it was not compulsory to participate.

The students were also bothered about support and checking how they respond to questions for feedback and to encourage participation. These views are analyzed and presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Question 3 was addressed in different ways and their views are summarised in Table 2. This observational study with students yielded similar constructs unveiled in the quantitative study in the same university [21]. Further explanations on how these constructs can be applied in achieving increased use and improve the quality of learning with Web 2.0 tools were unveiled in the students' discussion (see Table 3).

This research revealed that supporting student engagement is very important and this agrees with research by Baxter et al. [1]. Students' motivation (see Table 2) is also revealed and this is in line with lecturers' concern for quality use of technology [21]. Table 2 shows categories of users that could exist and how they can be supported for quality learning activities with Web 2.0 technologies

Figure 5. Database teaching with blogs

Table 2. Support to students

Participants	Behaviour	Handling student support
1	Copy and paste users	a) Check for such responses. b) Email and ask them to try to construct their knowledge from different sources and always acknowledge their sources.
2	Little participation users	a) Email these users and assign roles to them. b) The role they play online may stir up more participation.
3	Poor quality contributors	a) Discuss some of the posts and seek responses from others. b) Allocate marks to participants so as to attract quality contribution.
4	Very active and quality contributors	Commend or congratulate the very active users and encourage them by assigning them key online roles so that they would be motivated to keep contributing online.
5	Very irregular users	Check with them to be sure they have access to internet and send emails to them encouraging them to participate.
6	Very active users with prompt responses which however lack quality	Assign key roles to them making them the last set of people to send input thereby making these students to summarise quality input.

Table 3. Application of the Constructs in Implementation

Construct	Implication
Perceived usefulness	Give users reasons for online collaboration and also tell them the usefulness of this participation in their learning processes.
Social factors	Get students to start and move together in learning groups and encourage activities using interventions such as emails.
Motivation to use	Encourage students to write constructively and also ask them to collaborate with others by giving feedback to each other and participating in peer review.
Behaviour	Frequently check their online activities and encourage them to use Web technologies to support themselves in their learning and to establish a network of learning using technologies.
Facilitating conditions	Ensure that users have access to institutional or personal ICT facilities; also support users at different stages of learning activities when needed.
Ease of use	Ensure that the platforms or tools used for learning activities are reasonably easy (not requiring much training effort) to serve as motivation to users, and this also enhances confidence and frequency of use.
Prior knowledge	Get users to be familiar with the platform or tools so that they are motivated to use it frequently.
Performance expectancy	Give users a clear importance of participation that relate with reward and expectation in performance in test assignments, in order to motivate quality participation.

5. Analysis of Qualitative Study

After the implementation with blogs with 10 students who were registered to take Oracle Database and SQL in trimester three (a six weeks' programme), it was observed that there was still a low utilization of Web 2.0 interactive tools (group blogs) by students. The analysis also revealed the need for students to be guided at different stages in order for them to participate effectively. However, the surprising findings were in the evaluation of students' usage of the LMS. The students frequently accessed the LMS to download course content, lab materials but did not read the blogs or posted blogs; neither did they comment on the blogs posted by the instructor.

The qualitative study unveiled eight themes: ease of use, motivation, compulsion, training, guide, inadequacy of knowledge, relationship of the activities with their performance improvement, and support. The data also provided suggestion on how these constructs can be applied to increase the use of Web 2.0. These themes were similar to the constructs (see Table 3) measured in the first phase of this research using the survey. It also agrees with existing research [22], [23], [24]. The qualitative data validated the constructs in the quantitative data (see Table 3).

Table 3. Interview themes and survey constructs

Themes in interviews	Corresponding construct in survey
Not compulsory	Motivation
No grades	Performance expectancy
Better blogs with mobile app in mobile phone	Facilitating condition
Not easy to use	Perceived ease of use
Like to share with Friends	Social factors
Did not have much understanding of blogging	Prior Knowledge

6. Quantitative Study

The quantitative study in previous study measured eight constructs: ease of use, motivation, facilitating condition, prior knowledge, social factor, performance expectancy and perceived usefulness. These constructs were validated with data collected from 270 participants (203 student and 76 lecturers [21]).

7. Comparison of the Quantitative and the Quantitative Study

The qualitative data and the quantitative data analysis agree in this research. The quantitative data validated the constructs in the conceptual model in the

first phase of the research [18] and also confirmed similar constructs in this qualitative study with explanation to understand how these constructs are implemented. Thus, the study developed an enhanced model of Web 2.0 acceptance as shown in Figure 6.

8. Key Findings

The qualitative data analysis revealed that technologies for learning activities need to be easily accessible, simple, easy to use, and have tools that are easy to find.

The students need guidance on how best to use and where to find these tools in the platforms (e.g. Learning Management systems (LMS)) especially if students are new to the system. This agrees with the work in existing research [16], [8].

The use of these tools for learning could be achieved when usage and participation is made mandatory.

Adding grades or scores on participation and commenting on post and adding the grade to overall students' performance would influence behavior in using these tools.

Attitude towards use can be enhanced where there is awareness. There should be provision of training on how to use these tools for those not familiar with the tools, platform, or application. This agrees with an existing research [1].

The tools or applications should be readily available online and offline to cater for those with limited internet facilities or poor internet signals.

Another implication for practice from this study is that adequate measures need to be put in place to encourage students and academics to use Web 2.0 technologies for learning. This also agrees with Baxter et al. [1] research.

9. Conclusion

The data collected were analysed and it confirmed the results of the analysis from previous quantitative survey with major constructs in the research model for effective use of Web 2.0 in learning activities [18]. The findings reveal that the constructs (perceived usefulness, facilitating conditions, prior knowledge, social factors perceived ease of use, performance expectancy) influence behavioural intention. These constructs are important factors that influence acceptance and effective use of Web 2.0 technology tools for learning. The interview results agree with the quantitative results that validated the research model which contained factors that would influence the use of Web 2.0 technologies in learning in higher education in Scotland. All the hypotheses of the model were validated.

Figure 6. Enhanced model of Acceptance of Web 2.0 in learning in higher Education

The interviews conducted after the experimentation revealed that more than half of the students attributed their lack of use to three problems: not being easily accessible, not being motivated, and not perceiving the usefulness. One third of the students needed to be guided on using these technologies for effective learning. The students who needed guidance were not familiar with the platform and with using blogs for learning.

The research used the LMS evaluation tool and observed that the students frequently accessed the LMS but did not participate in posting blogs or commenting on the blogs posted by the lecturer and this was very surprising. A more comprehensive list of key factors observed to be accountable for failure of students to use these tools are scaffolding, support and guidance in addition to motivation, performance expectancy, ease of use and perceived usefulness.

The interviews also revealed that the students would have preferred informal interactive discussion forums (audio, text and video). This research agrees with existing research [1], [15], [19], [20], [21] on the view that quality learning with the use of Web 2.0 technologies for learning in higher education need intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, ease of use, perceived usefulness, facilitating condition as well as prior knowledge and support. A combination of these constructs was used to develop an enhanced model of acceptance and effective use of Web 2.0 technology (see Figure 6).

10. Limitation and Future Studies

The students were not the regular students and were not familiar with the LMS. These students were not trained due to the time required to finish the programme which was a six weeks' short course. They needed to be guided on how to use the platform. Thus this suggests a

future experimentation which will be preceded by the training of teachers and students to encourage effective use of these technologies for learning.

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